

Deliverable report for

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

Project 101058632

Deliverable n°:	D6.9
Deliverable name:	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities
Version:	2.0
Release date:	29.11.2024
Dissemination level:	Public (PU)
Status:	Final
Author(s):	Bruno Vicenzi (EPMA), Gracia Olivenza (ASGMI) Luis Lopes (LPRC), Filipe Neves (LNEG)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Change Records

Version	Date	Changes	Edited by
v1.0	26.11.2024	Draft	Bruno Vicenzi
v2.0	29.11.2024	Adoption of the changes proposed by the reviewers	Bruno Vicenzi

Peer reviewed by WP Leaders:

WP	Leader / Reviewer
1	Filipe Neves (LNEG)
2	Igor Morais (LNEG)
3	Alvise Bianchin (MBN)
4	Patricia Carvalho (SINTEF)
5	Aniruddha Ray (RGS)
6	Kenan Boz (EPMA)
7	Luis Lopes (LPRC)

Deliverable beneficiaries:

WP / Task
All WPs and Tasks

1 TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Table of contents.....	3
2	Abbreviations and Acronyms.....	6
3	Executive summary.....	7
4	Introduction: structure of WP6 and general plan of activities.....	8
4.1	Objectives of WP6.....	8
4.2	Structure of WP6.....	8
4.2.1	Tasks.....	8
4.2.2	Deliverables and Milestones.....	10
5	Task 6.1: Specific project dissemination and communication tools.....	13
5.1	Project Website.....	14
5.2	EPMA newsletters.....	22
5.3	Social Media.....	24
5.3.1	Activity on Twitter/X.....	25
5.3.2	Activity on LinkedIn.....	26
5.3.3	Activity on YouTube.....	28
5.3.3.1	START Webinar #5 (Thermoelectric Devices and Applications).....	28
5.3.3.2	Starty volumes 1-4 (published on 21 st March 2024).....	29
5.3.4	Activity on Twitch.....	29
5.3.5	Activity on SlideShare.....	29
5.4	START Newsletter.....	32
5.4.1	Newsletter issue #1.....	32
5.4.2	Newsletter issue #2.....	33
5.4.3	Newsletter issue #3.....	33
5.4.4	Newsletter issue #4.....	33
5.4.5	Newsletter issue #5.....	34
5.5	START comics - Starty.....	34
5.6	Updated leaflet.....	34
5.7	Videos.....	38
5.7.1	START introductory video.....	39
5.7.2	Other videos uploaded in earlier periods.....	40
5.7.3	Other videos uploaded in the last 6 months.....	40
5.7.3.1	Webinar #5.....	40

5.7.3.2	Starty volumes 1 to 4.....	40
5.8	Continuous Evaluation of D&C Performance.....	40
5.8.1	KPIs.....	40
5.8.1.1	LinkedIn.....	43
5.8.1.2	X (formerly Twitter).....	45
5.8.1.3	Videos	46
5.8.1.4	Project website.....	46
5.8.1.5	Newsletter	53
5.8.2	WP6 meetings.....	53
5.8.3	Continuous reporting on Funding&Tender website	53
6	Task 6.2: Technical and scientific dissemination.....	54
6.1	Events list.....	55
6.2	Events covered in M25-M30.....	57
6.2.1	5 th START free webinar, 7 June 2024	57
6.2.2	40 th International and 20 th European Thermoelectric Conference (ICT/ECT 2024) in Krakow, Poland (30 th June - 4 th July).....	58
6.2.3	Congreso Geológico de España 2024 in Avila, Spain (2 nd – 6 th July).....	61
6.2.4	XX Congreso Internacional sobre Patrimonio Geológico y Minero, Madrid 15 - 18 September 2024.....	62
6.2.5	START Industrial Workshop “Re-structuring of EU value chain on thermoelectrics - From supply chain to end user”, Kastrup (Denmark), 26 th September 2024.....	63
6.2.6	START online training course, 25 th September-3 rd October 2024	66
6.2.7	START at the MacaroNight on 27 th September 2024	68
6.2.8	Euro PM2024 Congress & Exhibition, Malmö (Sweden), 29 th September - 2 nd October 2024.....	68
6.2.9	Conference at the "Comú de Particulars" Cultural Center in La Pobla de Segur (Catalonia, Spain), 2 nd November 2024.....	70
6.3	Events in preparation.....	72
6.3.1	Conferences, Exhibitions, Workshops, Webinars.....	72
6.3.1.1	Clustering Workshop “Supporting the Critical Raw Materials Act: Research Projects in the European Union”, Brussels (Belgium), 10 th December 2024	72
6.3.1.2	PDAC, 2-5 March 2025, Toronto (Canada)	75
6.3.2	Training Activities:	75
6.4	Publications	75
6.4.1	EPMA newsletters	75
6.4.2	START on the Innovation News Network	76
6.4.3	Publication on “Geo-Temas”	77

7	Task 6.3: Training activities.....	78
8	Task 6.4: Clustering	79
8.1	Clustering strategy.....	79
8.1.1	Internal clustering	79
8.1.2	External clustering.....	80
8.1.2.1	Key institutions and actors	80
8.1.2.1.1	ERHASE Cluster.....	80
8.1.2.1.2	THERMOS Project.....	82
8.1.2.1.3	XTRACT Project	82
8.1.2.1.4	Clustering Workshop at the RMW2024	82
8.1.2.2	Link with communication and dissemination activities.....	82
8.1.2.3	CORDIS	82
8.1.2.4	Clustering Database.....	83
8.1.2.5	Invite key actors to project meetings	84
8.2	Key events and meetings	84
9	Task 6.5: Final event.....	86
10	ANNEX I – START Newsletter – Issue #5 – November 2024.....	87
11	ANNEX II – START article on “The Innovation Platform”	116

2 ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan (for START)
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ExCom	START's Executive Committee (WP leaders)
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KoM	Kick-off meeting
MTOD	Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination
PM	Powder Metallurgy
RMW	Raw Materials Week
TEG	ThermoElectric Generators
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP	Work Package

3 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable reports on the activity of WP6 “Dissemination and Communication” in the period 1st June 2023 – 30th November 2024¹ (M25-M30 of the START project).

It covers the endeavours within the following tasks (the ones running in said period):

- Task 6.1: Specific project dissemination and communication tools
- Task 6.2: Technical and scientific dissemination
- Task 6.4: Clustering

Task 6.3 (Training) is also running, but it is being reported in D6.11 also in May 2025 (M36), so it is not touched upon here if not to mention some activities that can also be considered as Dissemination.

The activities for D&C, that are reported in this deliverable, include:

- Updates to the START project website.
- Updates on the Social Media accounts (LinkedIn, YouTube, X/Twitter, Twitch, SlideShare).
- A new 4-sided A5 leaflet with results from the first part of the project.
- The fifth issue of the public biannual newsletter “RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE”.
- The fifth free webinar (hybrid).
- The Industrial Workshop in Copenhagen in September 2024.
- A virtual training Workshop on «Mining Environmental Liabilities» in September 2024.
- Organisation of a Side Event at the EU Raw Materials Week in Brussels (to happen in December 2024).
- Publication on “The Innovation Platform” and “Geo-Temas”.
- Dissemination at events (EPMA Summer School, training webinar, workshops, congresses and others, in person and online), including some upcoming events (Side Event at the RMW 2024).
- Strong clustering with Thermos and other projects.

The KPIs set for the D&C activities have been met (not considering those that have a longer deadline). The KPIs to be achieved later appear to be attainable.

The clustering activity has continued in such a way that the database on EU-funded projects, which was created at the beginning of the project, has been further updated and completed. Contacts led to important events co-organised, as the Industrial Workshop and the upcoming Clustering Workshop.

¹ For practical reasons linked to text reviewing and submission, some details related to month of November 2024 could not be reported and will be dealt with in the next deliverable of the same series, D6.10 (M36, May 2025).

4 INTRODUCTION: STRUCTURE OF WP6 AND GENERAL PLAN OF ACTIVITIES

4.1 OBJECTIVES OF WP6

The overall objective of WP6 is to disseminate widely the results of the START project in order to maximise its impact. The key objectives are:

- To raise awareness of all relevant parties (scientific and industrial communities, general public and policy makers) about START project activities in a coherent and consistent manner.
- To ensure an effective dissemination of the technical and scientific results of START project to the scientific and industrial communities.
- To ensure an effective communication of the achievements of START project to the wider scientific and technical communities, policy makers and the general public.
- To elaborate the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) and update it when required.

Various communication activities are envisaged to disseminate the on-going and final project findings:

- Participations in congresses, workshops, webinars
- Training events
- Websites and social media
- Scientific papers
- Newsletters and other publications
- Participation in trade fairs and exhibitions
- Other activities, etc.

All partners are required to collaborate in dissemination and communication by delivering content and executing some dissemination subtasks.

4.2 STRUCTURE OF WP6

4.2.1 Tasks

The activity is organised in 5 Tasks, whose scope and activities will be explained in the main chapters of this report.

- Task 6.1: Specific project dissemination and communication tools
- Task 6.2: Technical and scientific dissemination
- Task 6.3: Training activities
- Task 6.4: Clustering
- Task 6.5: Final event

The GANTT shows that only Tasks 6.1, 6.2, 6.3 and 6.4 have already begun, whereas Task 6.5 will only run in Year 4.

Figure 1: GANTT chart for WP6. M01 = June 2022; M48 = May 2026. Highlighted in orange, the period covered by this deliverable D6.9 (M25-M30).

4.2.2 Deliverables and Milestones

The WP lists 15 deliverables out of a total of 39 for the whole project, but only one milestone, that has already been achieved in M03 (August 2022). The deliverables (all classified as public), also visible in Figure 3, can be grouped in the following categories:

- D6.1 - Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools (M02): This deliverable describes the project's website, addresses the inherent need of the project to develop the START graphical identity, together with all the other online tools designed to support objectives of WP6. *(Submitted and approved)*
- D6.2 - Dissemination and Communication Plan (M03): Document outlining the most efficient strategy and means for implementing the dissemination and communication activities. *(Submitted and approved)*
- D6.3, D6.4, D6.6, D6.7, D6.9, D6.10, D6.12, D6.13 - Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities (M06, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36, M42, M48): Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed. *(D6.3 and D6.4 submitted and approved, D6.6 and D6.7 submitted, D6.9 is the present report, D6.10 upcoming in 6 months)*
- D6.5, D6.8, D6.11, D6.14 - Training activities (M12, M24, M36, M48): Report on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented. *(D6.5 submitted and approved, D6.8 submitted, D6.11 upcoming in 6 months)*
- D6.15 - Final Event (M46): Final event conference report.

Concerning milestones, only one was envisaged, namely Milestone 8:

- MS08: Project Website (M03) - Project website functional and accessible

The website was in fact the key stone of all further dissemination, so it needed to be started as early as possible and was set as a milestone. This milestone has been achieved as planned (declared on 22 August 2022 on the Funding & Tenders Portal, the website being also subject of Deliverable D6.1 submitted earlier and already accepted).

Deliverables												
Work Package No	Deliverable Related No	Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date	Approval Date	Status
WP6	D6.1	D19	Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools	This deliverable describes the project's website, addresses the inherent need of the project to develop the START graphical identity, together with all the other online tools designed to support objectives of WP6.	EPMA	DEC	PU	31 Jul 2022		29 Jul 2022	31 Aug 2022	Approved
WP6	D6.2	D20	Dissemination and Communication Plan	Document outlining the most efficient strategy and means for implementing the dissemination and communication activities.	EPMA	R	PU	31 Aug 2022		30 Aug 2022	06 Dec 2023	Approved
WP6	D6.3	D21	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M6	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2022		30 Nov 2022	06 Dec 2023	Approved
WP6	D6.4	D22	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M12	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2023		31 May 2023	06 Dec 2023	Approved
WP6	D6.5	D23	Training activities - M12	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2023		31 May 2023	06 Dec 2023	Approved
WP6	D6.6	D24	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M18	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2023		30 Nov 2023		Submitted
WP6	D6.7	D25	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M24	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2024		31 May 2024		Submitted
WP6	D6.8	D26	Training activities - M24	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2024		30 May 2024		Submitted
WP6	D6.9	D27	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M30	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2024				Pending
WP6	D6.10	D28	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M36	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.11	D29	Training activities - M36	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.12	D30	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M42	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.13	D31	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M48	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2026				Pending
WP6	D6.14	D32	Training activities - M48	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2026				Pending
WP6	D6.15	D33	Final Event	Final event conference report.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 Mar 2026				Pending

To be completed on the current year
 Deadline approaching
 Submitted
 Approved

Figure 2: List of WP6 deliverables, with deadlines and status.

5 TASK 6.1: SPECIFIC PROJECT DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M01 to M48

The objective of this task is to develop tools and produce materials that will be used during and after the project to disseminate the information about the project, its partners, and its results. According to our proposal, these were the items that needed to be developed:

- The Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) at the start of the project (described in full in Deliverable D6.2 submitted in August 2022) and updated when required (a mid-term update by M24 was made as reported in D6.7, another one will be made at M48).
- As described in Deliverable D6.1 (submitted in July 2022):
 - The Project's Graphical Identity (logo, branding).
 - The START project website (www.START-HEproject.com and www.HE-START.eu automatically redirected to the main address).
 - A special area on the EPMA website (www.epma.com) devoted to the START project.
 - Social Media platforms, in particular:
 - A LinkedIn page for networking with the professional community (managed by EPMA).
 - A YouTube profile for engaging with the greater public (managed by EPMA).
 - A Twitter/X account for business and policy makers (managed by LPRC).
 - A Twitch profile for engagement with young people (managed by LPRC).
 - A SlideShare account for disseminating project presentations globally (managed by ASGMI).
- Leaflets, posters, banners, branded consumables that will be used as advertising material to be distributed in digital and/or physical versions.
- A public biannual newsletter to be distributed in digital and/or physical versions.
- A serious game (see WP7, Task 7.1 and deliverable D7.2)
- Videos about the project (2 generic videos, 1 at the start and one at the end, 3 more focused videos on specific topics).

The tools had been further described in the original proposal as in Table 1.

Table 1: Tools for Dissemination and Communication as indicated in the proposal.

Tool	Purpose	Audience	Due	Quantified target
Project Graphical Identity	A Graphical Identity for the START project (logo and general branding colour schemes, for the website, the social media, mail signatures for partners, and all other uses) will be developed in the first months.	All	M02	-
Project website	Main channel for information and major tool for the visibility of the START activities. Updated frequently, with a blend of status, push and active content, including: project overview; public documents; agenda; articles and news; multimedia. Individuals can also use the website to sign up to the newsletter and social media channels.	All groups	M02 onwards	Visitors: 2000 in year 1 rising to at least 4000 in year 4
Social media	LinkedIn, YouTube and Twitter will be considered as main dissemination channels, Slideshare and Twitch as secondary dissemination channels. LinkedIn supports community management with restricted fora. A YouTube channel will be used to engage with a broader audience by sharing videos, including an introduction to START, short interviews, and selected partner videos.	All groups	M02 onwards	Twitter: 1000 followers in year 1, rising to 2500 by the end of the project ² LinkedIn: 800 followers by the end of the project.
Videos	Some videos are planned for various uses: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A short generic video (0.5-1 min) with simple information, to be used for general awareness about START. • A mid-term longer video, highlighting preliminary project results. • 2 or more short videos focused on different subtopics within the project, with examples of improvements achieved within the project. • A short generic video (0.5-1 min) with simple information, to be used as a summary of the results obtained in START. 	Groups 1-4 1-3 2-3 1-4	M04 M24 M48 M48	Average of 200 views per video (at least 100 total views)
Newsletters	A public biannual newsletter will be circulated to individuals who sign up. The newsletter will include a summary of the activities over a 6-month period.	Groups 1-3	M06 onwards	Demand led but minimum of 500 per semester
Webinars/ seminars/ workshop	Communication of the project outcomes and activities, to share knowledge, ideas and updates.	Groups 2, 3	M06 onwards	Audience of 100 per event
Serious online game	A serious online game for capacity building on raw materials, sustainability and circular economy.	All groups	M24 onwards	Visitors: 300
Other publications	Articles on web-based innovation news services, like the Horizon Magazine, Cordis, and on commercial magazines like Open Access Management	All groups	M06 onwards	Total reach >400000

New achievements will be described in the next pages.

5.1 PROJECT WEBSITE

The project's website has been already developed and reported in deliverable D6.1 ("Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools"), submitted on 29th July 2022. It also constituted the criterion for the achievement of Milestone MS08 ("Project Website (M03) - Project website functional and accessible"), that was declared achieved on 22nd August 2022.

The website address is:

www.START-HEproject.com

Another site address, www.HE-START.eu, is automatically redirected to the main address.

² The Twitter/X KPIs have been reviewed, changing from Followers to Impressions (15k/year in Year4).

The website is continually updated in terms of contents and new features are introduced (new pages, widgets, etc.) if deemed useful.

During the last six months, the period covered by this deliverable, there were some changes in the structure of the website, and some news items, media and documents were added.

Due to the organisation of 2 special events, the Industrial Workshop in September 2024 and the Clustering Side Event at the Raw Materials Week 2024, specific pages have been created, that were directly accessible from the main menu.

The “Industrial Workshop” page is a temporary page (Figure 4) that was published to advertise the organisation of the workshop "Restructuring of EU value chain on thermoelectrics", that was held in Kastrup (Copenhagen, Denmark) on 26th September. In the page, it was possible to download the agenda of the meeting and register for it (via a Google Forms questionnaire). After the event it was removed from the menu but kept stored to use the same format for next events.

Accordingly, the “Clustering RM Event” page (Figure 5) was created with the same format, again in the form of a temporary page, to advertise on the event “Supporting the Critical Raw Materials Act: Research Projects in the European Union” that is being organised for December 10th, 2024. It is still visible in the menu now, although the deadline for registration was the 25th of November, both to keep the attention on it, and due to the fact that late registrants could still be accepted if there will be room in the seminar hall of the Hotel Marivaux.

The screenshot shows a website for an industrial workshop. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'START' logo and links for Home, The Project, Documents, News, Multimedia, Consortium, and Industrial Workshop. The main header features the title 'Industrial Workshop' and 'Re-Structuring Of EU Value Chain On Thermolectrics' with the subtitle 'From supply chain to end user'. A green button indicates 'REGISTRATION CLOSED'. Below this is a table with columns: EVENT TIME, EVENT ADDRESS, FULL PROGRAMME, REGISTRATION DEADLINE, and FREE PARTICIPATION. The table contains details for the event on September 26th, 2024, at the Claren and Comfart Hotel in Copenhagen. Below the table are sections titled 'Why?', 'What?', 'This is A Summary Agenda:', 'Where?', and 'How?'. The 'Why?' section discusses the need for a resilient value chain in Europe for thermoelectrics. The 'What?' section describes the program's structure, including a plenary and breakout sessions. The 'Summary Agenda' lists a detailed schedule from 8:30 AM to 6:00 PM. The 'Where?' section provides the venue location in Copenhagen. The 'How?' section states that registration is now closed and provides contact information for further details.

Figure 4 The temporary page dedicated to the Industrial Workshop run in Kastrup (Copenhagen, Denmark) in September 2024.

Figure 5 The temporary page dedicated to the Clustering Workshop organised as a Side Event of the Raw Materials Week in Brussels (Belgium) at the Hotel Marivaux on 10th December 2024.

On the “Documents” page, two documents were added (Figure 6):

- a new 4-sided A5 leaflet (mid-term leaflet)
- the fifth issue of the Newsletter, published in November 2024

More documents will be made available in the future.

The “News” page is the first place where the info about the events and the news about the project are posted (Figure 7). The news published amount now to 32, as we published 7 in the last 6 months:

1. Register for our 5th webinar on 7th June!
2. START on “The Innovation Platform” Issue 18
3. Register for the Virtual Course “Mining Environmental Liabilities and Secondary Raw Materials”
4. Rewatch our 5th free webinar!
5. The success of the Industrial Workshop
6. The Clustering Event at the RMW2024
7. The publication of Newsletter RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE Issue #5

In the Multimedia page (Figure 8), 1 more item is now available, that is the footage of our Webinar #5, held (hybrid) in June 2024.

Figure 6: Updated Documents page (screenshot taken on 26/11/2024).

Figure 7: The updated News page (screenshot taken on 26/11/2024).

Figure 8: The updated Multimedia page.

5.2 EPMA NEWSLETTERS

EPMA publishes regular newsletters for its members and for interested contacts. These are containing at least the link to the START website if not specific pieces of news. Typically, the weekly E-Mail newsletters are distributed to more than 1600 member contacts and in a reduced version to 400+ non-member contacts. In addition to these, a longer newsletter is published quarterly.

A weekly newsletter, sent on 14th May 2024, contained a news item related to the publication of Issue #4 of the START Newsletter (Figure 9).

One periodic (quarterly) EPMA Newsletter issue (Figure 10), quarterly newsletter #131, published in June 2024, that is a web based³, publication that reaches all EPMA members, also reported the news from START. There also an advertisement for the upcoming Industrial Workshop was included.

³ <https://www.epma.com/epma-newsletter-june-2024/>

[View in browser](#)

EPMA News

[Download the START Project's 4th Newsletter](#)

In the news, you will find reports from START activities: on assessing thermoelectric materials, on LCA and LCC applied to thermoelectrics, and on the Delphi Survey.

[Join the EuroAM LinkedIn Group](#)

Network with fellow AM professionals, and keep up to date with all the activities from EPMA's dedicated Additive Manufacturing Group.

Industry News

[New car registrations: -5.2% in March 2024, battery electric 13% market share](#)

In March 2024, the European Union car market experienced its first decline of the year, registering a 5.2% decrease to 1 million units.

[AMEXCI looks to large-scale Additive Manufacturing with additional Nikon SLM Solutions machines](#)

AMEXCI, located in Sweden, and Nikon SLM Solutions AG, based in Germany, have announced a significant expansion of their partnership.

[UK Centre of Excellence for AM launched by University of Wolverhampton, EOS, and AMCM](#)

The group have announced that they will be launching a new UK Centre of Excellence for Additive Manufacturing.

[MTC PS adds third Hot Isostatic Press at Swedish facility](#)

MTC Powder Solutions (MTC PS), Surahammar, Sweden, has announced its investment in a third Hot Isostatic Press (HIP).

EPMA Projects

<p>START Project Read More ></p>	<p>Address Project Read More ></p>	<p>RESQTOOL Read More ></p>
--	--	---

Upcoming Events

[AM Seminar 2024](#)

4-6 June 2024 - Augsburg, Germany

[Summer School 2024](#)

15 July - 19 July 2024 - Alessandria, Italy

Powder Handling and Flow for Additive Manufacturing

EPIC Meeting on Laser Micromachining: New Developments and Applications at Light Conversion

24-25 September 2024 - Vilnius, Lithuania

EPIC Members can click the "member registration" option and when they register, in the comments section, with "EPIMEMBER2024", to receive a discount on registration.

EPMA
1 avenue du General de Gaulle, 60500, Chantilly

This email was sent to info@epma.com
You've received this email because you've subscribed to our newsletter.

[Unsubscribe](#)

Figure 9: Content of the EPMA weekly newsletter, including the news of the launch of Issue #4 of the START Newsletter (14th May 2024). All weekly newsletters also contain the usual link to the project website.

European Projects

START is making progress towards new thermoelectric devices

The Horizon Europe project START continues its work on creating thermoelectric materials from mine waste minerals, specifically sulphides like tetrahedrites. These materials are intended for use in waste heat recovery devices. New findings on the developed materials are already showing good potential. The EPMA is heavily involved in spreading the project's results, and developing new materials and events related to the project.

A new issue of the "RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE" newsletter, the 4th issue, has been published, and we encourage you to go to the [website](#) and download it for free. If you have missed any previous issues, you can find them all there as well.

Our 4th free webinar, held on 14th March, focused on the powder metallurgical processing of thermoelectric materials, and their assessment. The presenters were Serena Busatto (MBN Nanomaterialia), Damian Karpowicz (GeniCore) and Patricia Almeida Carvalho (SINTEF).

"Our 5th webinar just took place during the Annual Meeting of the project consortium at SINTEF's premises in Oslo, on 7th June. It was dedicated to the topic "Thermoelectric Devices and Applications", with three speakers: Maarten Den Heijer (RGS Development), Hao Yin (TEGnology) and Jean-Yves Escabasse (CEA-Liten and STARTS' Scientific Advisory Board).

START effectively liaised with the EraNet project THERMOS led by TU Dresden and including IFAM Dresden. A meeting was held in IFW Dresden on 11th April and that set the path for a very fruitful cooperation. The first example should be an industrial workshop on Applications of Thermoelectrics that will be held in Copenhagen just before Euro PM2024, on Thursday 26th September. More details will be available during next weeks, so please keep in touch.

If you are interested in the project, check out its website www.START-HEproject.com, and find out more; you can follow also on X, LinkedIn, YouTube, etc. Subscribing to the mailing list on the website will allow to directly receive news about the project, and in particular the newsletter.

Figure 10: Excerpt of the EPMA Quarterly Newsletter #131, June 2024.

5.3 SOCIAL MEDIA

Social media are the tool used by the project to engage the audience, bring them to the website, and in general to disseminate and communicate (also to the wider public) about START activities, results and partners.

The project's social media accounts have been already created and reported in deliverable D6.1 ("Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools"), submitted on 29th July 2022. The START social media are:

- Twitter/X (partner responsible: LPRC): https://twitter.com/START_HEproject
- LinkedIn (EPMA): <https://www.linkedin.com/company/86266991/>
- YouTube (EPMA): <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCHVjEhpVz9uaEgzlCj2lnPA>
- Twitch (LPRC): https://www.twitch.tv/start_he_project
- SlideShare (ASGMI): <https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject/>

In addition to these, an account on the Zenodo service⁴, the Open Data service created by CERN within the OpenAIRE project in 2013, that also offers the creation of a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) number, has been created by LNEG and is used, in parallel with SlideShare, to help us assuring that the rule for OpenAccess publication is fulfilled (see chapter 6.4), together with the publication on our website and social media.

5.3.1 Activity on Twitter/X

START Twitter/X posts have two main goals:

1. Sharing information with the community on the project's goals, objectives, and concept, as well as on the relevant communication activities such as presentations at conferences, the START video, the webinars, workshops and meetings, and online materials and,
2. Sharing how the START project contributes to the main topics of interest, e.g., thermoelectrics, reuse of mining waste, waste heat energy, green energy and sustainability.

During M25-M30 a total of 31 posts were made, spanning from 04/06/2024 to 26/11/2024, and contributing to the following statistics:

- 1) Total number of Followers: 267 (raising from 192 since last 6 months)
- 2) Number of views/Impressions during the period: 4816

Similarly to the previous analysed data (M19-M24), the Total number of Audience (counted as Engagements + Detail Expands + New followers + Profile visits) and Views statistics are around the same values. However, during the presented period data is actually better since it reaches similar values with less posts made (31 posts in this period vs 37 posts in the previous one). Following a trend already observed in the last report, the number of page followers has seen a raise of 75 followers, which is a considerable number for the X platform.

Figure 11 shows the "homepage" of the START Twitter/X account.

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/>

Figure 11: The START X profile (status on 20/11/2024).

5.3.2 Activity on LinkedIn

The activity on LinkedIn continued along the two already established main lines:

- Achieving a larger audience for the START page. This was done mainly by EPMA, using the network available to them. These are the data about followers' growth: 29 November 2022, 142; 6th May 2023, 312; 9th November 2023, 408; 26th April 2024, 515; 28th October 2024, 612. The relative chart is in Figure 12. Followers have been growing steadily to more than 600 in October 2024; as the objective is to reach 800 followers by the end of the project, it is likely that the KPI can be reached, as the last months of activity, with many results to disseminate, will bring new interested contacts to the account.
- Posting project news to bring interest and send interested people to the website, if possible, to let them subscribe to the project's mailing list.

Figure 12: Growth of LinkedIn followers for START.

Occasionally, some third-party news has been published, in order to create some traffic to the page (a similar approach has been followed on Twitter).

Concerning posts, in the period between 10/05/2024 and 09/11/2024⁵ there were:

- 28 posts on the START page (more than 1 per week).
- 80 posts on LinkedIn groups ("EPMA networking group", "Sustainability professionals" group, "Thermoelectrics" group, "Thermoelectric matters" group, "Metallurgy and Materials Science" group, "Global Metallurgist, Metallurgical & Material Engineers Community" group, "Materials Research Society" group, "Materials Research Network" group, "Materials Science Engineer" Group, "American Ceramic Society" Group, "Horizon Europe, Framework Programme for Research and Innovation" Group, and a few others).
- posts on personal accounts (surely more than 12, as this is the number posted by B. Vicenzi, the EPMA main contributor to LinkedIn, on his own account, that lists more than 1900 followers) by members of the consortium, that have been only partly considered in the evaluation of impact, plus other posts on some partners' pages.

See also paragraph 5.8.1.1 for relevant KPIs.

⁵ The previous deliverable D6.6 reported data until 9th May 2024.

5.3.3 Activity on YouTube

On YouTube the activity is lower, as it practically involves the uploading of the videos produced during the project. There are now 15 public videos on the START YouTube channel, for a total of more than 8 h of video time, with video durations ranging from just above 1 m to 1 h 34 m; and about 580 total views. Here follows (Table 2) an update of the data about views acquired on 09th November 2024.

Table 2: Recap of all statistical data for the videos publicly available on the START website as of 09/11/2024.

			Totals=>				
			08:09:59	573	28.1		
Video	Published	Measured	Duration	Views	Watch time (h)	Av. View (s)	Av. %view
START Introductory Video - Starty tells you the basics!	25/10/2022	09/11/2024	00:01:28	125	1.0	00:28	32.6%
START Webinar #01 - 2023-28-02	05/03/2023	09/11/2024	01:03:53	52	3.8	04:24	6.9%
START - 8th March 2023 - Gracia Olivenza (ASGMI)	08/03/2023	09/11/2024	00:01:17	9	0.1	-	-
START - 8th March 2023 - Concepción Fernández Leyva (IGME-CSIC)	08/03/2023	09/11/2024	00:01:19	7	0.1	-	-
START Webinar #02 - 2023-04-26	02/05/2023	09/11/2024	01:17:20	32	0.4	00:48	1.0%
Thermoelectric energy harvesting: principles, challenges and opportunities - D. Crane	12/07/2023	09/11/2024	00:46:50	85	4.7	03:17	7.0%
EuroGeoSurveys' support to EU domestic CRM supply from secondary resources/mine wastes - J. Hollis	14/07/2023	09/11/2024	00:24:33	13	0.1	00:34	2.3%
START partners - Tetrahedrites in European mine waste sites	17/07/2023	09/11/2024	00:46:06	31	1.4	02:39	5.8%
START Workshop - Use of Life Cycle Assessment as an Environmental Impact Tool (E. Santos/A. Braga)	21/07/2023	09/11/2024	00:44:39	38	0.7	01:04	2.4%
START video for the Raw Materials Week 2023	18/10/2023	09/11/2024	00:03:47	24	0.2	00:25	11.0%
START Project - Starty #2 Eng	18/10/2023	09/11/2024	00:02:19	14	0.1	00:26	19.4%
START Webinar #4 "Powder technology for tetrahedrite p type semiconductors"	15/03/2024	09/11/2024	01:33:14	77	7.5	05:48	6.2%
Starty volumes 1 - 3	21/03/2024	09/11/2024	00:06:22	8	0.3	-	-
START Webinar #5 Thermoelectric Devices and Applications	06/09/2024	09/11/2024	01:11:00	52	7.4	08:33	12.1%
Starty 1 to 4	19/09/2024	09/11/2024	00:05:52	6	0.3	-	-

For the last two videos published, here are some more details.

5.3.3.1 START Webinar #5 Thermoelectric Devices and Applications

This is a long video with the footage of the last START webinar. Visualisations on YouTube in 2 months are 52 for a total of more than 7 hours. As stated in the image, this is a performance above average for the channel.

Figure 13: Statistics for visualisations of the START Webinar #5 on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication).

The analysis of visualisation behaviour shows that 12.1% of the users viewed the video beyond the 30s mark, for an average duration of the views of 8m 33s seconds.

Figure 14: Statistics for retention of viewers during the START Webinar #5 (YouTube).

5.3.3.2 Starty volumes 1-4 (published on 21st March 2024)

This video includes all the tables for the first 4 issues of Starty’s comics. The views collected in less than 2 months on YouTube are 6.

5.3.4 *Activity on Twitch*

Twitch has not been used yet.

5.3.5 *Activity on SlideShare*

As already reported in the previous deliverables D6.3, D6.4, and D6.6, SlideShare had been used to host documents prepared that were also uploaded to the website, and some on Zenodo. In the following Table 3 the views collected on SlideShare are shown for each item.

Table 3: Presentations and documents uploaded to Slideshare in previous periods and their performance. In parenthesis, the change from the previous deliverable D6.6, i.e., the status in November 2024).

PRESENTATION/ DOCUMENT	LINK	PERFORMANCE
"Green energy harvesting – State of the art"	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/green-energy-harvesting	61 views (+17)
"Project START: From WASTE to HIGH-TECH", presentation at EU-Latin America Raw Materials Convention 2022 (Santiago de Chile, 3-4 November 2022) given by Daniel de Oliveira (LNEG).	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/project-start-from-waste-to-hightech	31 views (+16)
Presentation at World PM 2022 (Lyon, 9-13 October 2022) given by Filipe Neves (LNEG).	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/presentations-at-world-pm2022	12 views (+2)
START Factsheet in Portuguese.	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/sistemas-sustentveis-de-captura-de-energia-baseados-uma-abordagem-inovadora-de-reciclagem-de-resduos-de-mina	7 views (+2)
START Factsheet in English.	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/sustainable-energy-harvesting-systems-based-on-innovative-mine-waste-recycling	6 views (+1)
START Flyer.	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/start-flyer-254343547	9 views (+3)
START Newsletter Issue #1	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/startnewsletterissue1pdf	22 views (+5)
Starty Explains START – The comics (multilingual)	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/startyexplainsstartpdf	9 views (+4)
START Newsletter Issue #2	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/startnewsletterissue2pdf	26 views (+10)
Powder Metallurgy Review, Spring 2023	https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/powder-metallurgy-review-spring-2023-b6aa/263358173	5 views (+3)
START Newsletter Issue #3	https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/start-newsletter-3/264082754	18 views (+9)
START Supercluster Event Abstract	https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject/startsupercluster2023finalpdf	37 views (+15)
START Newsletter Issue #4	https://es.slideshare.net/slideshow/eu-start-project-start-newsletter-issue-4-pdf/268586918	65 views (+22)

In the last period, few more documents were added to SlideShare (Table 4), for a total of 20.

Table 4: Presentations and documents uploaded to SlideShare in the last period and their performance.

PRESENTATION/ DOCUMENT	LINK	PERFORMANCE
---------------------------	------	-------------

<p>Presentation at “Virtual Course on Mining Environmental Liabilities”: Types of environmental liabilities in mining. Methodology for conducting an inventory of abandoned mines. (Dr. Fredy Guzmán)</p>	<p>https://es.slideshare.net/slideshow/types-of-environmental-liabilities-in-mining-methodology-for-conducting-an-inventory-of-abandoned-mines/273580982</p>	<p>0 views (uploaded on 25th November 2024)</p>
<p>Presentation at “Virtual Course on Mining Environmental Liabilities”: Environmental and health risks related to MELs From risk assessment to rehabilitation (Dra. Virginia Rodríguez)</p>	<p>https://es.slideshare.net/slideshow/environmental-and-health-risks-related-to-mels-from-risk-assessment-to-rehabilitation/273581028</p>	<p>0 views (uploaded 25/11/2024)</p>
<p>Presentation at “Virtual Course on Mining Environmental Liabilities”: Rehabilitation of affected ecosystems: geomorphic approach and practical field examples. Monitoring Suspended sediment in mining spillages. (Dr. Ignacio Zapico)</p>	<p>https://es.slideshare.net/slideshow/rehabilitation-of-affected-ecosystems-geomorphic-approach-and-practical-field-examples-monitoring-suspended-sediment-in-mining-spillages/273581082</p>	<p>0 views (uploaded on 25/11/2024)</p>
<p>Presentation at “Virtual Course on Mining Environmental Liabilities”: START Project: Selection, sampling and laboratory tests for the extraction of tetrahedrites in mining wastes (Dra. Concepción Fernández-Leyva, Dra. Paula Adánez)</p>	<p>https://es.slideshare.net/slideshow/start-project-selection-sampling-and-laboratory-tests-for-the-extraction-of-tetrahedrites-in-mining-wastes/273581122</p>	<p>0 views (uploaded 25/11/2024)</p>
<p>Presentation at “Virtual Course on Mining Environmental Liabilities”: Reuse of Mining Waste in the Manufacturing of Sustainable Construction Materials. (Dra. Patricia Pérez)</p>	<p>https://es.slideshare.net/slideshow/reuse-of-mining-waste-in-the-manufacturing-of-sustainable-construction-materials/273581143</p>	<p>0 views (uploaded 25/11/2024)</p>
<p>Presentation at “Virtual Course on Mining Environmental Liabilities”: Managing the social impact of extractive industries – The intersection between mining and society. (Dra. Sara Bjorn, Dra. Anne Merrill)</p>	<p>https://es.slideshare.net/slideshow/managing-the-social-impact-of-extractive-industries-the-intersection-between-mining-and-society/273581217</p>	<p>0 views (uploaded 25/11/2024)</p>
<p>START Newsletter Issue #5</p>	<p>Lin https://es.slideshare.net/slideshow/start-newsletter-issue-5-start-project-eu/273610090</p>	<p>0 views (uploaded 26/11/2024)</p>

5.4 START NEWSLETTER

The project's Newsletter is published on its website and social media every 6 months, starting from Issue 1 at M06, November 2022. The name was decided among the consortium to be "RECOVER – REFORM - REUSE": this was made to give more appeal to the newsletter. The consortium chose a name that is suggesting that the content will not be just related to START but will be connected with the sustainability solutions imagined, the ideas of recovering (mine wastes, heat), of transformation (of wastes into raw materials for thermoelectric devices, of otherwise dispersed heat into electrical energy), and of reusing (materials and energy achieved to obtain better efficiency).

The information conveyed in the various issues of the newsletter always include general information about START, thermoelectric materials, energy harvesting from waste heat, and linked sustainability topics, including state-of-the-art documents and scientific reviews, updates on project activities, project events and other dissemination topics, with invitation to join events where START will be featured, the description of consortium partners (typically 2 per issue), and all information on the various ways to keep informed about START (links to website, social media, link to the contact and subscription forms, etc.).

Being completely public, the information in the Newsletter must be duly checked in order to avoid IPR management issues. The direct distribution is partly based on a list of subscribers (and partly on social media and other partners networks). To create this list, the website tool for registration is used, and social media posts attract new subscribers to the website tool.

Here we update the distribution data for the first issues, and give some info on issue #5, that was published just before this deliverable.

The KPI foreseen for the newsletter is the distribution to at least 500 recipients for each issue.

5.4.1 Newsletter issue #1

Issue #1 was published on 28th November 2022 (and covered in deliverable D6.3). It consists of 11 pages.

From the website, the newsletter has been downloaded 596 times (10th November 2024), again a strong increase from the figure of 448 (6th May 2024). Downloads will likely continue to increase.

On LinkedIn this issue originally obtained more than 400 impressions, with about 100 clicks and a high engagement rate, and X gave about 900 impressions in the first year. On Zenodo⁶ it was uploaded on 29th November 2022 and was viewed 51 times and downloaded 41 times (data of 10th November 2024). In D6.3 we already documented that it had been delivered to more than 500 recipients; with time, downloads are now close to 500 (counting also clicks on X and LinkedIn, the 500 has been passed), and still increasing.

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/7377126>

5.4.2 Newsletter issue #2

The Issue 2 of the newsletter was first published on 22nd May 2023 (see D6.4) and had more than double pages compared to #1 (23 compared to 11). In D6.4 we already documented that it had been delivered to more than 500 recipients.

From the website, the newsletter has been downloaded 332 times, and we expect more in the next months.

On LinkedIn this issue obtained about 250 impressions in the first months, and X reported about 460 impressions. On Zenodo⁷ it was uploaded on 25th May 2023 and was viewed 59 times and downloaded 36 times (data of 10th November 2024). Thus, downloads are now about 475 (they were 360 in May 2024).

5.4.3 Newsletter issue #3

The Issue 3 of the newsletter was published on 29th November 2023 (see D6.6). It consists of 25 pages, 2 more than Issue #2. In D6.6 we already documented that it had been delivered to more than 500 recipients.

From the website, the newsletter had been downloaded 197 times until May 2024, and on 10th November 2024 the figure has grown to 341. On LinkedIn it had obtained about 1070 impressions, and on X about 460 impressions. On Zenodo⁸ and SlideShare⁹ it was uploaded on 29th November 2023 and on Zenodo it has been viewed 77 times and downloaded 20 times (data of 10th November 2024).

5.4.4 Newsletter issue #4

The Issue #4 of the newsletter was published on 30th April 2024. It consists of 27 pages, 2 more than Issue #3.

The newsletter was uploaded to the website on the Documents page (with reference also in the News page) on 7th May 2024 and was uploaded also to Zenodo¹⁰ and SlideShare¹¹ on 16th May. It was advertised on LinkedIn (7th May 2024) and X (9th May 2024). A mailing to the START mailing list was carried out on 14th May 2024. The launch of Issue #4 was also announced on the EPMA weekly Newsletter for members in the third week of May 2024 and later to non-members (about 1600 and 400 contacts, respectively). A news item on the EPMA quarterly newsletter was sent to all EPMA members (about 1600 contacts) in June 2024.

Downloads from the website amount to 186, whereas on Zenodo views are 46 and downloads 23 (data of 10th November 2024). On LinkedIn the various posts obtained 620 impressions, and on X further 60.

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/7925963>

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/7925963>

⁹ <https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/start-newsletter-3/264082754>

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/10979280>

¹¹ https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/eu-start-project-start-newsletter_issue_4-pdf/268586918

5.4.5 Newsletter issue #5

The Issue #5 of the newsletter was published on 25th November 2024. It consists of 29 pages, 2 more than Issue #4.

The newsletter was uploaded to the website on the Documents page (with reference also in the News page) on 25th November 2024 and was uploaded also to Zenodo¹² and SlideShare¹³ on 26th November. It was advertised on LinkedIn (26th November 2024) and X (27th November 2024). A mailing to the START mailing list will be sent in the next days. The launch of Issue #5 will be announced on the EPMA weekly Newsletter for members in the first week of December 2024 and later to non-members (about 1600 and 400 contacts, respectively). A news item on the EPMA quarterly newsletter will be sent to all EPMA members (about 1600 contacts) later. The data for downloads will be analysed in the next weeks and reported in the next deliverable.

5.5 START COMICS - STARTY

As already explained in previous Deliverables, START is making use of a comics character, “Starty, the robot”, that will be employed as much as possible to make communication more appealing also to those categories in the target that are not too scientifically involved in the subject, including the general public. This character will guide the reader or viewer into the START contents. Starty was already used as the main character in many videos and in the various issues of the Newsletter “RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE”.

Starty strips were also translated in other languages: the first issue in 11 more languages, the 2nd in 12 languages, and the 3rd (and subsequent editions) in 14 languages. The translation effort includes not only the translation of the text, but also the adaptation of each comics balloon to each language, so each version needs to be graphically reworked. The list of languages is the following: Catalan, Danish, German, English, Spanish, French, Italian, Dutch, Norwegian, Polish, Portuguese, Slovak, Turkish, Japanese, Hungarian.

In Newsletter #1, Starty had 2 pages, in Newsletter Issue #2, #3 and #4 3 pages, in Issue #4 and #5 4 pages.

Starty will also be the main character of the “serious game”, that is under development within WP7 activities and will be reported in deliverable D7.2 - Serious Game.

5.6 UPDATED LEAFLET

A second leaflet was prepared in July 2024. The introductory leaflet had in fact been prepared almost 2 years before, and it was felt that it was now time to include in a new version also the achievements obtained by the partners in the first part of the project. Thus, the original 2-sided A5 size was not enough anymore, and the leaflet was enlarged to 4-sides. Roughly, the 2 first sides include general information about the project, whilst pages 3 and 4 contain details on the sites investigated for the collection of tetrahedrite-containing minerals, the collection activity, and the subsequent processing (concentration, high energy ball milling, FAST-SPS sintering,

¹² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14062520>

¹³ https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/eu-start-project-start-newsletter_issue_4-pdf/268586918

characterisation). In addition, some attention to the upcoming production of device, the choice of the application sectors and the supply chain analysis, and the LCA studies, is shown as well.

Here are reported the 4 sides of the new leaflet. It has already been printed and distributed in the following events.

START: SUSTAINABLE ENERGY HARVESTING SYSTEMS BASED ON INNOVATIVE MINE WASTE RECYCLING

AN INNOVATION ACTION PROJECT CO-FUNDED BY THE EUROPEAN UNION VIA ITS HORIZON EUROPE PROGRAMME

MAIN OBJECTIVE

Create a sustainable supply chain for green energy harvesting products

TELLURIUM-FREE THERMOELECTRIC DEVICES

Using a unique technological solution, START is transforming waste secondary sulphide materials in sustainable high added-value components for tellurium-free thermoelectric devices.

START produces advanced p-type materials that incorporate discarded waste secondary sulphides, mainly tetrahedrite, a widely available copper-antimony sulfosalt mineral not containing tellurium, that is rather scarce and must be imported to Europe (mostly from China).

DURATION 48 months (June 2022 - May 2026)

COST 9.19M€ **GRANT** 7.67M€

COORDINATOR LNEG (PT)

Figure 15: Page 1 of the new leaflet with START results.

START: SUSTAINABLE ENERGY HARVESTING SYSTEMS BASED ON INNOVATIVE MINE WASTE RECYCLING

- The use of **mine wastes** as valuable secondary raw materials for the development of advanced energy conversion devices creates an increased economic incentive to eliminate environmentally hazardous tailings.
- A huge amount of the primary energy produced worldwide is **lost to the environment as waste heat**, which can be recovered using thermoelectric devices.
- Opportunity for an **efficient use of resources** and to decrease resource, dependence and waste
- Diversification of the sources of renewable energy production systems using green energy harvesting through thermoelectrics.

In line with:

- European Green Deal
- EU Action Plan on Critical Raw Materials
- EU Action Plan on Circular Economy
- UN Sustainable Development Goals

The infographic is divided into two main sections. On the left, under the 'European Commission' logo, is the 'Action Plan on Critical Raw Materials'. It lists five actions:

- ACTION 3:** Launch research and innovation on waste processing, advanced materials and substitution of critical raw materials
- ACTION 4:** Map the potential supply of secondary critical raw materials in Europe and identify viable recovery projects
- ACTION 5:** Identify priority mining and processing projects for critical raw materials in the EU
- ACTION 8:** Develop research and innovation projects to reduce environmental impacts of raw materials extraction and processing
- ACTION 9:** Develop strategic international partnerships to secure a diversified supply of sustainable critical raw materials, starting with pilot partnerships with Canada, interested countries in Africa and the EU's neighborhood (partially)

 On the right, under the 'SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS' logo, are three goal cards:

- 7 AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY:** Represented by a sun icon with a power button symbol.
- 9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE:** Represented by a cube icon.
- 11 SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES:** Represented by a city skyline icon.

 A cartoon robot character is positioned at the bottom right of the goal cards. The entire infographic is framed by a decorative border of horizontal lines in grey, green, and red.

Figure 16: Page 2 of the new leaflet with START results.

START: SUSTAINABLE ENERGY HARVESTING SYSTEMS BASED ON INNOVATIVE MINE WASTE RECYCLING

ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE FIRST PART OF THE PROJECT

Sites containing mineralogically suitable sulphide minerals for producing the p-type semiconductor thermoelement were identified in various historical European mines, based on the volume of sulphides, the presence and content of tetrahedrite, and accessibility and logistical issues.

Several hundred kg discarded mining waste sulphides were collected where the necessary authorisations were granted.

Figure 17: Page 3 of the new leaflet with START results.

START: SUSTAINABLE ENERGY HARVESTING SYSTEMS BASED ON INNOVATIVE MINE WASTE RECYCLING

- Tetrahedrite-rich concentrates from these minerals were successfully processed via High Energy Ball Milling (HEBM) in a pre-pilot scale (300 g batches) to produce kg scale batches of mineral-derived tetrahedrite p-type powder materials incorporating different amounts of synthetic material.
- Spark Plasma Sintering successfully produced thermoelectric elements. A compatible n-type TE material was also identified.

- Based on simulated performances, two applications have been selected: combined heat and power (CHP) and low-grade waste heat from heavy industry.
- Work is underway to assemble the first TE device of the START project.
- Life cycle assessment (LCA) and life cycle costing (LCC) studies are used for benchmarking.
- Focus Groups and a Delphi Survey were organised to assess the market perspective and the social acceptance.

www.START-HEproject.com

Subscribe to our mailing list there!

 <https://www.linkedin.com/company/start-he-project>

 https://twitter.com/START_HEproject

 <https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject>

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 18: Page 4 of the new leaflet with START results.

5.7 VIDEOS

According to what was planned in the proposal, at least 5 videos were supposed to be produced during the project:

- 2 short videos (0.5-1 min), one at the start of the project to raise awareness and one at the end to summarise results. The language should be suitable for a wider audience; animations or cartoons could be used to attract non-specialists. One video at M04 (September 2022), one at M48 (May 2026).
- 2 longer videos (but still not too long, max 3 min) during the project, focusing on project topics and activities. The target should be more to groups 2-3, i.e., scientists, engineers, and entrepreneurs. Both videos are due at M48 (May 2026)
- 1 detailed video (about 5 min) at mid project (M24, May 2024), highlighting the results of the first part of the project (in fact, this was postponed).

Other videos were imagined, like:

- Interviews with key partners, describing the project or specific topics
- Recording of presentations given in events
- Short ads for specific events or for the “serious game”

EPMA normally is the partner taking care of producing the videos but will ask all relevant partners to help by delivering videos, images, and text. The videos are hosted on YouTube and/or Twitch, embedded in the START website, and posted on other social media like LinkedIn and Twitter/X.

The KPIs decided for these tools are the views achieved: minimum of 100 views per video is the base KPI, and an overall average above 200 views/video is an additional KPI. Social media analysis tools allow collecting further information about the audience (including additional views). We will apply these KPIs to the forecast videos mentioned above, and not to all additional videos.

5.7.1 *START introductory video*

A short introductory video for the project, created in September 2022, where Starty gives the introductory info about START. The video is present on YouTube, the website, LinkedIn and X, plus has been used in many dissemination events.

This is the situation of views on YouTube on 09th November 2024:

- YouTube (published on 25th October 2022):
 - views: 125
 - Average duration of viewing: 0m28s
 - Average view rate, %: 32.6%

As documented in the previous deliverable D6.4, LinkedIn¹⁴ gave immediately about 800 additional views, while X contributed with 60 more impressions with the first post; about 30 more with subsequent posts (these numbers have not been further updated). Thus, the number of views, especially from LinkedIn, largely exceeds the minimum set, and is also way above the average requested of 200.

¹⁴ LinkedIn data are available until 1 year after the publication, after that the posts and their related data are not retrievable anymore.

5.7.2 Other videos uploaded in earlier periods

For the other videos, reference can be made to the previous deliverables submitted and to the chapter about YouTube performance (chapter 5.3.3).

5.7.3 Other videos uploaded in the last 6 months

5.7.3.1 Webinar #5

Full footage of the fourth START webinar, held on 7th June 2024 (1 h 11 m) and published on YouTube on 6th September 2024, where the number of views is 52. On LinkedIn, the posts collected 816 impressions. It might still be posted as a video directly, to collect more views.

5.7.3.2 Starty volumes 1 to 4

This video includes all the tables for the first 3 issues of Starty's comics and was published on YouTube on 21st March 2024. The views collected YouTube are 6, but it has been used in the Euro PM2024 event as looping video.

5.8 CONTINUOUS EVALUATION OF D&C PERFORMANCE

5.8.1 KPIs

KPIs are “a quantifiable measure of performance over time for a specific objective”. Although they are not the same as metrics, in the case of measuring the performance of a website or a social media that is normal.

To assess the dissemination, START collects metrics from the website, and the social media, and compares some selected KPIs to chosen reference values that the project expects to meet of the years. A list of the KPIs chosen, with their reference values, is given in Table 5. Note that the KPI for X has been modified to be more realistic during the revision of the DCP, so that now a KPI on Impressions is envisaged (before the KPIs were on followers, and were deemed to be utterly unattainable, also because of the reduced interest for X in the targeted audience).

Table 5: KPIs considered for D&C activities (after DCP update at M24).

Tool	KPI	Reference value
Project website	Visitors	Year 1: 2000 Year 4: 4000
X	Impressions	Year 4: 15000/yr
LinkedIn	Followers	End:800
Videos	Views	More than 100/video Average 200
Newsletters	Addressees	More than 500/issue
Webinars/ seminars/ workshop	Audience	100
Serious online game	Visitors	300
Other publications	Reach	More than 400000

According to previous project experiences, as already shown in deliverable D6.1 (“Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools”), an Excel file, named Monitoring Tool for

Online Dissemination (MTOD) is used to collect the data of dissemination performance on social media, in order to quantify the audience reached and the interest raised.

This is located on the START SharePoint (its address is [START/Work Packages/WP6 - Dissemination and communication/START Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination.xlsx¹⁵](#)) and contains all the details collected from the different social media posts and contents, and from the website. A view of the present status of the file is visible in the screenshot of Figure 19.

The file allows to calculate total audience and views of the actions, and the ratio between views and audience for each action. In this way, during the project course, priorities about the social media could be given.

The data from MTOD is used to update the Funding & Tender website page on Dissemination (see 5.8.3). At present, almost 550 lines are included in the file; the sum of all audience data is about 7 million and the sum of views is about 100k. Views have had highs of about 1850 (on Twitter) and 1400 (on LinkedIn), with a median of about 120 and an average of about 190 (slightly decreasing from the previous data).

We believe that the overall social media performance can be considered satisfactory: views have a remarkable median and average, so many of the followers actually visualise our content.

¹⁵ Note: this is a private address, not accessible from outside the Consortium.

Figure 19: The Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination (status on 15/11/2024, over 540 activities listed, one per line). In green, data that are considered final (in red, data that are not final but could be finalised as the date is after the expected end date).

5.8.1.1 LinkedIn

For LinkedIn, the number of followers is now above 515 (see also chapter 5.3.2), that is still below the target of 800 followers at the end of the project, but in line with the possibility of reaching the KPI at the end of the project. A plot of the number of new followers (see Figure 20) shows some correlation with the newsletters and the webinars, but also with the times when many invitations to follow the page have been sent (there is a 100 invitations per month limit). Page views, show more than 1000 visitors in 1 year (Figure 21). Impressions reached more than 15000 (Figure 22).

Figure 20: LinkedIn Follower metrics (last 365 days until 26 April 2024).

Figure 21: LinkedIn Page views metrics (last 365 days).

Figure 22: LinkedIn Impressions metrics (last 365 days).

5.8.1.2 X (formerly Twitter)

For Twitter/X the number of actual followers (currently at 267) is still considered to be underperforming, despite this period seeing the greatest raise in percentage of followers when compared to previous period analysis. This general lack of followers on the platform can be mainly explained by the turmoil regarding X itself as a platform (acquisition of Twitter – including the “political” debate about the new owner -, transformation from Twitter into X, monetisation of the platform, present involvement in the US Presidential Campaign for the newly elected president Trump). The newly implemented “paywall” to see the Analytics (statistical data) for X pages is another added problem to the usefulness in communication of the platform as a whole.

The issue with the X platform in terms of KPIs has been addressed by the KPI change from the number of followers to the yearly number of impressions, which is considered to be a better measurement target. The number of audiences reached – counting the number of views/impressions, Likes, Retweets, Engagements, Detail Expands, New followers and Profile visits – reached close to 5500 (more precisely 5438) between 4 June 2024 and 26 November 2024: this number corresponds to real engagement with the project posts.

It must be noted that in addition to these posts, on X, LPRC has in many cases reposted news from other accounts, concerning raw materials, sustainability, thermoelectrics, waste heat recovery, and

similar topics of relevance to START. This helped in growing the followers' base and kept the account busy between project posts. We have not counted these views and impressions, but they surely contribute to the visibility of the account.

5.8.1.3 Videos

The KPIs for video are: at least 100 views each, and an average of 200 views. As we are producing a larger number of videos compared to the original number of 5, it would be really difficult to maintain this as a general rule. We will apply them only to the 5 "institutional" videos. Only the first one has been prepared until now, the introductory video. It exceeds the KPI, considering all views on all platforms and not only on YouTube.

- Introductory video:
 - YouTube: 120 views
 - LinkedIn: about 800 in the first year
 - Twitter about 60 in the first year (so the total amount on social media is about 860 views).

So, the KPI of at least 100 views, and even the average expected of 200 views, are exceeded by far.

For the other videos, we have collected now more than 260 views on YouTube and many more on LinkedIn, both when the videos have been posted directly (e.g., about 300 for the International Women Day videos) and definitely much more as views of the posts.

For the webinar footage videos we felt that the length made them not so appealing, only a few viewers have watched the whole Webinar #1 and #2 events apart from those who were present live. For this reason, the third webinar had been split in three shorter videos, and this paid off especially for the video of the presentation of D. Crane that is the second most viewed.

For Webinar #4 we went back to the full footage video, and this achieved a good response for the moment (more than average in the first 40 days). We did the same for Webinar #5.

A second "institutional" video has been postponed due to the workload and the possibility of including more results by making it a bit later.

5.8.1.4 Project website

Concerning the project website, we remind that the analysis is limited to the data after 17th October 2022 as because of an erroneous setting of Google Analytics all data before that date have been lost.

For all the available periods, these data have been collected:

- Audience (users, new users, numbers of sessions per user, pageviews, pages/session)
- Acquisition
- Behaviour (visited pages)

In the following pages we switch to the new data available for the website (from 5th July 2023 when the change in Google Analytics already mentioned in D6.6 took place).

A chart of the activity on pages in the last 6 months is shown in Figure 23. There are no evident activities linked to bots, so we conclude that all data are linked to "normal" traffic. Some peaks for

some pages are probably linked to the specific advertisement on social media. Please note how the page on the Industrial Workshop is among the most read.

Figure 23: Page Views in the last 6 months for the project website. No particular activities seem due to “bots”.

Figure 24 shows the Audience data for this last period, including Views and Users.

The most visited page is still the home page, and the 7 main pages are in the most visited 8 pages. The Industrial Workshop page was visited a lot, with more than 600 visits in a few months: it was published on 18th June 2024 and the Workshop ran just 3 months later, so it was there roughly for about half of the observed period, and yet it was the second most viewed. Also, the Clustering Workshop page, and the news post about the workshop, are already showing a number of views although having been published at the end of October. The total views of about 4400 would scale on a yearly basis to about 8000/yr, that is about two times the KPI of 4000/yr that is due at the end of the project and growing from the previous period (it was around 6000, and 5000 in the previous 6 months). This demonstrates that the traffic on the website is growing as more events and interesting info is being published.

Per user, the most viewed page amongst the most viewed is now the Multimedia page, followed by the Industrial Workshop and the News pages.

Users were about 2600 (4800/yr) compared to 1700 (3700/yr) for the previous period, thus growing as well.

Sessions are estimated to be about 4700/yr (almost 2600 in this period).

Views-Users				
Period:	26/04/2024	11/11/2024	Days: 200	
Page	Views	Users	Views per user	Average engagement time
Total/365 days	7977.1	4792.5		
Total/average	4371	2626	1.66	25.93
/	1850	1181	1.57	16.75
/industrial-workshop/	639	294	2.17	43.45
/the-project/	336	219	1.53	20.17
/documents/	332	177	1.88	25.55
/multimedia/	225	73	3.08	47.60
/news/	220	109	2.02	39.46
/consortium/	188	127	1.48	28.09
/contact/	88	77	1.14	14.75
/1673-2/	84	68	1.24	12.31
/clustering-rm-workshop/	60	35	1.71	62.17
/register-for-our-5th-webinar-on-7th-june/	55	39	1.41	23.44
/5th-free-webinar/	44	29	1.52	11.72
/come-to-the-start-workshop-in-brussels-on-10th-december/	30	22	1.36	12.32
/projet-workshop/	24	4	6.00	117.75
/watch-the-footage-from-our-4th-webinar-on-powder-metallurgy-in-start/	23	19	1.21	15.11
/our-industrial-workshop-in-copenhagen-was-a-great-day-for-thermoelctrics-in-europe/	22	19	1.16	18.84
/register-for-the-virtual-course-mining-environmental-liabilities-and-secondary-raw-materials/	22	11	2.00	39.36
/1690-2/	12	9	1.33	25.33
/403.shtml	11	10	1.10	0.00
/the-project-scientific-advisory-board-has-been-appointed/	11	11	1.00	29.00
/user.php	11	11	1.00	0.00
/administrator/	9	9	1.00	0.00
/file.php	8	8	1.00	0.00
/watch-the-lecture-by-3drivers-on-use-of-lca-for-environmental-impact-assessment/	8	7	1.14	10.71
/news-we-started/	7	6	1.17	15.50
/recover-reform-reuse-issue-1-our-start-newsletter-is-here/	5	5	1.00	17.40
/starty-is-back-in-13-languages/	5	5	1.00	21.20
/more-than-60-participants-in-starts-first-free-webinar/	4	4	1.00	63.75
/start-featured-on-the-innovation-news-network-website/	4	4	1.00	13.50
/starts-1st-annual-meeting-successfully-run-in-madrid/	4	4	1.00	19.25
/*	3	3	1.00	0.00
/register-for-our-4th-webinar-on-march-14th/	3	3	1.00	148.00
/start-webinar-3-watch-doug-cranes-speech-on-thermoelectric-energy-harvesting/	3	3	1.00	7.00
/author/rrrayez/	2	2	1	0
/iwd2023/	2	2	1	14.5
/join-the-third-webinar-on-may-31st-live-from-our-project-meeting/	2	2	1	0
/start-on-powder-metallurgy-review/	2	2	1	22.5
/download-recover-reform-reuse-issue-3-nov-2023/	1	1	1	0
/epmaadmin	1	1	1	2
/industrial-workshop/ TEGnology ApS	1	1	1	14
/news-start-wpm2022/	1	1	1	0
/recover-reform-reuse-issue-2-is-now-available-may-2023/	1	1	1	0
/start-free-webinar-series-connect-to-our-research/	1	1	1	0
/start-looks-southwest-the-second-start-webinar-connects-to-latin-america/	1	1	1	0
/start-webinar-3-start-partners-share-knowledge-about-tetrahydrofuran-in-europe/	1	1	1	0
/start-webinar-3-watch-julie-hollis-speech-on-the-eus-crm-ambitions-ant-the-role-of-eurogeosurveys/	1	1	1	0
/start-will-speak-in-the-incomess-final-workshop/	1	1	1	0
/starty-comics-starty-explains-start-now-available-in-12-languages/	1	1	1	0
/the-footage-of-the-second-start-free-webinar-dedicated-to-latin-america-is-now-available/	1	1	1	0
/workshop	1	1	1	1

Figure 24: Views and Users data per page for the project website (26/04/2024 to 11/11/2024) and projections to 1 yr data.

Landing page					
Period:		26/04/2024	11/11/2024	Days:	200
Landing page	Sessions	Users	New users	Average engagement time per session	
Total/365 days	4695.7	3465.7	3058.7		
Total/average	2573	1899	1676	24.06	
/	1421	1125	1090	23.75862069	
/industrial-workshop	404	258	239	33.69059406	
(not set)	173	106	0	3.930635838	
/multimedia	119	16	7	16.48739496	
/1673-2	67	61	54	14.26865672	
/documents	52	42	30	41.86538462	
/the-project	41	33	25	31.65853659	
/5th-free-webinar	34	22	21	11.35294118	
/register-for-our-5th-webinar-on-7th-june	33	30	27	35.93939394	
/come-to-the-start-workshop-in-brussels-on-10	25	22	17	36.68	
/news	25	22	13	66.88	
/consortium	21	14	11	28.66666667	
/contact	21	21	20	8.285714286	
/clustering-rm-workshop	20	17	16	71.2	
/our-industrial-workshop-in-copenhagen-was-a	17	17	15	22.70588235	
/register-for-the-virtual-course-mining-enviro	11	8	7	24.36363636	
/user.php	11	11	11	0	
/403.shtml	10	10	11	0	
/administrator	9	9	9	0	
/watch-the-footage-from-our-4th-webinar-on-j	9	7	7	0.1111111111	
/file.php	8	8	8	0	
/watch-the-lecture-by-3drivers-on-use-of-lca-fc	6	5	5	2.833333333	
/news-we-started	4	3	2	36.75	
/*	3	3	3	12	
/projet-workshop	3	3	2	52	
/join-the-third-webinar-on-may-31st-live-from	2	2	2	0	
/recover-reform-reuse-issue-1-our-start-newsle	2	2	2	0	
/register-for-our-4th-webinar-on-march-14th	2	2	2	0	
/start-featured-on-the-innovation-news-netwo	2	2	2	10	
/starts-1st-annual-meeting-successfully-run-in-	2	2	2	24.5	
/author/rrayez	1	1	1	0	
/download-recover-reform-reuse-issue-3-nov-2	1	1	1	0	
/industrial-workshop/ TEGnology ApS	1	1	1	14	
/more-than-60-participants-in-starts-first-free-	1	1	1	0	
/news-start-wpm2022	1	1	1	0	
/recover-reform-reuse-issue-2-is-now-available	1	1	1	0	
/start-free-webinar-series-connect-to-our-rese	1	1	1	0	
/start-looks-southwest-the-second-start-webin	1	1	1	0	
/start-on-powder-metallurgy-review	1	1	1	8	
/start-webinar-3-start-partners-share-knowled	1	1	1	0	
/start-webinar-3-watch-doug-cranes-speech-or	1	1	1	0	
/start-webinar-3-watch-julie-hollis-speech-on-t	1	1	1	0	
/start-will-speak-in-the-incomess-final-workshc	1	1	1	0	
/starty-comics-starty-explains-start-now-availa	1	1	1	0	
/the-footage-of-the-second-start-free-webinar-	1	1	1	0	
/the-project-scientific-advisory-board-has-beer	1	1	1	0	

Figure 25: Sessions and Users data per page for the project website (26/04/2024 to 11/04/2024) and projections to 1 yr data.

The distribution by countries (Figure 26) in the past were led by USA and Portugal; in this period, the USA are still on top, but now followed by the Netherlands, India (big increase from previous period) and Germany, with Portugal only 5th. Most of the main countries have increased and even more than doubled the users. Visibility is clearly extended to the whole world.

Looking at the sources for connections to the website (Figure 27), most happen directly via typing in the address bar in the browser (probably using Favourites bookmarks), followed by Google searches. LinkedIn is the 3rd contributor, then Sendinblue (and Brevo), the provider of our mailing service, so clicks on the mails that we deliver to our mailing list. Bing, Baidu (Chinese search engine) and Twitter (t.co) are also at the top of the list. A Japanese service (peltier.moo.jp) brought some traffic, probably linked to the Industrial Workshop. Zenodo was this time used by many visitors. Some other referrals are via project partners' websites (EPMA, LNEG, GeniCore, 3drivers, LPRC), and to events where START is included in the useful links (for instance the InComEss Final Workshop). The Innovation News Network banner also led to some traffic.

Country	26/04/2024	11/11/2024				Days:	200
Country	Users	New users	Engaged session	Engagement rate	Engaged sessions per user	Average engagement time	
United States	288	287	30	0.10	0.10	4.31	
Netherlands	143	143	112	0.48	0.78	34.94	
India	136	135	51	0.31	0.38	15.52	
Germany	93	86	62	0.43	0.67	47.40	
Portugal	90	79	139	0.63	1.54	77.86	
Ireland	86	86	17	0.17	0.20	6.12	
Spain	85	81	81	0.51	0.95	54.49	
France	78	72	72	0.53	0.92	70.64	
Austria	64	64	19	0.27	0.30	14.42	
Poland	59	54	40	0.44	0.68	93.14	
Denmark	54	50	63	0.54	1.17	54.02	
Finland	52	50	9	0.15	0.17	5.50	
Japan	47	45	34	0.52	0.72	76.26	
China	39	39	1	0.03	0.03	0.36	
Belgium	37	34	25	0.42	0.68	34.86	
Italy	33	31	49	0.55	1.48	110.36	
United Kingdom	31	28	18	0.47	0.58	47.00	
Norway	29	27	19	0.53	0.66	28.41	
(not set)	23	23	10	0.43	0.43	10.09	
Sweden	21	19	14	0.56	0.67	37.67	
Canada	17	19	5	0.26	0.29	2.06	
Brazil	12	12	10	0.56	0.83	59.42	
Romania	11	11	4	0.31	0.36	16.73	
South Korea	11	11	10	0.71	0.91	56.82	
Switzerland	11	11	8	0.57	0.73	26.45	
Vietnam	10	10	1	0.10	0.10	5.20	
Iran	9	8	7	0.58	0.78	16.78	
Singapore	9	9	9	0.56	1.00	129.44	
Greece	8	8	9	0.09	1.13	56.25	
Türkiye	8	8	5	0.56	0.63	51.88	
Australia	7	7	3	0.38	0.43	42.86	
Thailand	7	7	1	0.11	0.14	3.43	
Ukraine	7	7	2	0.20	0.29	6.57	
Colombia	6	6	3	0.50	0.50	7.00	
Croatia	6	5	3	0.33	0.50	25.33	
Russia	6	6	1	0.13	0.17	2.33	
Sri Lanka	6	6	3	0.50	0.50	11.83	
Uganda	6	6	3	0.43	0.50	26.00	
Slovakia	5	3	9	0.64	1.80	545.00	
South Africa	5	5	1	0.17	0.20	11.20	
Bangladesh	4	4	3	0.75	0.75	26.50	
Israel	4	4	2	0.50	0.50	78.00	
Morocco	4	4	1	0.25	0.25	7.75	
Peru	4	3	1	0.25	0.25	58.00	
Taiwan	4	4	4	0.80	1.00	41.00	
Cuba	3	3	2	0.67	0.67	141.00	
Czechia	3	3	2	0.50	0.67	53.33	
Egypt	3	3	3	1.00	1.00	16.00	
Hong Kong	3	2	1	0.33	0.33	23.00	
Indonesia	3	3	2	0.67	0.67	14.33	
Pakistan	3	3	3	1.00	1.00	22.67	
Philippines	3	3	1	0.25	0.33	0.67	
Venezuela	3	3	1	0.33	0.33	2.00	
Algeria	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	4.50	
Bulgaria	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	2.50	
Chile	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	91.50	
Congo - Kinshasa	2	2	2	1.00	1.00	29.00	
Hungary	2	1	1	0.50	0.50	15.50	
Iraq	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	22.00	
Latvia	2	2	0	0.00	0.00	1.50	
Malaysia	2	2	0	0.00	0.00	1.00	
Qatar	2	2	0	0.00	0.00	3.00	
Argentina	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Bosnia & Herzegovina	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	4.00	
Botswana	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Dominican Republic	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	15.00	
El Salvador	1	1	1	0.50	1.00	52.00	
Ethiopia	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Ghana	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Kenya	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	27.00	
Kosovo	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	7.00	
Lithuania	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Malta	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	31.00	
Mexico	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	1.00	
Montenegro	1	0	1	0.20	1.00	42.00	
Nigeria	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	7.00	
North Macedonia	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	32.00	
Saudi Arabia	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Serbia	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Slovenia	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Tanzania	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	
United Arab Emirates	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	133.00	

Figure 26: Users and Sessions by Country data for the project website (26/04/2024 to 11/04/2024).

Sources							
Period:	26/04/2024	11/11/2024			Days:	200	
Session source/medium	Sessions	Engaged sessions	Engagement rate	Average engagement time per session	Events per session	Event count	
(direct) / (none)	1292	422	0.33	19.42	4.11	5307	
google / organic	536	244	0.46	26.11	4.86	2603	
linkedin.com / referral	270	132	0.49	24.61	4.74	1281	
6fgo6.r.ag.d.sendibm3.com / referral	117	23	0.20	8.97	3.39	397	
9uxmp.r.sp1-brevo.net / referral	53	21	0.40	18.57	3.96	210	
t.co / referral	34	23	0.68	52.24	8.47	288	
bing / organic	33	16	0.48	27.61	5.88	194	
peltier.moo.jp / referral	29	21	0.72	53.59	5.41	157	
baidu / organic	27	0	0.00	0.00	3.00	81	
lnkd.in / referral	27	16	0.59	27.85	3.37	91	
zenodo.org / referral	19	13	0.68	33.21	6.68	127	
(not set)	16	0	0.00	49.81	4.38	70	
lneg.pt / referral	16	13	0.81	62.06	8.94	143	
asgmi.org / referral	11	10	0.91	93.45	7.36	81	
genicore.eu / referral	11	7	0.64	194.91	6.27	69	
epma.com / referral	9	4	0.44	44.67	5.89	53	
ecosia.org / organic	7	2	0.29	22.71	3.71	26	
innovationnewsnetwork.com / referral	7	6	0.86	46.43	7.57	53	
mail.google.com / referral	7	3	0.43	17.29	5.00	35	
6fgo6.r.a.d.sendibm1.com / referral	6	2	0.33	5.50	3.50	21	
es.search.yahoo.com / referral	6	3	0.50	66.17	7.00	42	
ntp.msn.com / referral	5	4	0.80	27.40	6.60	33	
fct-systeme.de / referral	4	0	0.00	0.00	2.25	9	
groups.google.com / referral	3	2	0.67	102.33	10.33	31	
duckduckgo / organic	2	1	0.50	278.00	12.00	24	
geology.sk / referral	2	2	1.00	39.00	9.50	19	
incomess-project.com / referral	2	0	0.00	0.00	2.50	5	
l.facebook.com / referral	2	1	0.50	22.50	4.00	8	
macaronight.eu / referral	2	1	0.50	8.00	3.50	7	
mbn.it / referral	2	2	1.00	16.00	5.00	10	
yahoo / organic	2	1	0.50	151.00	17.00	34	
3drivers.pt / referral	1	1	1.00	103.00	8.00	8	
canva.com / referral	1	1	1.00	0.00	3.00	3	
enlit.world / referral	1	0	0.00	8.00	4.00	4	
erias.xyz / referral	1	0	0.00	0.00	3.00	3	
eurogeosurveys.org / referral	1	1	1.00	44.00	4.00	4	
facebook.com / referral	1	0	0.00	0.00	3.00	3	
he-start.eu / referral	1	1	1.00	11.00	4.00	4	
localhost / referral	1	1	1.00	372.00	8.00	8	
m.facebook.com / referral	1	0	0.00	0.00	3.00	3	
perplexity.ai / referral	1	0	0.00	0.00	3.00	3	
scanned.page / referral	1	0	0.00	0.00	3.00	3	
suche.t-online.de / referral	1	0	0.00	5.00	4.00	4	
tegnology.dk / referral	1	1	1.00	94.00	4.00	4	
us16.admin.mailchimp.com / referral	1	1	1.00	12.00	3.00	3	
xtract-project.eu / referral	1	0	0.00	0.00	2.00	2	
xtrafficplus.xyz / referral	1	0	0.00	0.00	3.00	3	

Figure 27: Users and Sessions by Sources and referrals data for the project website (26/04/2024 to 11/04/2024).

Globally, we can consider the website performance even more satisfactory than in previous periods, that is also understandable as the project is running well and begins to deliver its important results and attract views on the website due to the many Dissemination events created.

5.8.1.5 *Newsletter*

Concerning the newsletter, the distribution through the START mailing list now comprises just above 200 names. As mentioned elsewhere, EPMA sends the link to download the various Newsletter issues to about 1600 EPMA member contacts via its weekly E-Mail Newsletter and in subsequent Newsletters to non-member contacts (about 400).

Thus, especially via the EPMA distribution, the target of 500 has been exceeded by far for all issues of the newsletter; clearly it must be correlated with the actual downloads recorded, but data for Issue #1 have grown above the 500 mark and this could happen with time for all subsequent issues.

Downloads show that they continue to grow even 2 years after the first publication, as new readers that get in touch later go back and download previous issues.

5.8.2 *WP6 meetings*

During this semester, many meetings were organised for specific discussions, in particular for organisational and clustering reasons:

- 21 May 2024 WP6 Industrial Workshop organisation (LNEG, EPMA, SINTEF, TEGnology, RGS, MBN, LPRC, THERMOS partners) (online)
- 31 May 2024 WP6 Industrial Workshop organisation (LNEG, EPMA, SINTEF, TEGnology, RGS, MBN, LPRC, THERMOS partners) (online)
- 13 June 2024 WP6 Industrial Workshop organisation (LNEG, EPMA, SINTEF, TEGnology, RGS, MBN, LPRC, THERMOS partners) (online)
- 26 June 2024 WP6 RMW Side Event organisation (LNEG, EPMA, ASGMI) (online)
- 05 September 2024 WP6 RMW Side Event organisation (LNEG, EPMA, ASGMI) (online)
- 11 October 2024 WP6 Meeting with XTRACT (LNEG, EPMA, ASGMI, XTRACT partners) (online)
- 16 October 2024 WP6 Meeting on Newsletter content (LNEG, EPMA, GeniCore) (online)

The rest of the arrangements were discussed via E-Mail, bi- or multilaterally.

5.8.3 *Continuous reporting on Funding&Tender website*

The WP Leader (EPMA) is responsible of regularly updating the information on Dissemination and Communication in the relevant section in the project's Continuous Reporting on the Funding&Tender website. There are three pages dedicated to these topics on the portal: "Publications", "Dissemination" and "Communication".

At the latest, an update must be made before the end of each reporting period, as at each periodic report, all the information present in the Continuous Reporting section is automatically compiled to create Part A of the Periodic Technical Report. This was done in August 2023 (M15), and for the moment the only other changes have been made, either automatically or manually, on the Publications page. The "Communication" and the "Dissemination" pages are not updated.

6 TASK 6.2: TECHNICAL AND SCIENTIFIC DISSEMINATION

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M01 to M48

All partners submit papers in relevant conferences, congresses, exhibitions, and scientific journals to give information on the results of the START project.

- Relevant EPMA events (for the PM community mainly):
 - The EuroPM and/or WorldPM Congress and Exhibition series (a project booth is foreseen)
 - The EPMA technical seminars by sectors (Functional Materials, Hot Isostatic Pressing, etc.)
 - Sectoral Group meetings, e.g.:
 - European Functional Materials Sectoral Group (EuroFM)
 - European Hot Isostatic Pressing Sectoral Group (EuroHIP)
 - Environment, Health, Quality and Safety Working Group (EHQS).
- International Conference on Thermoelectrics (ICT/ECT/ACT conference series), and other conferences to be defined by the consortium.
- Special dissemination seminars and presentations (webinars or in person) on specific project-related topics:
 - contributions from the consortium
 - selected external speakers
 - ads on dedicated printed or online magazines (e.g., Journal of Degraded and Mining Lands Management, Journal of Environmental Management, Environmental Earth Sciences, Environmental Science and Pollution Research, Mine Water and the Environment...)

External events to communicate to the public and to other scientific and industrial communities and improve the awareness of the energy and sustainability issues in the public: EPMA and other consortium partners will take part in

- At least 2 external events and exhibitions per year
- Possibly Science Festivals and Fairs (e.g., the European Researchers' Night) to communicate the scope of the project and improve the awareness of the energy and sustainability issues in the public.

Specific KPIs will be introduced to quantify the impact of project dissemination.

Publications and presentations in conferences, seminars and congresses are strongly encouraged: all consortium partners should try to organise a technical participation in an event to disseminate a part of the work carried out in START. This will broaden the audience for the project topics and in the end will create the condition for successful exploitation.

Thus, maybe with some exceptions, we expect that during the course of the project almost all partners will submit papers in relevant conferences, congresses, exhibitions, and scientific journals to give information on the results of the START project.

Addressing communities that are outside those already covered by the consortium members activities and by the standard journals, magazines and conferences/events is also rather important for an innovative project like START. For this reason, the plan is to try addressing external

communities by publishing well balanced papers and articles in more general magazines, or news services/websites (the Horizon Results, the Horizon Magazine, also suitable generic magazines, like for instance the Open Access Government magazine).

6.1 EVENTS LIST

In order to select the events where the partners, individually or as consortium, should take part, and take materials concerning the project, a “START Events List” is established and regularly updated by the WP6 leader (EPMA) on the START SharePoint and every partner will collaborate by giving information on possible events.

In this Excel file, the following information is collected for each event:

- Name of Event
- Priority: the partners are asked to evaluate what is the priority to give to this event in order to try maximising the impact by optimising the effort.
- Date of start of event
- Date of end of event
- Physical/Online/Hybrid: if available, information on the type of participation requested.
- Website: where possible, the link to obtain fresh info about the event
- Location: where the event will be held (in case, “online”)
- Type of audience: scientific (what sector), industrial (what sector), general (what composition) etc.
- START Booth: whether a START booth should be present at the event
- Partner Booth: whether a START partner booth should be present at the event (including name of partner)
- START lectures/papers: in case a presentation is given, details on the topic (e.g., “Generic project presentation” or a specific topic)
- START lecture/paper date: when the presentation will happen
- Presenter: who is going to present
- Reference partner: the partner who will be coordinating the participation
- Attendees: expected number of attendees

The list is the basis for discussion, in the meetings, about participation at the various events.

In Figure 28 the present status of the list is shown.

Event	Priority (1=high)	Date start	Date end	Physical /Online/ Hybrid	Website	Location	Type of audience	START Booth	Partner Booth	START lectures/papers	START lecture/paper date	Presenter	Reference partner	Attendees
EGU - European Geoscience Union (every year around April/May)	-	Apr-May 24		Physical	https://www.egu.eu/	Vienna (Austria)	Raw materials/mining							
EIT Raw Materials Summit (every year around April/May)	-	Apr-May 24		Physical	https://www.eitrawsummit.com/	Brussels (Belgium)	Raw materials/mining							
2024 MRS Spring Meeting & Exhibit	1.00	22/04/2024	26/04/2024	Physical	https://www.mrs.org/meetings-events/spring-meetings-2024	Seattle WA (USA)	Materials	No		Technical presentation		A. Ray	RGS	
Hannover Messe 2024 (ENERGIZING A SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRY)	3.00	22/04/2024	26/04/2024	Physical	https://www.hannovermesse.de/en/	Hannover (Germany)								
Conference on Industrial Technologies IndTech 2024	n.d.	03/06/2024	05/06/2024	Physical	https://indtech2024.eu/	Namur (Belgium)								
5th START Webinar	1	07/06/2024	07/06/2024	Hybrid		Oslo (Norway)				TE devices			LNEG	
40th International & 20th European Conference on Thermoelectrics (ICT/ECT) 2024	1.00	30/06/2024	04/07/2024	Physical	https://ict2024.aah.edu.pl/en	Krakow (Poland)	Thermoelectric Academic					Maarten Den Heijer	RGS	
EPMA Summer School 2024	1	17/07/2024	21/07/2024	Physical	https://summerschool.epma.com/	Alessandria (Italy)	PM community	-	-	Thermoelectricity experience?		H. Yin?	EPMA	
Sustainable Minerals '24	n.d.	2024, Jul?		Physical	https://mei.eventsair.com/sustainable-minerals-22/									
Researchers' Night 2024	1	27/09/2024	27/09/2024	Hybrid	https://maie-sklodowska-curie-actions.ec.europa.eu/ever	Many	Academic, wide	-	-	?		?		
BSc/MSc free online training seminar/workshop	1	25/09/2024	03/10/2024	Online	START website	-		-	-	Technical pres		Many		
START Industrial Workshop	1	26/09/2024	26/09/2024	Physical	START website	Kastrup (Denmark)		-	-	Many	26-Sep	Yin, den Heijer, Neve	TEGnology	70+
EuroPM24	1	29/09/2024	02/10/2024	Physical	Europm2024.com	Malmö (Sweden)	PM community	Yes	-	Technical pres		Many	EPMA	
MMH (Mining and Minerals Hall)	n.d.	2024, Oct?			https://mmhseville.com/?lang=en	Sevilla	Mining							
CONAMA (biannual congress)	n.d.	2024, Oct?			http://www.fundacionconama.org/	Madrid	Sustainability					Ester Boixereu	IGME	
Raw Materials Week 2024 (every year)	1	09/12/2024	13/12/2024	Physical	https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/raw-materials	Brussels	Raw Materials	-	-				EPMA/LPRC/LNEG/ASGMI	
START Clustering Side Event	1	10/12/2024	10/12/2024	Physical	https://www.start-heproject.com/clustering-rm-worksh	Brussels	Raw Materials	-	-	Yes	10-Dec	Filipe Neves	EPMA	
Giornate sulla Termoelettricità 2025 (congress of the Italian Associazione Italiana di Termoelettricità)	n.d.	11/02/2025	12/02/2025	Physical	https://ait.icmate.cnr.it/	Rome (Italy)	Thermoelectric Academic							
6th START Webinar (LNEG)	n.d.	2025, Feb?		Online									LNEG	
EPMA FM or HIP seminar 2025	n.d.	2025, TBD		Hybrid	seminars.epma.com	TBD	PM community	-	-	Technical pres		?	EPMA	
PDAC 2025: The World's Premier Mineral Exploration & Mining Convention	1.00	02/03/2025	05/03/2025	Physical	https://www.pdac.ca/convention	Toronto (Canada)	Raw materials/mining			Project update		Filipe Neves	LNEG	
TMS 2025 Annual Meeting & Exhibition	1.00	23/03/2024	27/03/2024	Physical	https://www.tms.org/AnnualMeeting/TMS2025	Las Vegas (USA)	Materials	?						
7th START Webinar (LNEG)	n.d.	2025, May/June?		Hybrid									LNEG	
International Conference on Thermoelectrics (ICT) 2025	n.d.	2025, Jun/Jul		Physical		Sendai (Japan)	Thermoelectric Academic			to be considered for the following years		?		

Figure 28: Status of the START Events List Excel file (updated 14/11/2024), section concerning the period between April 2024 and June 2025. In light green the events already covered, in bold the events where START is the organiser.

The tool is updated about upcoming events, reassessing the priorities continuously. In general, some high priority recurring events are these:

- European Conference on Thermoelectrics (ECT) and International Conference on Thermoelectrics (ICT) conference series
- GENERA (International Energy and Environment Fair)
- Raw Materials Week
- EIT Raw Materials summit
- EU Sustainable Energy Week
- EU Green week
- EPMA's EuroPM Powder Metallurgy yearly Congress & Exhibition (was World PM in 2022)
- EPMA's seminars (HIP, Functional Materials)
- Sustainable Minerals
- In general, when partners have large internal events, these will be covered.

6.2 EVENTS COVERED IN M25-M30

The consortium continued to take part in events organised by third parties, and organised some large event as well, so the effort was particularly strong in this period, as it will probably be the case until the end of the project due the increasing amount of information and topics being covered.

The partners most involved in the industrial side (and the consortium agreed) preferred to postpone participation in industrial events like trade fairs, more related to the application, to later years in the project, when more practical achievements could be shown to attract interest.

The consortium also organised a free webinar with good attendance.

Most of these activities can still be considered a mix of communication and dissemination.

6.2.1 5th START free webinar, 7 June 2024

A START free Webinar #05 was organised on Friday 7th June 11:00-12:45 as a hybrid event during our Annual Meeting at SINTEF, in Oslo (Norway). This format allowed the consortium to take part in person, and other participants, including consortium members that could not be in Oslo, to take part remotely. One speaker, H. Yin, was connected online.

The webinar, titled "Thermoelectric devices and applications" followed this programme:

- 11:00 Welcome and introduction Bruno Vicenzi (EPMA)/Filipe Neves (LNEG)
- 11:00 Maarten den Heijer (RGS Developments) – "Thermoelectric Power Generation applications for Heavy industries and Combined Heat and Power"
- 11:30 Hao Yin (TEGnology) – "100% Green Power for IoT sensors and industrial applications from low-grade excessive heat"
- 12:00 Jean-Yves Escabasse (START's Scientific Advisory Board member) – "Adding value to TEG design by Additive Manufacturing: illustration in STARTREC, a new HORIZON project".

12:30 Q&A with all speakers

12:45 End of webinar

As always, the webinar was totally free, but registration was strictly required (Figure 29). Registrations were 60, although only 25 actually connected. This is a typical turnout for a free webinar. To this number, the consortium members present in Oslo must be added, 35, for a total of 60.

Figure 29: Image used on the project website and the social media to advertise the 5th free webinar.

The footage was recorded, but due to an IT issue it resulted incomplete. The partially recovered video has later been made available on START's YouTube channel¹⁶ and on the website's Multimedia page. The presentation by M. den Heijer could not be saved and has been made available in the video only as slides.

The webinar was also used to advertise for the Industrial Workshop that was organised for the next September in Copenhagen (see below). Its scope was in fact very linked to the theme of the webinar itself.

6.2.2 40th International and 20th European Thermoelectric Conference (ICT/ECT 2024) in Krakow, Poland (30th June - 4th July)

The START project took active part at the 40th International and 20th European Thermoelectric Conference (ICT/ECT 2024) in Krakow, Poland (30th June - 4th July). The ECT and ICT are regular events that were already highlighted in the Events List, and the occasion of having them coinciding in Europe could not be missed.

¹⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xyyf9siMpZI>

Figure 30: Logo of the 40th International and 20th European Thermoelectric Conference (ICT/ECT 2024) in Krakow, Poland (30th June - 4th July).

Presentations were delivered in two sessions. In particular F. Neves (LNEG), our Coordinator, has been invited to speak in the session “Cu-based chalcogenides II”, planned for Thursday 4th July 11:30-13:00, with the presentation “Tetrahedrite-based thermoelectrics: the START project's approach”. Furthermore, RGS has pushed for the establishment of an industrial session for thermoelectric application (“TE Industry”, planned as well on Thursday 4th July 09:00-11:00) where A. Ray presented a talk on “Thermoelectric Modules and Applications: An Industrial Perspective”. The programme¹⁷ of the mentioned sessions is visible in Figure 31.

¹⁷ <https://ict2024.agh.edu.pl/en/conference/final-program>

40th INTERNATIONAL & 20th EUROPEAN CONFERENCE on THERMOELECTRICS
June 30–July 4, 2024, Krakow, POLAND

Welcome **Conference** Traveling Registration Thermoelectric School Login LOT Polish Airlines - Official Carr

THURSDAY, JULY 4, 2024			
	Large Hall A Session: TE Industry Chairman: Jean-Pierre FLEURIAL	Large Hall B Session: Zintl phases II Chairman: Franck GASCOIN	Medium Hall Session: Organic materials Chairman: Przemyslaw DATA
9:00-9:15	Vincent LINSEIS <i>Thermoelectric Metrology: A Comprehensive Review from a Manufacturer's Perspective</i> (Linseis Messgeräte GmbH, Germany)	Alexandra ZEVALKINK <i>Thermoelectric properties of layered AlMX compounds with tunable vacancy concentrations and interlayer bonding</i>	S. Muhammad, D. Motta, M. Bonomo, E. Marchini, S. Carli, S. Caramori, C. Barolo, Andrea REALE <i>Deep eutectic solvents for thermoelectrochemical redox systems for waste-heat recovery applications</i>
9:15-9:30	R. Mohanraman, R. Lydiard, Richard S. TULEY <i>Device substrates: high performance with low thermal conductivity</i> (European Thermodynamics Ltd, UK)		Konosuke OCHI, Ryota MIYAKE, Yuki HANAMURA, Hirokazu TADA <i>Thermoelectric Properties of Ionic Liquids</i>
9:30-9:45	Alex GUREVICH, I. Steiner, Z. Dashevsky, S. Vitriuk <i>A High Performance Thermoelectric Modules with Substrates Made by Vapor Chamber Technology</i> (Double Check Ltd, Israel)	S. Baranets, A. Ovchinnikov, Svilen BOBEV <i>Structural disorder in Zintl phases: The case of Yb₂Mn₂Sb₄ and Yb₂MnSb₃</i>	G. Calabrese, R. Cecchini, M. Ferri, F. Mancarella, D. Gentili, M. Cavallini, V. Morandi, Fabiola LISICIO <i>Enhancing Organic Thermoelectric Materials Through Local Control Wetting</i>
9:45-10:00	Aniruddha RAY, M. D. Hejzer <i>Thermoelectric Modules and Applications: An Industrial Perspective</i> (RGS Development, Netherlands)	Amandine DUPARCHY, F. Kreps, E. Müller, J. de Boor <i>Unlocking the full potential of MgAgSb by unravelling the interrelation of phase constitution and thermoelectric properties</i>	Szymon GOGOC, P. Data, K. Wojciechowski <i>Influence of acidic p-type dopant on thermoelectric properties of conducting polymers</i>
10:00-10:15	Damian KARPOWICZ <i>Enhancing Thermoelectric Efficiency: The U-FAST Glovebox Solution</i> (Genicore, Poland)	Longquan WANG, W. Zhang, S. Back, N. Kawamoto, D. H. Nguyen, T. Mori <i>High-performance Mg₂Sb₂-based thermoelectrics with increased structural ordering and microstructure evolution</i>	M. Betty LINCOLN, R. A. Sujatha, P. Veluswamy, H. Ikeda <i>Flexible polymer based textile thermoelectric generator for wearable human body energy harvesting</i>
10:15-10:30	Uttam GHOSHAL, K. Kollé, A. Stautzenberger, M. Koelber, J. Jamison <i>Large-Scale Integrated Microcooler Technology</i> (Sheetak Inc., Austin, USA)	Kejia LIU, C. Chen, H. Li, Y. Chen <i>Advancing thermoelectric performance in NaCdSb-based Zintl phase via the synergistic effect of Na deficiency and dynamic doping</i>	Sanyin QU, Q. Xu, C. Ming, P. Qiu, X. Shi, L. Chen <i>High-performance n-type Te_{0.8}Se_{0.2}PVDF/graphdiyne organic-inorganic flexible thermoelectric composites</i>
10:30-10:45	Marcin BORCUCH, Michal MUSIAL <i>The performance study of the gas-liquid thermoelectric generator for waste heat harvesting</i> (TEGEOS, Poland)	Shunya SAKANE, A. Ayukawa, N. Kiridoshi, Y. Yamashita, H. Udono <i>Thermoelectric performance of epitaxially grown Mg₂Sb₂ thin films on sapphire substrates</i>	Sajid MUHAMMAD, M. Franzini, S. Galliano, C. Barolo, A. Reale <i>Printable thermoelectric devices based on organic semiconductor composites for low-temperature grade energy harvesting</i>
10:45-11:00		Hong-Jing SHANG, H.-W. Gu, F.-Z. Ding <i>Realizing ultrahigh zT values in Mg₂(Sb,Bi)₂ for superior thermoelectric power-generation</i>	Shun-ichiro ITO, K. Kanahashi, H. Tanaka, B. Chen, H. Ohta, T. Takenobu, <i>Temperature Dependence of Thermoelectric Properties in Electrochemically-Doped Conducting Polymer PBTTT</i>

40th INTERNATIONAL & 20th EUROPEAN CONFERENCE on THERMOELECTRICS
June 30–July 4, 2024, Krakow, POLAND

Welcome **Conference** Traveling Registration Thermoelectric School Login LOT Polish Airlines - Official Carrie

THURSDAY, JULY 4, 2024			
	Large Hall A Session: TE systems Chairman: Jan KOENIG	Large Hall B Session: Cu-based chalcogenides II Chairman: Paz VAQUEIRO	Medium Hall Session: Composites Chairman: Xanthippi ZIANNI
11:00-11:30	Coffee break		
11:30-11:45	M. M. Maia, A. L. Pires, Andre M. PEREIRA <i>Wireless Energy Transfer using Photothermoelectric Devices</i>	Filipe NEVES <i>Tetrahedrite-based thermoelectrics: the START project's approach</i>	Vijay VAIYAPURI, A. Jayaram, N. Mani <i>Boosting the thermoelectric performance of HMS/CNF composites via thermally activated conduction and microstructure engineering</i>
11:45-12:00	Álvaro CASI, A. Patricia, C. David, A. Iñaki, R. Antonio <i>Thermoelectric Subcooling Optimization for Enhancing Vapour Compression Refrigeration Systems</i>		Van Quang Nguyen, Thi Huong Nguyen, Cheng Chang, Li-dong Zhao, JongHo Park, Jae Ki Lee, Su-dong Park, Sunglae CHO <i>SrSe-SnSe₂ & Bi₂Se₃-Sb₂Se₃ Misfit Layered Composite Crystal: Growth and Thermoelectric Properties</i>
12:00-12:15	David ASTRAIN, M. Aralız, L. Catalan, N. Pascual, P. Alegria <i>Electric production from fumaroles of volcanic origin in Antarctica by passive thermoelectric generators</i>	Juliusz LESZCZYŃSKI, P. Laskosz, C. Candolfi, B. Lenoir, P. Nieroda, A. Koleczynski <i>Thermoelectric properties of Cu_{1-x}Fe_xMn₂Sb_{4-y}Te_{3-y} tetrahedrites</i>	Andrii BOICHUK, T. Boichuk, M. E. Changarath, M. Krečmarová, J. P. Martínez-Pastor, J. F. Sánchez-Royo <i>Novel 2D materials with tunable properties for thermoelectric application</i>
12:15-12:30		Cancelled	Peter BALÁŽ, M. Rajhák, M.B.Hudáková, L. Kubičková, N. Daneu, P.Levinský, K.Knížek, J. Hejtmánek, R. Džunda, M. Achimovičová, M. Baláž <i>Mechanochemistry in Preparation of Chalkalite/Stannite Nanocomposite: Kinetics of Synthesis and Thermoelectricity</i>
12:30-12:45	Mykola MAKSYMUK, T. Parashchuk, A. Burelko, K. T. Wojciechowski <i>High energy conversion efficiency realized by the thermoelectric converter with stepwise legs</i>	Frantisek MIHOK, K. Saksli, M. Kruszewski, S. Michalk <i>Polarity switch and thermoelectric properties of polycrystalline SnSe doped with Bi</i>	Abinaya RENGARAJAN, M. Navaneethan, J. Archana <i>Enhanced charge transfer at zero-barrier injection of MoS₂/MoO₃ nanocomposites for thermoelectric applications</i>
12:45-13:00	Alaa ATTAR, A. Alharbi <i>A New Design of a Geothermal Thermoelectric Generator System (GTEG) for Geothermal Heat Recovery</i>	Sana SALAMI, S. Pailhès, C. Adessi, V. Giordano, N. Mahonisi, Z. Mthwesi, S. Vignoli, R. Debord, R. Fulcrand, N. Blanchard, A. Every, S.R. Naidoo <i>Phonon-drag in a graphite channel buried in diamond</i>	Nouredine OUELDNA, A. Portavoce, K. Hoummada <i>Crystalline Mg-Ag-Sb thermoelectric thin films for energy harvesting applications</i>

Figure 31: Programme of the ICT/ECT 2024 for Thursday 4th July 2024, with the presentations related to the START project (highlighted in red).

The project also had a booth where all convened partners could explain the project to the interested participants and actively network with the (mainly academic) global thermoelectric community.

Figure 32: START booth at the ICT/ECT in Krakow with the START consortium members present in the conference.

6.2.3 Congreso Geológico de España 2024 in Avila, Spain (2nd – 6th July)

The IGME team (Figure 34) presented a communication titled "Transforming mining liabilities into energy assets. The case of the START project" (Figure 35) at the "Congreso Geológico de España 2024" in Avila, Spain (2nd – 6th July). This presentation introduced the project and focused on activities carried out in Spain. The proceedings of the congress are published on Geo-Temas, and a related publication appeared there (see chapter 6.4.3).

Figure 33: Logo of the Congreso Geológico de España 2024 in Avila, Spain (2nd – 6th July).

Figure 34: IGME-CSIC team (Concepción Fernández-Leyva, Paula Adánez, Ester Boixereu and Ramón Jimenez) at the Congreso Geológico de España.

Figure 35: Presentation at the Congreso Geológico de España 2024.

6.2.4 XX Congreso Internacional sobre Patrimonio Geológico y Minero, Madrid 15 - 18 September 2024

The IGME team presented a communication titled “Tetrahedrite, movable geological heritage or cutting-edge mining resource?” at the “XX Congreso sobre Patrimonio Geológico y Minero” in Madrid Spain (15th – 18th September). This presentation dealt with how movable geological heritage can help the development of a scientific project: the case of the START project and the collections of the IGME Museo Geominero.

Figure 36: Ester Boixereu (IGME-CSIC) in her speech in the International Congress on Geological and Mining Heritage.

6.2.5 *START Industrial Workshop “Re-structuring of EU value chain on thermoelectrics - From supply chain to end user”, Kastrup (Denmark), 26th September 2024*

Following internal discussions on accelerating the adoption of thermoelectrics, particularly in Europe, we organized an Industrial Workshop with the aim of restructuring a robust European value chain for this technology. This initiative also sought to elevate thermoelectrics as a key driver of sustainable energy efficiency in Europe. In collaboration with the M-era.Net project THERMOS and the Eurostars project FLEX-TEG, we leveraged the expertise of our partner TEGnology to convene all relevant stakeholders. This included established companies utilizing thermoelectric devices, potential adopters, industrial players, startups, and research institutions operating in this domain. We reached out to participants through direct contact and online promotion.

The workshop, which was entirely free of charge for participants, was held at the conveniently located Clarion Hotel at Copenhagen Airport. This venue's direct connection to the airport arrival hall ensured easy access for international participants, attracting attendees and speakers even from South Korea.

The program comprised two key parts. The morning featured a plenary session with invited speakers, while the afternoon offered three breakout sessions addressing specific aspects of thermoelectrics. Additionally, a dedicated networking and matchmaking session facilitated connections during a concluding break. Closing remarks were delivered by H. Yin. Comprehensive details, including the final program with speaker information, are available on the dedicated webpage used for workshop promotion and registration.

The workshop witnessed a remarkable turnout of 70 participants, a significant achievement within the relatively small thermoelectrics community. Among the esteemed speakers were representatives from leading organizations like the European Energy Research Agency, the Japanese National Institute for Materials Science, the Korea Advanced Institute of Science & Technology, Hanyang University in South Korea, the German Space Center, TU Vienna, RGS Development, Quick Ohm, DTP Thermoelectrics, Wideco, and Fraunhofer IFAM. All three projects (START, THERMOS, and FLEX-TEG) were presented during the workshop. Most of the participants agreed to be included in the START mailing list.

The afternoon breakout sessions, with an additional four speakers and dedicated discussions in each room, provided attendees with the opportunity to delve deeper into specific areas of expertise. Networking opportunities were fostered throughout the event, including during lunch and breaks, allowing participants to establish connections and potentially collaborate on future endeavors. This proved particularly valuable for consortium members working towards the successful exploitation of START's research outcomes.

The workshop was a resounding success, and the possibility of a future edition is being explored. START remains committed to driving improvements within the thermoelectric supply chain, not just for their tetrahedrite solution but for the entire industry.

Figure 37: The full room in Industrial Workshop the plenary session.

Figure 38: Group photo of the participants at the START Industrial Workshop in Copenhagen.

Figure 39: START's four speakers in the event. Clockwise and in order of appearance in the workshop, starting from top left: Hao Yin (TEGnology), also local organiser and moderator of the plenary; Maarten den Heijer (RGS Developments); Filipe Neves (LNEG), START's coordinator; Alvis Bianchin (MBN Nanomaterialia).

6.2.6 START online training course, 25th September-3rd October 2024

This is mainly a training activity, so we will report fully on this in the next training deliverable due in May 2025 (D6.11).

The "Virtual Course: Mining Environmental Liabilities and Secondary Raw Materials" took place between 25th September and 3rd October 2024, organized by ASGMI¹⁸ on behalf of the START project. Its objective was to equip participants with a comprehensive understanding of mining processes, their environmental and social impacts, and the tools necessary for identifying, assessing, and remediating environmental liabilities.

Primarily targeting postgraduate students, the course featured presentations from seven experts across diverse fields. These presentations, delivered over six sessions, covered a range of crucial topics:

- Fundamentals of Mining Environmental Liabilities
- Environmental and health risks related to Mining Environmental Liabilities (MELs), encompassing risk assessment and rehabilitation strategies
- Remediation of Environmental Liabilities
- Reuse of Secondary Raw Materials
- Environmental Management and Corporate Social Responsibility

¹⁸ <https://asgmi.org/en/curso-virtual-pasivos-ambientales-mineros-y-materias-primas-secundarias/>

Colleagues from IGME (Concepción Fernández-Leyva and Paula Adánez), involved in the START project, presented on the project itself, offering participants valuable insights.

The workshop garnered significant interest, with 419 registered participants. This included 112 students from various European and non-European countries. Daily attendance fluctuated between 30% and 40% of registered participants, demonstrating a consistent level of engagement.

Recordings of all sessions and presentations used in the workshop are now available for access on the ASGMI website. Students seeking a certificate of completion were required to pass an evaluation test following the course.

<https://asgmi.org/en/curso-virtual-pasivos-ambientales-mineros-y-materias-primas-secundarias/>

ASGMI | START PROJECT VIRTUAL TRAINING

25th Sept - 3rd Oct 2024 (10 hours)

“Mining environmental liabilities and secondary raw materials”

REGISTER NOW

Figure 40: The advertisement used to collect registrations, on websites and on social media.

Project: 101058632
HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01

TETRAHEDRITE

Tetrahedrite ($\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$) is a copper antimony sulphosalt that forms a complete solid solution with Tennantite in which antimony (Sb) is replaced by arsenic ($\text{Cu}_{12}(\text{Sb,As})_4\text{S}_{13}$)

Argentotennantite	$\text{Ag}_6[\text{Cu}_4(\text{Fe,Zn})_2]\text{As}_2\text{S}_{13}$
Argentotetrahedrite	$\text{Ag}_{10}(\text{Fe,Zn})_2\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$
Freibergite	$\text{Ag}_6[\text{Cu}_4\text{Fe}_2]\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13,x}$
Giraudite	$\text{Cu}_6[\text{Cu}_4(\text{Fe,Zn})_2]\text{As}_2\text{Se}_{13}$
Goldfieldite	$\text{Cu}_{10}\text{Te}_2\text{S}_{13}$
Hakite	$\text{Cu}_6[\text{Cu}_4\text{Hg}_2]\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_{13}$
Tennantite	$\text{Cu}_6[\text{Cu}_4(\text{Fe,Zn})_2]\text{As}_2\text{S}_{13}$

Legend: Cu (blue), Sb (red), S (yellow)

Figure 41: A moment of the course, where tetrahedrite, START’s material of election, was introduced.

6.2.7 START at the MacaroNight on 27th September 2024

START was again present at the MacaroNight event that LPRC organised in the Canary Islands as part of the European Researchers' Night. At the event, the visitors of the EU Corner could find 100 copies of the START comic that LPRC printed. In total, there were 762 students and 171 general public attending the event.

Figure 42: START leaflets available at the 2024 Macaronight.

6.2.8 Euro PM2024 Congress & Exhibition, Malmö (Sweden), 29th September - 2nd October 2024

START took part with its own booth in the Euro PM2024 European Powder Metallurgy Congress & Exhibition, organised as usual by EPMA

**EURO
PM2024**
CONGRESS & EXHIBITION

EPMA
european powder metallurgy association
29 Sep - 2 Oct 2024
MALMÖ

and taking place this year in Malmö (Sweden) from 29th September to 2nd October. The booth (Figure 43) featured all materials about the project, posters (some also outside of the START booth), roller banner, leaflets, looping video with the Starty stories published to date, samples in the showcase, all available for the visitors of the large PM community. The running thermoelectric device demo from TEGnology already taken to the EPMA Summer School was shown at the booth as well (Figure 44).

This year there was no presentation of START in the technical sessions, but there was again a visit of the so-called Young Engineers, a group of students that have a special care during the congress, and in particular visit the exhibition booths; D. Karpowicz (GeniCore), A. Colella and E. Forlin (MBN) addressed them with 10' presentations and answering to questions on the afternoon of Tuesday 1st October.

Figure 43: The START booth at the Euro PM2024 Congress&Exhibition in Sweden.

Figure 44: Detail of the START booth's showcase at the Euro PM2024 Congress&Exhibition in Sweden, with various materials, including the TE demo (visible on the wooden tabletop).

6.2.9 Conference at the "Comú de Particulars" Cultural Center in La Pobla de Segur (Catalonia, Spain), 2nd November 2024

On 2nd November, Ester Boixereu of OGME-CSIC gave a presentation at the "Comú de Particulars" Cultural Center in La Pobla de Segur (Catalonia, Spain) titled "Recursos minerales per a la transició energètica. El projecte START" ("Mineral resources for the energy transition. The START project"). The presentation was recorded and is available on YouTube¹⁹.

¹⁹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AVcenCMK_C0

Figure 45: Promotional poster of the event at La Pobla de Segur (in Catalan).

Figure 46: Ester Boixereu presenting at La Pobla de Segur.

6.3 EVENTS IN PREPARATION

The START project is preparing the participation in several events throughout the coming months and is also organising a clustering event in Brussels.

6.3.1 Conferences, Exhibitions, Workshops, Webinars

6.3.1.1 Clustering Workshop “Supporting the Critical Raw Materials Act: Research Projects in the European Union”, Brussels (Belgium), 10th December 2024

In previous years, START took part in the Raw Materials Weeks (RMWs) organised in Brussels with a lower profile; some partners were there, and some videos prepared specifically have been shown in the screens during breaks.

This year, and originating from the clustering activities, we decided to prepare a Side Event for the RMW, thus taking a more active role in the RMW, as was anticipated in the previous deliverable.

A specific page on the START website was created to give details on the event and lead people to the registration form (see chapter 5.1).

The agenda will commence with an introductory speech from a representative of the EU funding agency (to be announced). This will be followed by 15-minute presentations from eight EU projects focused on the efficient use of Raw Materials. Each project will elaborate on its contribution to addressing the challenges outlined in the Critical Raw Materials Act.

A panel discussion moderated by Thomas Unterweissacher of GEO Unterweissacher GmbH, a START partner, will follow the presentations. This session will involve the presenters and will be open to audience participation.

The event will conclude with a networking session, allowing participants to further engage with each other. In fact, the event aims to facilitate knowledge exchange, identify shared challenges, and promote collaboration and the formation of new partnerships. The Raw Materials Week, which convenes all relevant stakeholders, provides an ideal opportunity to host a productive event, and indeed, our workshop is officially recognized as a Side Event. For START, putting together many interested projects and listeners is also a way to enlarge the mailing list (participants filling the registration form are giving their specific consent to that, according to GDPR requirements), thus improving the diffusion of all our materials, and finally our impact.

This is a summary agenda:

14:00 – 15:15	First block: Opening presentation (HaDEA – TBA), START, GSEU, FutuRAM, CRM Geothermal
15:15 – 15:30	Coffee Break
15:30 – 16:30	Second block: CIRAN, SUPREEMO, REESOURCE, REPTiS
16:30 – 17:10	Roundtable and conclusions – moderated by T. Unterweissacher
17:10 – 17:30	Final networking session

At the moment of writing this deliverable, some information on speakers is still missing. On the website, a detailed sheet with the programme is available for download, and this file will be updated

until the programme will be finalised. The presentation for START will be given by the coordinator F. Neves, who will also take part, together with T. Unterweissacher, in the panel discussion.

The event is free of charge, but we require a previous registration. Advertisement has been made via a mass mail to the START mailing list, and on LinkedIn and X, and will continue until the registration deadline and even after. Registrants at the date of 26 November are 49.

The graphic features a red triangle on the left side. To its right is the START logo, which consists of a green and red geometric icon followed by the word 'START' in a bold, grey, sans-serif font. Below the logo, the text 'START free workshop (Side Event of the Raw Materials Week 2024)' is written in red. Underneath that, the date and time '10th December 2024, 14:00-17:30 CET' are listed in blue, followed by the location 'Hotel Marivaux, Auditorium Alfred Hitchcock, Boulevard Adolphe Maxlaan 98, B-1000 Brussels' in a smaller blue font. A central banner with a blue background and white text reads 'SUPPORTING THE CRITICAL RAW MATERIALS ACT: RESEARCH PROJECTS IN THE EUROPEAN UNION'. Below this banner is a green bar with white text that says 'REGISTRATION IS REQUIRED!'. On the right side of the graphic is a small image of an orange excavator bucket dumping grey rocks. The bottom of the graphic is decorated with horizontal lines in grey, green, and red.

Figure 47: Image used for the initial advertisement on social media.

A screenshot of the Side Events page on the RMW website is visible in Figure 48.

Figure 48: Screenshot of the RMW website page concerning the side events, where the START Clustering Workshop is reported with the link for registration (downloaded on 14th November 2024).

6.3.1.2 *PDAC, 2-5 March 2025, Toronto (Canada)*

START has been again invited by the EU to express the interest in joining the EU booth in the Prospectors and Developers Association of Canada's world-renowned event PDAC, one of the most important mining events globally, that will take place at the beginning of March 2025.

START is willing to take part and also offered for a presentation in the event, and we are awaiting confirmation and details from the EU.

Other smaller events where project partners will bring information and short presentations about the project will surely be attended. Participation in fairs and exhibitions next year will be discussed.

6.3.2 *Training Activities:*

These will be better explained in D6.11, that will be prepared in May 2025, but we report them here as well.

- During the EPMA Powder Metallurgy Summer School in Alessandria, Italy (15th - 19th July), H. Yin (TEGnology) demonstrated thermoelectric devices for waste heat harvesting and other applications. Additionally, B. Vicenzi of EPMA provided a project overview in the opening speech.
- A training course for Master students interested in the project, organised by ASGMI, was run in English from 25th Sept to 3rd Oct 2024 for a total of about 8 hours. This course aimed to raise awareness of the START project among students. Experts from geological surveys and universities participated as lecturers. More details are available in chapter 6.2.6.

6.4 PUBLICATIONS

In the first part of the project, as documented in Deliverables D6.3, D6.4, D6.6 and D6.7, a few documents had already been produced for publication.

Publications that have been uploaded on the website and on the Zenodo open access repository, where a “community” named “Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling” was created, obtained a specific DOI, and they have automatically been added in the Continuous Reporting Publications page in the Funding & Tender portal for the project (see chapter 5.8.3).

In addition to this, a publication on a magazine, as reported in the following chapters, has not been uploaded to Zenodo, yet it is fully readable online, with open access, in the magazine's website.

6.4.1 *EPMA newsletters*

As already detailed in chapter 5.2, EPMA published many internal newsletters with details on START.

6.4.2 START on the Innovation News Network

The article written by the consortium, with contributions from F. Neves (LNEG) and B. Vicenzi (EPMA), that was published on the website Innovations News Network²⁰ (see Annex II for the full article) on 12th March 2024²¹, was also published in Issue 18 of their periodical magazine “The Innovation Platform”, which is Open Access and that was issued on 3rd June 2024. Another article is foreseen to be published on the INN website in 2025, and in Issue 24 of “The Innovation Platform” that should be available in December 2025. In addition to this, a START banner, linking to the START website, was hosted on the INN website.

On 5th August 2024 specific feedback on the page views and distribution of the magazine was delivered by the publisher. They reported interesting figures, that testify a good audience for our article:

- Total reach (considering all products where START materials appeared): 204'563
- Total engagement: 141'156
- Total reach for The Innovation Platform edition: 152'822
- Total Edition Engagement: 140'727
- Client engagement (START article specifically): 3'112 views

Figure 49: The cover of the web magazine “The Innovation Platform”, Issue 18, published in June 2024 and containing the START article (pages 36 to 38).

²⁰ <https://www.innovationnewsnetwork.com/>

²¹ <https://www.innovationnewsnetwork.com/the-start-project-transforming-mining-waste-into-waste-heat-recovery-materials/45204/>

6.4.3 Publication on “Geo-Temas”

Our partner IGME-CSIC also published on the issue 20 of the magazine Geo-Temas²², a publication of the Sociedad Geológica de España (Spanish Geological Society), that is distributed to the members of the society (about 1000) but is also available online. The title of the paper²³ was “Transformación de pasivos mineros en activos energéticos. El caso del Proyecto START” (“Transforming mining wastes into energy assets. The case of the START project.”).

Geo-Temas 20, ISSN: 1576-5173 (versión impresa) 2792-2308 (versión digital)

Transformación de pasivos mineros en activos energéticos. El caso del proyecto START.

Transforming mining wastes into energy assets. The case of the START project.

E. Boixereu¹, C. Fernández-Leyva², R. Jiménez-Martínez¹, P. Adáñez¹ y D. Gómez-Limón³

- 1 CN-Instituto Geológico y Minero de España. c/Ríos Rosas, 23, Madrid e.boixereu@igme.es, r.jimenez@igme.es, p.adanez@igme.es
- 2 CN-Instituto Geológico y Minero de España. Urb. Alcázar del Genil, edificio. Zukema bajo. Granada c.fernandez@igme.es
- 3 ETSI Minas y Energía. Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. c/Ríos Rosas, 21, Madrid

Resumen: El objetivo general del proyecto es transformar un material desechado en las escombreras mineras, en concreto, minerales del Grupo de la tetraedrita, en recuperadores de calor residual. De esta forma se lograría sustituir a los actuales termoelementos tipo P comerciales, basados en telurio, que resultan caros y raros desde el punto de vista de su accesibilidad. Las tetraedritas son sulfosales de cobre y arsénico o antimonio, con otros metales (Ag, Zn, Fe, Cd, Hg, Se, Te, Mn, Ni, In). Por sus características físicas y su estructura de celda, tienen excelentes propiedades para aplicaciones termoelectricas. Por otro lado, son relativamente abundantes en algunos residuos mineros de cobre. Se ha llevado a cabo una selección de yacimientos de toda España en cuyas escombreras hay una mayor potencialidad para encontrar tetraedritas. Se han muestreado un total de 4 yacimientos, en los que se han realizado ensayos de separación y concentración del mineral.

Palabras clave: Tetraedrita, semiconductor, residuos mineros, economía circular, yacimientos españoles.

Abstract: The overall objective of the project is to transform mining waste materials, namely those belonging to the tetrahedrite group, into waste heat recovery materials. This would replace current commercial p-type thermoelements, which are based on tellurium, and expensive and rare in terms of accessibility. Tetrahedrites are sulphosalts of copper and arsenic or antimony, with other metals (Ag, Zn, Fe, Cd, Hg, Se, Te, Mn, Ni, In). Due to their physical characteristics and cell structure, they have excellent properties for thermoelectric applications. Besides, they are relatively abundant in some copper mining waste. Ore deposits throughout Spain have been selected regarding in whose mining wastes there is a greater potential to find tetrahedrites. A total of 4 deposits have been sampled, in which mineral separation and concentration tests have been carried out.

Key words: Tetrahedrite, semiconductor, mining waste, circular economy, Spanish mineral deposits

ANTECEDENTES

El proyecto START es un proyecto europeo perteneciente al Pilar II (Desafíos mundiales y competitividad industrial europea), Cluster 4 (Mundo digital, industria y espacio). El concepto fundamental es la transformación de materiales existentes en residuos mineros en recuperadores del calor residual.

El calor residual es aquel generado como subproducto en el sector industrial o terciario, que se disipa en el aire o el agua. Casi todos los procesos y maquinarias de fabricación generan calor y se calcula que dos tercios de la energía primaria producida en todo el mundo se pierde como calor residual. En resumen, es un calor generado por los humanos y las actividades que desarrollan. El potencial de recuperación de calor residual estimado en la UE podría evitar decenas de millones de toneladas de emisiones de CO₂.

La posibilidad de utilizar materiales termoelectricos para capturar y convertir directamente el calor residual en energía eléctrica es un enfoque muy atractivo y valioso para mejorar la eficiencia energética global. Permiten transformar el calor residual en una fuente de energía, convirtiendo una diferencia de temperatura en electricidad. Un material termoelectrico eficaz debe ser buen conductor eléctrico y mal conductor térmico. Hay pocos materiales con estas características. Actualmente, los más utilizados son materiales basados en telurio (Bi₂Te₃, PbTe) o silicio (SiGe), que además son caros, raros o tóxicos.

El objetivo general del proyecto es crear un ecosistema de innovación en la UE relacionado con el desarrollo de sistemas termoelectricos de aprovechamiento del calor residual, sostenibles, económicamente viables y libres de telurio.

Figure 50: First page of the publication on Geo-Temas issue 20.

²² <https://sociedadgeologica.org/publicaciones/geotemas/>

²³ Boixereu, E., Fernández-Leyva, C., Jiménez-Martínez R., Adáñez P., D. Gómez-Limón D., García, M. y Reyes, J. 2024. Transformación de pasivos mineros en activos energéticos. El caso del proyecto START. Geotemas, 20: 679-682. Also available online: https://sge.usal.es/archivos/GEO_TEMAS/Geo_temas20.pdf

7 TASK 6.3: TRAINING ACTIVITIES

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M12 to M48

This task's activities started officially in May 2023, but details have been given in D6.5 (May 2023) and D6.8 (May 2024), that are dedicated to the training activities. A full description of the training activities will be given in D6.11 (May 2025). Nevertheless, some activities (EPMA Summer School and the training workshop) have been mentioned elsewhere in this deliverable.

8 TASK 6.4: CLUSTERING

Task leader: ASGMI; Participants: All; M03 to M48

The objective of the clustering activity, that constitutes task T6.4 and began at M03 and will continue for the whole project duration to end at M48, is building a comprehensive cluster for the dissemination of the project. The main idea is to create an effective strategy to identify similar and interesting projects and find synergies to create value, avoid duplications and strengthen and maximize the START project results impact.

Projects that share a common theme or address similar challenges can form a cluster initiative and deliver shared strategic outputs. Thus, START wants to enhance links and synergies with such projects and initiatives. ASGMI with the support of all partners is identifying the project coordinators of the selected projects & initiatives. Mapping the synergies among the different projects will maximize the impact and contribute to have a more efficient and strong European Innovation.

A database was created and has been updated during this period with interesting initiatives and projects and will be kept updated throughout the rest of the project. Some of the resources consulted to feed this database are the following:

- The Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS) for H2020 or Horizon Europe projects
- The EIT (including the KICs on Raw Materials, InnoEnergy & Climate KIC)
- The internal community (partners in the consortium and its members)

The links are being established by a series of online short meetings with the relevant Project Coordinators or key people and the START project coordinator and/or the Communication WP leader.

Key events and meetings are essential to identify and establish good connections: the people from the initiatives in the clustering database, likely belonging to the audience target Groups 2 and 3, but in some cases also from Group 1, will be invited to the relevant events organized by START (seminars, webinars, trainings, final event) ensuring dedicated time for networking and collaboration. Conversely, START consortium members participating to events are supposed to seek connections with all interesting stakeholders.

8.1 CLUSTERING STRATEGY

A clustering strategy has been designed in order to be implemented during the whole project duration. This strategy consists of two work lines: internal and external clustering:

8.1.1 Internal clustering

Consortium members are being contacted to identify projects, or other initiatives in which they are involved and/or are aware of, and check if they have common points and potential to establish synergies.

8.1.2 External clustering

The strategy for external clustering consists in contacting institutions and organizations that are not directly involved in the START project but work in similar or complementary themes.

These can be classified as explained in the next subchapters.

8.1.2.1 Key institutions and actors

Associations and big organizations directly or indirectly related to technical projects or other research initiatives are especially important because networks in which they are involved have a big potential for clustering with START project. They have a “helicopter view” of the activities done by their members and contacting them is a fast and easy way to reach a large number of potential projects.

Key people (outreach people and project leaders) in these organizations have been identified and contacted in order to schedule meetings between projects or Work Package leaders.

Clustering task and communication leaders of the project contacted key individuals at EIT Raw Materials, InnoEnergy KICs, and EuroGeoSurveys during the previous reporting period. Additionally, contact has been established and meetings held with other initiatives and organizations, which are detailed in the following sections.

8.1.2.1.1 ERHASE Cluster

As we already documented in D6.7, START effectively joined the ERHASE Cluster, formed by three European Projects (FAST-SMART, SYMPHONY, InComEss), and is now listed on the web page of the cluster as a partner project (Figure 51).

ERHASE cluster
The ERHASE cluster is formed by 3 projects: the FAST-SMART Project, the SYMPHONY Project and the InComEss Project.

ERHASE stands for **Energy Harvesting for a Sustainable Future** and the aim of the cluster is to address the technical scope areas within the context of energy harvesting and storage technologies. Through the cluster, participating projects must expand their impact beyond the project term, while contributing to the dissemination of state-of-the-art research and developments. Together, the 3 projects will boost awareness regarding the research outcomes and promote energy harvesting with relevant stakeholders, such as academia and industry.

Goals

- Define a knowledge sharing framework around common goals
- Increase the outreach of each project's activities and enhance the visibility of all efforts towards energy harvesting and storage technologies
- Enhance and rationalise dissemination and communication activities
- Strengthen the networking between all member projects

Participants

Symphony
The SYMPHONY project delivers an energy supply platform for the powering of wireless sensor/ sensor nodes for monitoring remote or difficult-to-access locations. The energy supply in this system is completely made of green, recyclable, and non-toxic materials including the biodegradable polymer (COP-102), printable to speed matters, solar polymer batteries and cellulose-based supercapacitors. The SYMPHONY project develops cost-effective and scalable methods to print these materials on flexible films and to combine them with energy-efficient electronics and sensor technologies.
The SYMPHONY solution will significantly reduce CO2 emissions by increasing the lifetime of wind turbines, making room heating/cooling more efficient, through presence and motion tracking smart floors and decreasing the energy consumption in e-bikes, through remote tube pressure control. The printed technology can be integrated cost-effectively in amorphous and flexible devices, representing a huge potential for usage in a wide range of further self-powered applications.

FAST-SMART
FAST-AND-FORGET is the inspirational model that generated FAST-SMART, an International European project funded by EC that gathered together for 48 months top-rated universities, research centres and companies expert in materials, solar panels and transport systems. The objective of the project is to improve the efficiency of how we can collect alternative forms of energies generated by our surroundings (e.g. light, heat, mechanical vibrations) and convert them in energy that we can reuse to feed our devices, such as sensors and solar panels. This process is called **ENERGY HARVESTING**.
Energy harvesting happens using devices called **ENERGY HARVESTERS**. Their science and development is relatively new one, at the moment, it is possible to obtain only small amounts of energy that, by the way, can already allow small devices such as mobile phones handset to have their own power supply without being plugged.
Energy harvesting is beneficial to our environment because reuse natural forms of energies that otherwise would be dissipated or wasted.
At present energy harvesters are produced using toxic materials (such as lead) and other strategic materials classified as Critical Raw Materials (such as Thorium), available in limited quantities in Europe and making our external vulnerable and dependent from external sources.
FAST-SMART project aims to develop energy harvesters based on new materials without elements that can run out or elements no present in Europe mining portfolio, in particular, two categories of energy harvesters will be introduced: **piezoelectric** and **thermoelectric** and tested in three application fields: **sensors for railway track vibration detection, solar panels and hybrid engines**. FAST-SMART project will bring innovation not only in materials but also in the assembly steps, with more efficient low energy consumption synthesis process and faster assembly techniques.

START
Europe's fight for a sustainable green transition:
Climate change looms large, threatening our planet and demanding swift action. The ambitious European Green Deal tackles this head-on, prioritising climate action and a green transition. However, success hinges on access to raw materials within the EU and fostering circularity in strategic industries.
Enter START: A Game-Changing Initiative (launched June 2022, 4-year duration)
The groundbreaking project aligns perfectly with the Green Deal's goals. It proposes a revolutionary approach: recovering waste sulphides belonging to the tetrahedrite series (Cu₄S₁₀TeS₄) from abandoned mine sites and ongoing mining operations across the EU. These recovered materials will be transformed into cutting-edge 3D-printed transistors, powering next-generation thermoelectric generators that harvest waste heat.
START's impact:

- Reduced reliance** on imported critical raw materials, strengthening Europe's economic and environmental resilience.
- Championing circularity:** Minimising waste and maximising resource utilization.
- Developing clean energy solutions** through thermoelectric systems that decrease fossil fuel dependence, boost energy efficiency, and cut greenhouse gas emissions.

A United Effort:
Led by start (Germany), START unites 16 organizations from 16 EU member states and 1 associated country. This diverse team comprises 6 research institutions with expertise in geology, materials science, and renewable energy, 7 SMEs covering the entire supply chain (production, exploitation, and eco-footprint assessment), and 2 non-profit associations with extensive partner networks.
START aims to be a game-changer promoting a greener and more sustainable future for Europe.

InComEss
The InComEss project proposes a new **green and cost-effective strategy for high-efficient energy harvesting** by combining new smart carbonized polymer-based composite materials and structures into an **single/multi-source concept** to harvest electrical energy from mechanical energy and/or waste heat ambient sources, which consists of three novel Energy Harvesting Systems (EHS) configurations: Piezoelectric, Thermoelectric and Hybrid ThermoPiezoelectric EHS. InComEss will implement innovative lead-free Materials, Systems and Structures to develop Energy Harvesting Systems able to power VDS, GPS and MEMS sensors in SIM and vehicle monitoring in automotive, aerospace and building, presenting the highest market potential.
The project seeks at developing **efficient smart materials with energy harvesting and storage capabilities** combining advanced polymer-based-composite materials into a novel **single/multi-source concept to harvest electrical energy from mechanical energy and/or waste heat ambient sources**. The project will demonstrate its applicability in key sectors and applications, SIM and vehicle monitoring in automotive, aerospace and building, presenting the highest market potential.

Figure 51: The page describing the ERHASE cluster and its partners, hosted on the InComEss project website²⁴.

Since the three projects comprising ERHASE were ending in February, March (extended to September), and April 2024, no other joint initiatives were carried out. On the other hand, recent discussions might lead to other projects joining the cluster.

8.1.2.1.2 THERMOS Project

START is also tightly connecting with the project THERMOS²⁵, as explained already in D6.7. This led to a very fruitful collaboration, that originated the Industrial Workshop organised in September 2024 (see chapter 6.2.5).

8.1.2.1.3 XTRACT Project

Active talks are currently happening with the Horizon Europe project XTRACT²⁶. With this project the main point of contact is the recovery of waste piles in mines. The XTRACT objective is introduce a new concept of the Zero Emission Mine of the Future, developing and validating innovative microinvasive technologies for sustainable and decarbonised extraction. After a first meeting, at the moment a clustering proposal is being discussed among the main partners of the two projects. XTRACT was also initially contacted also for the Side Event at the RMW2024, but they had to decline due to other commitments.

8.1.2.1.4 Clustering Workshop at the RMW2024

Another outcome of the search for synergies is clearly the Clustering Workshop organised as a Side Event of the Raw Materials Week 2024 in Brussels, on 10th December 2024 (see chapter 6.3.1.1). Seven other projects are involved, and with all of them common interests are evident. On the occasion of the workshop, there will be more discussions in order to see if more formal relationships can be established.

8.1.2.2 Link with communication and dissemination activities

Project consortium members participation in technical or commercial big events, congress or other initiatives is interesting because this participation brings the opportunity to meet key people and find out new projects or initiatives related directly or indirectly with the project in order to stablish synergies.

To maximize the potential of clustering in these events, the clustering strategy builds a list of the events in which the consortium members are going to attend, identify potential organizations or key participants in the event and suggest to the consortium members to contact them before and during the events to talk about related projects. This list is actually included in the Events List for Dissemination and the most interesting events for clustering are given a higher priority.

8.1.2.3 CORDIS

CORDIS provides information on all EU-supported R&D activities, including programs (Horizon Europe, H2020, FP7 and older), projects, results and publications so is an essential platform for looking for projects under same or similar calls and finding out the coordinator to establish contact.

²⁴ <https://www.incomess-project.com/erhase-cluster>

²⁵ <https://www.m-era.net/materipedia/2021/thermos>

²⁶ <https://xtract-project.eu/>

8.1.2.4 Clustering Database

The clustering database has been created in order to achieve the objectives of the clustering strategy. The database is being updated with new organizations and projects and will remain active throughout the project. It includes data such as the name or organization, contact person, date of meeting and comments related to experiences exchanged in the meeting

At the moment, the database lists 50 projects that may have a connection with START. The key organizations and projects with which initial contact has been made or meetings have been held are included in the following table. As this deliverable is public, but the full list cannot be public for privacy issues, it is not shown here. Only stakeholder entities' names are shown in Table 5.

Table 6: Key institutions and interesting related project identified for Clustering.

Organization	Meeting date	Projects	
EIT Raw Materials	16/11/2022	EuGeLi	https://eitrawmaterials.eu/project/eugeli/
		RIS-CuRE	RIS-CuRE: Zero waste recovery of copper tailings in the ESEE region - EIT RawMaterials
		BioLeach	BioLeach: Innovative Bio-treatment of RM - EIT RawMaterials
		INCO-Piles 2020	INCO-Piles-2020. International consortium to recover CRMs from stockpiles/tailings targeting RIS - EIT RawMaterials
EIT InnoEnergy	To be scheduled		
Fraunhofer Institute for Manufacturing Technology and Advanced Materials IFAM	18/10/2023	THERMOS	https://www.m-era.net/materipedia/2021/thermos
Leibniz institute for Solid State and Materials Research Dresden (IFW)			
H2020 and Horizon Europe Projects			
FutuRaM	To be scheduled	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058522	
FAST-SMART	ERHASE Cluster	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/862289	
InComEss		https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/862597/es	
Symphony		https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/862095	
STARTREC	Contacted		

REESOURCE	To be scheduled	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101138460
XTRACT	Contacted	https://xtract-project.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101138432
GSEU	Contacted	https://www.geologicalservice.eu/
CRM Geothermal	Contacted	https://crm-geothermal.eu/
CIRAN	Contacted	https://ciranproject.eu/
SUPREEMO	Contacted	https://www.supreemo-project.eu/
REPTiS	Contacted	http://www.reptis.eu/

8.1.2.5 *Invite key actors to project meetings*

Project meeting or events (virtual and in person) are good opportunities for inviting key actors (project leaders, researchers or stakeholders) to disseminate the objectives and advances in the project and try to establish synergies and common dissemination actions. Some of these researchers have been invited as speakers in the webinars organized by the project and have contributed to their dissemination and diffusion:

- Webinar #05 (7th July 2024):
 - Jean-Yves Escabasse (CEA, START Scientific Advisory Board)
- Industrial Workshop (September 2024):
 - Co-organisation with THERMOS and FLEX-TEG
 - Other speakers
 - Key industrial contacts
- Clustering Workshop (December 2024):
 - Presentation(s) from 7 other projects
 - Presentation from HaDEA

More experts will be invited to future events, also from the clusters and projects that we have been talking with.

8.2 KEY EVENTS AND MEETINGS

During this period of the START project, the consortium members have participated in different events in which they have disseminated about the project, its main objectives and topics.

In these events, members have had the opportunity to seek connections with interesting stakeholders.

The main events for clustering, that have been described with more details in paragraph 6.2, are listed below:

- 40th International and 20th European Thermoelectric Conference (ICT/ECT 2024) in Krakow, Poland (30th June - 4th July)
- START Industrial Workshop “Re-structuring of EU value chain on thermoelectrics - From supply chain to end user”, Kastrup (Denmark), 26th September 2024

To these, the upcoming Clustering Workshop “Supporting the Critical Raw Materials Act: Research Projects in the European Union” must definitely be added.

Several meetings happened online with other projects (e.g. THERMOS, XTRACT, REESOURCE) among START partners and some partners of the other projects.

9 TASK 6.5: FINAL EVENT

Task leader: ASGMI; Participants: LNEG, All; M42 to M48

A final conference will be organised at the end of the project as a main dissemination event showcasing the successes achieved over the four years of the project.

The conference will likely take place in Brussels.

The details of the event (type of event, audience, keynote speakers...) will be determined during the project (starting around M42).

The final conference will try to be organised back-to-back with another mayor relevant event to ensure as large attendance as possible.

This task is not active yet. Nothing to report.

10 ANNEX I – START NEWSLETTER – ISSUE #5 – NOVEMBER 2024

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14062520

BIANNUAL NEWSLETTER OF THE START PROJECT | ISSUE 5

RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE

for a Sustainable Future

EDITORIAL

don't miss the latest comic strip that cleverly demystifies life cycle assessment in a way only Starty can.

We've also got updates on the progress of our work packages, showcasing the collaborative efforts and milestones achieved thus far. The highlight of our year, the annual project meeting at SINTEF, was a resounding success, fostering synergy and innovation among our team members. Our commitment to spreading the word about START's mission continues with a roundup of our dissemination, communication, and clustering activities. Looking ahead, we're excited to announce the upcoming events that promise to further our reach and impact.

This edition features interesting interviews with two experts: one with Dr. Doris Hiam-Galvez, a senior Advisor at Hatch Consulting, who passionately advocates for sustainable development, and another with Hao Yin from TEGnology, discussing cutting-edge topics in the field of thermoelectric technology. Lastly, join us on a virtual tour to meet our partners GEO and MBN, whose contributions are invaluable to the success of the project.

We hope this issue of the newsletter provides you with valuable insights and keeps you informed about the exciting developments within the START project. Thank you for your continued support and engagement. Stay tuned for more updates and breakthroughs in our journey towards a sustainable future.

(F. Neves)

CONTENT

- Recover-Reform-Reuse	1
- STARTY – 5: Sustainable product design	2
- Interview with João Mascarenhas, author of Starty	6
- START Chronicles: Geology, thermoelectrics and more	8
* News from WorkPackages	8
* START Annual Assembly in Oslo, 6-7 June 2024	11
* START webinar #5	12
* START Industrial Workshop "Re-structuring of EU value chain on thermoelectrics - From supply chain to end user", Kastrup (Denmark), 26th September 2024	13
* START online training course, 25th September-3rd October 2024	14
* START seeks synergies with the XTRACT project	15
* Other START dissemination events	16
- Register for the Clustering Event in Brussels!	19
- Technical pills	20
* Basic LCA Concepts and LCA in the START project	20
- Meet the experts	23
* Interview with Dr. Doris HIAM-GALVEZ	23
* Interview with Hao YIN, published on the bulletin of Associazione Italiana di Termoelettricità (Italian Association for Thermoelectricity, AIT)	25
- Consortium tour	27
* GEO Unterweissacher (GEO)	27
* MBN Nanomaterialia (MBN)	29
- Bibliography	29
- Contacts	29

Project: 101058632 HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-07

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 52: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-001.

STARTY - 5: SUSTAINABLE PRODUCT DESIGN

Figure 53: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-002.

Figure 54: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-003.

Figure 55: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-004.

Figure 56: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-005.

INTERVIEW WITH JOÃO MASCARENHAS, AUTHOR OF STARTY

Figure 1 - João Mascarenhas (LNEG), author of Starty and renowned cartoon author.

In this issue, we will take some space to recognize the huge work done by the author of Starty, João Mascarenhas, of Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia, I.P. (LNEG), the coordinating partner of START. João is at the same time a well-known cartoonist and an experienced researcher at LNEG. In his professional career, he has been working on Powder Metallurgy and Materials Science since 1990, and more recently in Materials for Energy. As a cartoonist, he is an internationally awarded author, and his books published in several countries.

Every time a newsletter is prepared, João embarks in the preparation of some pages with Starty. Together with the text on the subject of each issue, he develops and draws the scenes alone. And each time we prepare a multilingual edition, he has to adapt all the dialogues to each language (we have 15 languages on board now!). A lot of effort, with quite good results, what do you think?

Here he will tell us something about his art, its connection to his engineering and research career, and some more details about the idea of Starty. We hope you will enjoy this interview!

Q: Hello João, thanks for accepting to reveal yourself to the readers of the newsletter! You have been working very hard to produce Starty's cartoons for the project, and we think that the readers might be curious to know who produced them. Can you tell us something about how you developed your passion and skills for drawing characters and stories?

João Mascarenhas: It's a pleasure to share some words with our readers. For as long as I can remember, I have always drawn something. But I only started as a comic professional author after my PhD (in 1997). My stories are based on Humanism, the preservation of Memory and the noble values of the Human being.

Q: People can Google your name and will find all the stories you have published. But let's list some of them here - with some personal words on them.

JM: My best-known books, in national terms, is O Menino Triste (The Sad Boy). This is a character who is my alter ego. It's not about my life, but rather using it as a basis to later build stories, based on my childhood memories, and my experiences as a Human being. I also published a 200-pages book about science fiction, where I speculate about the use of memories that may be retained in our DNA. It's called The Butterfly Chronicles, and was initially published in Portuguese, English and Japanese. My most recent published book deals with a topic that is very much on the agenda, and it has to do with migrations. It is the story of an Arab musician, poet and perfumer who comes to live in Portugal in the 1980s.

Q: What are the tools a cartoonist like you uses nowadays? Supposedly, most of the work is now done digitally; tell us some of your secrets.

JM: I have no secrets. Normally, I draw in a traditional, conventional way, that what is with the old blue colour pencil. Then I ink the drawings with black ink, using brushes or pens. The blue pencil is because when the drawings are scanned, the blue colour does not appear on the digital file, so it is not necessary to erase the pencil traces, as we need to do with the carbon pencil. These digital inked drawings are then coloured in the computer, that is a powerful tool, as it allows the author to change colours all over the process.

Figure 57: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-006.

Q: You are an artist, but also an engineer, a scientist. People often think that scientists are “dry” persons, that just think by numbers and logic. I think you can object against this view!

JM: Yes. Normally, people have that idea. But it is not right. Even the more “traditional” engineers or scientists, they must be very creative to perform their work. We’ve all seen engineering work where we say, Wow, that’s a work of art! Personally, I do not know if I am an engineer that makes art, or an artist that does engineering. Whenever I can, I bring comics to Science, and Science to Comics. An example of the first case is our “STARTY”. An example of the second case is what I did a few years ago with a colleague of mine who is a biologist. He, using my hair, extracted my DNA. This DNA was multiplied and placed in an alcohol suspension, which I mixed with the ink with which I drew the autographs for one of my books.

Q: Let’s talk about Starty. You came up with this idea immediately, and everyone was enthusiastic about it. Let’s explain why we chose a robot, with a somewhat “steam-punk” (please correct me if I am wrong, João!) appearance, as testimonial for START.

JM: The idea of making a comic book with the work we are developing in the START project occurred at the first project meeting. Some colleagues suggested creating a kind of dictionary with some of the main topics about thermoelectric materials and devices. The project leader immediately said that what would be done was a Comic Book, for the general public, and I would draw it. So, considering the nowadays reality, we decided to use a small robot, with the capacity of explain to everyone what we are doing. Not only explaining, but also answering to questions that someone could do. It’s natural AI

Q: What should people expect now? I think we will see Starty not only in the cartoons, but also elsewhere – who said “game”? Can we give some spoilers?

JM: Yes, our scientists are keen on showing the European (and not only) people what we are developing in the START project. So, various approaches can be taken. One is the STARTY comic book, and the other one is a Board Game, that can be played by up to four players or four teams. So, questions and answers are the way the players can go along the game, having fun and at the same time acquiring some knowledge about the area of our project, regarding the materials, the devices, the way they are manufactured, their use and some aspects of sustainability and circular economy. It will be possible to play this game on a board, or in digital format.

We are looking forward to Starty’s new adventures, and we hope that some readers can also be attracted by your other works. Thanks, João!

JM: I hope that both the Comics and the Board Game can help the public become familiar with the topic of thermoelectric devices and materials, as it will be something they will increasingly encounter on a daily basis. Thank you so much.

Well, stay tuned with us and you will have more from João!

Figure 58: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-007.

START CHRONICLES: GEOLOGY, THERMOELECTRICS AND MORE

News from Work Packages

NEWS FROM WORK PACKAGE 4 “Maximising thermal stability”

A task force has been created within WP4 to specifically investigate how to maximize the thermal stability of the tetrahedrites through composition optimization, while mitigating any deleterious effects on thermoelectric performance. Keeping in mind that Fe substitution is to be maximized to take fully advantage of the high proportion of this element in the ore, two research lines are currently being pursued:

1. Substitution of copper by refractory metals to minimize sulphur sublimation and possibly promote the formation of a passivation layer through oxidation in service conditions.
2. Substitution of copper by nickel following the suggestion of the industrial consultant involved in the project.

Evaluation is carried out by screening the compositions through high energy ball milling followed by thermogravimetric experiments in inert and oxidative atmospheres. The best materials in terms of minimization of sulphur sublimation are subsequently sintered and tested to determine the power factors and thermoelectric figure of merits.

Figure 2 - Materials to be tested by thermogravimetry at 350 °C for 24h.

Figure 3 - Apparatus used for thermogravimetry measurements.

NEWS FROM WORK PACKAGE 5 “Design and construction of prototype TE modules”

In Task T5.1, the COMSOL model developed by RGS and SINTEF successfully incorporated the experimental data of the synthetically produced p-type tetrahedrite and the n-type magnesium antimonide material (Figure 4(a)). The temperature of the “Hot-Side” was fixed at 350°C to simulate the high-temperature application (Combined Heat and Power generation, CHP) and the fill factor (ratio of active thermoelectric material to uncouple surface area) was varied to optimize for maximum power generation (Figure 4(b,c)). In the following steps we will account for the electrical resistances of the interfacial materials (diffusion barrier layer, bonding material) and perform a detailed mechanical stress analysis of such a uncouple.

Task T5.2 focusses on the physical build-up of the module. A selected diffusion barrier layer was coated on both the p- and n-type materials as shown in Figure 5(a). Following this, the first dicing tests were carried out to obtain pellets (as shown in Figure 5(b,c)) to fabricate the first small tri-uncouple modules (Figure 5(d)). The electrical resistances of these uncouples will be measured, followed by a careful evaluation of the nanostructured silver bonds (cross-sectional imaging, shear tests). The next steps will involve the preparations for one-step bonding of the entire module (31 uncouples), including the design and fabrication of a stencil plate for silver paste application and of a brazing jig for holding the 62 thermoelectric pellets in place.

Figure 4 - COMSOL model developed by RGS and SINTEF: a) model, temperature of the “Hot-Side” fixed at 350°C; b) fill factor dependence of maximum power; c) hot side temperature dependence of heat flux density and power density.

Figure 5 - Building a module. a) coating both p- and n-type elements with a diffusion barrier; b) slicing of the wafers; c) individual elements; d) design of the tri-uncouple module.

NEWS FROM WORK PACKAGE 7 “Preparing for the future”

In WP7 there are parallel activities going on for investigating and enhancing both the short/ mid-term and the long-term future potentials of sustainable thermoelectric systems and applications.

During the 2024 Annual Assembly meeting (6th and 7th June 2024, Oslo), two workshops were held with the lead of LPRC. On Day 1, the focus was on data collection on commercial and feasibility aspects and key parameters of the START value chain that formulates the basis for assessing the industrial and economic viability of future technological developments. Day 2 included another workshop, this time dedicated to the sustainability of the START project itself after the funding period. During the event, participants contributed to the creation of a Lean Canvas of the START Service Company, that is to be established during the project lifetime to ensure that START results and findings are brought out to society and, more importantly, to potential businesses that will become the beneficiaries of a sustainable thermoelectric-based economic environment.

Figure 6 : Lean Canvas for the START Service Company developed during the workshop on sustainability of the START project.

In WP7 there are parallel activities going on for investigating and enhancing both the short/mid-term and the long-term future potentials of sustainable thermoelectric systems and applications.

During the 2024 Annual Assembly meeting (6th and 7th June 2024, Oslo), two workshops were held with the lead of LPRC. On Day 1, the focus was on data collection on commercial and feasibility aspects and key parameters of the START value chain that formulates the basis for assessing the industrial and economic viability of future technological developments. Day 2 included another workshop, this time dedicated to the sustainability of the START project itself after the funding period. During the event, participants contributed to the creation of a Lean Canvas of the START Service Company, that is to be established during the project lifetime to ensure that START results and findings are brought out to society and, more importantly, to potential businesses that will become the beneficiaries of a sustainable thermoelectric-based economic environment.

START Value Chain framework

Figure 7 : START Value Chain framework developed for the START project.

Figure 61: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-010.

START Annual Assembly in Oslo, 6-7 June 2024

On 6th and 7th June 2024, it was time to meet all together again for our third General Assembly. The host this time, in the fantastic city of Oslo, was the team at SINTEF, that let us use a very good meeting room in its great premises just some metro stops away from the centre of Oslo. Apart from some remarkably sunny Nordic weather (that you can see in [Figure 6](#)), the meeting was remarkable for the very interesting discussions among partners on the technical work done, and the challenges and opportunities that emerged from the various internal workshops organised within each work package. It was a time were all could review the results of the activities on minerals characterisation and concentration, preparation of tetrahedrite powders, optimisation of the composition, fabrication of samples and their characterisation, assessment of material stability, evaluation of sustainability, and dissemination and exploitation efforts. The activities were reviewed and discussed, and a plan for the next month was made for each task.

A lovely consortium dinner took place downtown Oslo on the night of the 6th.

During the second day the partners also actively took part in START's 5th free webinar (see the relevant news item below).

J.-Y. Escabasse was also involved in the meeting as a member of the Scientific Advisory Board (thanks Jean-Yves!) and spoke in the webinar as well.

We look forward to the next meeting in 2025!

Figure 8 - The START group at the third general assembly held in Oslo, at SINTEF's premises.

START webinar #5

As mentioned, we ran our 5th free START webinar during our Annual Meeting in SINTEF's facilities in Oslo (Norway), on 7th June 2024. The meeting room was fully equipped for hybrid meetings, thanks to SINTEF, so we had two speakers on site, and one connected remotely, and we had about 60 registrants for that part.

The hybrid event was dedicated to the important topic "Thermoelectric devices and applications": our two TE device producers and industrial partners, RGS Development and TEGnology, presented on high- and low-temperature applications, with speeches by Maarten den Heijer and Hao Yin, respectively. Additionally, we announced a new project, STAR-TREC, involving J.-I. Escabasse, member of our Scientific Advisory Board, as a presenter.

We also used the webinar to advertise for the Industrial Workshop, very linked to the theme of the session, that we were organising for the next September in Copenhagen (see below).

This is the full agenda of the 5th webinar:

Webinar "Thermoelectric devices and applications" – Friday, June 7th (11:00 – 12:45 CEST)

- 11:00 Welcome and introduction by Bruno Vicenzi (European Powder Metallurgy Association) and Filipe Neves (LNEG)
- 11:00-11:30: "Thermoelectric Power Generation applications for Heavy industries and Combined Heat and Power" by Maarten den Heijer (RGS Development) [Slides only]
- 11:30-12:00: "100% Green Power for IoT sensors and industrial applications from low-grade excessive heat" by Hao Yin (TEGnology)
- 12:00-12:30: "Adding value to TEG design by Additive Manufacturing: illustration in STARTREC, a new HORIZON project" by Jean-Yves Escabasse (CEA-Liten and START's Scientific Advisory Board)
- 12:30-12:45: Q&A

The footage was unfortunately incomplete due to an IT issue, but the partially recovered video has later been made available in our website's Multimedia page, and of course on our YouTube channel¹. One of the presentations has been made available in the video only as slides and we apologise for that.

Thanks to the speakers and to all participants!

Project: 101058632
HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01

Co-funded by
the European Union

Closing remarks

Sizeable Markets for Thermoelectrics can be identified. These are new markets, which require to be established across the value chain

The value chain development starts with raising end user interest and initiation of launching projects. Therefore the solution must be sufficiently mature (>TRL6)

All positions in the value chain will have to move simultaneously, hence share the recognition of future perspective

5th START Webinar: Thermoelectric devices and applications, June 7th, 2024
www.start-heproject.com

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 9 - A screenshot from the 5th webinar footage.

Figure 63: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-012.

START Industrial Workshop “Re-structuring of EU value chain on thermoelectrics - From supply chain to end user”, Kastrup (Denmark), 26th September 2024

Following several internal discussions on how to foster a quantum leap in the use of thermoelectrics, in particular in Europe, we came up with the idea of organizing an Industrial Workshop to try to re-structure an effective value chain in Europe. One of the objectives was also that thermoelectrics be recognized as one of the significant ways to make Europe more energy efficient in a sustainable way.

In coordination with the M-era.Net project THERMOS and the Eurostars project FLEX-TEG and based on the local efforts of our partner TEGnology, we invited all relevant stakeholders (all known companies using thermoelectric devices, those who are interested in introducing them, all industrial companies, startups and research actors in the field) by direct contacts and online advertisement.

The venue for the one-day workshop, that was totally free of charge, was the Clarion Hotel at Copenhagen Airport, a very convenient place as it is directly connected to the airport arrival hall, easy to reach for the participants from anywhere in the world. And in fact, we had speakers and participants even coming from Korea!

The agenda was split into two main parts: first a plenary part with several invited speakers, and in the afternoon, three different breakout sessions on different aspects, plus a specific time for networking and matchmaking, at the end of the event, during a break. H. Yin gave his closing remarks at the end.

Full details on the event, including the final programme with all speakers, can be found on our website, in a specific page² that was used to advertise the workshop and collect more registrations.

The participation was very good! Seventy people in the workshop, which is not easy for a relatively small community like that of thermoelectrics; and speakers from important actors in the field like the European Energy Research Agency, the Japanese National Institute for Materials Science, the Korea Advanced Institute of Science & Technology and the Hanyang University in South Korea, The German Space Centre (DLR), TU Vienna, RGS Development, QuickOhm, DTP Thermoelectrics, Wideco, Fraunhofer IFAM, and many others in the breakout sessions. The three projects (START, THERMOS and FLEX-TEG) presented themselves. The breakout rooms in the afternoon, with four more speakers and a discussion in each room, allowed the participants to delve into more details for the respective competence areas, and during lunches and breaks they had the chance of meeting (or re-meeting) each other and establish connections. Very useful also for our consortium colleagues that are working for the future exploitation of the START results.

The meeting was a clear success and there may be a next edition in the future. START is keen on obtaining improvements in the supply chain, not only for the tetrahedrite solution it pursues, but for the whole industry.

Figure 10 - Group photo of the participants at the START Industrial Workshop in Copenhagen

Figure 11 - The full room in the plenary session.

Figure 12 - Our four speakers in the event, clockwise and “in order of appearance” in the workshop, starting from top left: Hao Yin (TEGnology), also local organiser and moderator of the plenary; Maarten den Heijer (RGS Developments); Filipe Neves (LNEG), our coordinator; Alvise Bianchin (MBN Nanomaterialia).

START online training course, 25th September-3rd October 2024

Between September 25 and October 3, 2024, the "Virtual Course: Mining Environmental Liabilities and Secondary Raw Materials" was held, organized by ASGMI³. This course was organized within the framework of the START project with the objective to provide participants a deep understanding of mining processes, their environmental and social impacts, and equipping them with the necessary tools for the identification, evaluation, and remediation of environmental liabilities.

The course, primarily aimed at postgraduate students, featured 7 experts from different fields who, in 6 sessions, delivered lectures on the following topics:

- Fundamentals of Mining Environmental Liabilities (MELs)
- Environmental and health risks related to MELs: From risk assessment to rehabilitation
- Remediation of Environmental Liabilities
- Reuse of Secondary Raw Materials
- Environmental Management and Corporate Social Responsibility
- Colleagues from IGME who are involved in the START project gave a presentation about the project.

The workshop had 419 registered participants, including 112 students from various countries in Europe and outside the European Union.

The materials (presentations and session recordings) are available on the ASGMI website³. Students requesting a certificate of completion were required to first complete an evaluation test.

Figure 13 - The advertisement used to collect registrations, on websites and on social media.

Figure 14 - A moment of the course, where tetrahedrite, our material of election, was introduced.

Figure 65: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-014.

START seeks synergies with the XTRACT project

In its clustering activities, START is getting in contact with other projects that share one or more topics with us. This is the case of XTRACT, another Horizon Europe project that was funded in 2023. Although XTRACT clearly focused on the improvement of mining and processing, in a preliminary meeting we had together we already identified the use of secondary raw materials (in our case clearly the mine wastes containing tetrahedrites) to extract useful materials for the EU industrial supply chains as a common ground.

We will surely do many things together with XTRACT in the near future! Stay tuned with us (next issues of the newsletter, news on common events and initiatives) and then for more details. Here follows a short description of XTRACT, but you can also find more information on the XTRACT project in the links⁴.

XTRACT (Horizon Europe, project number 101138432)

The XTRACT project aims to develop a sustainable ecosystem for innovative resource recovery and complex ore extraction. The goal is to reduce ore losses and mining waste through a novel system for controlling ore loss and dilution, thereby reducing overall mine emissions and economic loss. XTRACT will develop and validate innovative microinvasive technologies and solutions tailored for remote, "hard-to-reach" locations and small quantities where extraction is typically unprofitable. The in-situ bioleaching process and membrane treatment will be optimized to achieve maximum metal recovery.

Launched in December 2023, XTRACT is a three-year Horizon Europe-funded initiative involving 14 partner organizations from 9 European countries. The project aims to contribute to the EU Climate Neutrality Goals by introducing low-TRL green technologies for mine waste remediation and the extraction of precious metals. XTRACT aligns with the European Commission's ambition for self-sufficiency in critical raw materials essential for the green and digital transition.

Figure 15 - The XTRACT homepage, where the main topic and the mines where they are actively working are clearly indicated.

Figure 66: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-015.

Other START dissemination events

XXIX Ordinary General Assembly of ASGMI, April 2024, Huasca de Ocampo – Pachuca de Soto, Hidalgo, Mexico.

The XXIX Ordinary General Assembly of ASGMI⁵ took place in April 2024 in Mexico. The event was attended by Directors of the Geological Surveys from 15 different Ibero-American countries, as well as invited experts from the Geological Survey of Canada and the United States. During the event, a technical workshop was held in which the topic “the role of geological services in the energy transition” was discussed. This workshop highlighted the importance of sustainable mining activities, which involve the proper management of mining environmental liabilities

Figure 16 - Group of participants at the XXIX Ordinary Assembly of ASGMI, in Mexico.

and the reuse of secondary raw materials. In this context, a presentation was also made about the activities of ASGMI's Expert Groups, ASGMI's participation in European projects, and a presentation of the START project.

EPMA General Assembly, Brussels and hybrid, 16th May 2024

The 2024 EPMA General Assembly was celebrated on 16th May 2024 in a hybrid format and gathered many members of the association (about 30 considering on site and remotely connected participants). In the afternoon, a presentation of Serena Busatto (MBN Nanomaterialia SpA) was given, titled “START approach to powder metallurgy: Advanced materials for energy harvesting”.

Figure 17 - A moment of Serena Busatto's presentation in the EPMA General Assembly 2024.

START at the 40th International and 20th European Thermoelectric Conference, ICT/ECT 2024, Krakow, Poland, 30th June - 4th July 2024

40th International Conference on Thermoelectrics - ICT/ECT2024START was present at the 40th International and 20th European Thermoelectric Conference, ICT/ECT 2024, that took place in Krakow, Poland, from 30th June to 4th July 2024. This is the main international event for thermoelectrics, that this year put together the European and the International events in the Polish conference.

Welcome		Conference	Traveling	Registration	Thermoelectric School	Login	LOT Polish Airlines	Official Car
11:00-11:30	Coffee break	Large Hall A Session: TE systems Chairmen: Jan KOBERG	Large Hall B Session: Cu-based chalcogenides II Chairmen: Paul VAQUERO	Medium Hall Session: Composites Chairmen: Xianfeng ZHANG				
11:30-11:45	M. M. MAIA, A. L. Pires, Andre M. PEREIRA Wireless Energy Transfer using Photothermoelectric Devices	Filipo NEVES Tetrahedrite-based thermoelectrics: the START project's approach	Van Quang NGUYEN, Thi Hong NGUYEN, Cheng Chang LI, Dong Zhao, Jungho Park, Jae Ki Lee, Su-dong Park, Sanghae CHO SnSe-SnSe ₂ & Bi ₂ Se ₃ -SnSe Multilayered Composite Crystal Growth and Thermoelectric Properties	Andrej KOCIBEK, Tomášek M. F. Chaves, M. Krawczuk, J. P. Martin-Pastor, J. F. Sánchez-Raya Novel 2D materials with tunable properties for thermoelectric application				
11:45-12:00	Álvaro CASI, A. Patricia, C. David, A. Wai, R. Antonio Thermoelectric Subcooling Optimization for Enhancing Vapor Compression Refrigeration Systems	Jialin LI, Liang LI, P. Leszczynski, C. Cantelli, B. Lenoir, P. Heredia, A. Kobyrczyk Thermoelectric properties of Cu ₂ Se _{1-x} Mn _x Se _{2-x} Te _{2-x} S _x tetrahedrites	Peter BALÁŽ, M. Rajčák, M. Uváčovská, L. Subčáková, N. Daniš, P. Levinský, K. Křížek, J. Hájek, R. Čadež, M. Achardová, M. Bašič Mechanochemistry in Preparation of Chalcite-Spinelle Nanocomposites: Kinetics of Synthesis and Thermoelectricity					
12:00-12:15	David A STRAIN, M. Aratz, L. Catalan, N. Pascual, P. Alegria Electric production from batteries of volcanic origin in Antarctica by passive thermoelectric generators	Cancobed Tian-Yu YANG, Yi-Ji Zhang, Zhi-Hua Peng Pseudomorphic Phase Engineering for Improved Thermoelectric Performance in Bi ₂ Te ₃ Nanorods	Abinaya RENGARAJAN, M. Narayanan, J. Archana Enhanced charge transfer at znn-barrier injection of Mn ₂ (p-MnO ₂) ₂ nanocomposites for thermoelectric applications					
12:15-12:30	Mykola MAKSYMUK, T. Parashchuk, A. Burbak, K. T. Wabickowski High energy conversion efficiency realized by the thermoelectric converter with stepwise legs	Franka MISHOK, K. Saki, M. Krawczuk, S. Michalk Purity control and thermoelectric properties of polycrystalline SnTe doped with Bi	Noureddine OUELLOU, A. Portavoce, K. Hosomura Crystalline Mg ₃ As ₂ thermoelectric thin films for energy harvesting applications					
12:30-12:45	Alex ATTAR, A. Albarzi A New Design of a Geothermal Thermoelectric Generator System (CTEG) for Geothermal Heat Recovery	Sama SALAM, S. Pathak, C. Adoni, V. Cristiana, H. Mahboubi, Z. Bilwani, C. Vignoli, P. D'Amico, R. Fazzolari, N. Bianchini, A. Ferry, S.R. Badkar Phonon-drag in a graphite channel buried in diamond						
12:45-13:00								

Figure 18 - Programme of the ECT/ACT conference in Krakow, with F. Neves' presentation highlighted in orange (top center).

The technical programme saw two presentations from START.

F. Neves (LNEG) presented as invited speaker in the session “Cu-based Chalcogenides II” on Thursday 4th July with the title “Tetrahedrite-based thermoelectrics: the START project's approach” (Figure 18), while A. Ray (RGS Developments) spoke on the same day on the topic “Thermoelectric Modules and Applications: An Industrial Perspective” in the session “TE Industry” (Figure 19).

www.START-HEproject.com 16 November 2024 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14062520

Figure 67: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-016.

Welcome **Conference** Traveling Registration Thermolectrics School Login LOT Polish Airlines - Official Car

THURSDAY, JULY 4, 2024			
	Large Hall A Session: TE Industry Chairman: Jean-Pierre FLEURBAE	Large Hall B Session: ZnTe phase II Chairman: Franck GASCOIN	Medium Hall Session: Organic materials Chairman: Przemysław OGA
9:00-9:10	Vincent LINSSELS Thermoelectric Metrology: A Comprehensive Review from a Manufacturer's Perspective (Linsse Messtechnik GmbH, Germany)	Alexandra ZELWINKA Thermoelectric properties of layered Al ₂ O ₃ compounds with tunable vacancy concentrations and interlayer bonding	S. Muhammad, D. Motta, M. Bonomo, F. Marabbi, S. Carl, S. Caramori, C. Barilo, Andrea REALE Liquid eutectic solvents for thermoelectrochemical reactor systems for waste-heat recovery applications
9:10-9:20	R. Muhamman, R. Lyland, Richard S. TULEY DEVICE SUBSTRATES: High performance with low thermal conductivity (European Thermodynamics Ltd, UK)		Konosuke OCHI, Ryota MIYAKE, Yuki HANAMURA, HIROKAZU IMAI Thermoelectric Properties of Ionic Liquids
9:30-9:45	Alex GUKSEVICH, I. Steiner, Z. Dashkevsky, S. Vitruk A High Performance Thermoelectric Modules with Substrate Made by Vapor Chamber Technology (Double Check Ltd, Israel)	S. Baccaro, A. Duchesneau, Sulten FIDREFF Structural disorder in ZnTe phases: The case of V ₂ Al ₂ Sn ₂ and Y ₂ Al ₂ Sn ₂	O. Calaisse, R. Cecouli, M. Paril, P. Mancaella, D. Gantli, M. Cavallin, V. Morandi, Fabiola LISCIO Enhancing Organic Thermoelectric Materials Through Local Control Wetting
9:45-10:00	Anirudha RAVI, M. D. Hojer Thermoelectric Modules and Applications: An Industrial Perspective (RGS Development, Netherlands)	Amandine DURBACHY, F. Kropp, E. Müller, J. de Boer Unlocking the full potential of Mg ₂ Sb by unravelling the interrelation of phase constitution and thermoelectric properties	Seymon ODOGO, P. Datta, K. Wojcikowski Influence of acido p-type dopant on thermoelectric properties of conducting polymers
10:00-10:15	Damian KARPOWICZ Enhancing Thermoelectric Efficiency: The U-HAST Generator Solution (Genione, Poland)	Liangqian WANG, W. Zhang, S. Beck, N. Karamoto, D. H. Nguyen, T. Mori High-performance Mg ₂ Sb-based thermoelectrics with increased structural ordering and microstructure evolution	M. Betty LINGCOLN, R. A. Sujatha, P. Velusamy, H. Ikeda Flexible polymer based flexible thermoelectric generator for wearable human body energy harvesting
10:15-10:20	Uttam GHO SHIL, K. Kolla, A. Staudenberger, M. Köster, J. Jamison Large-Scale Integrated Microstructural Technology (Shenzek Inc., Austin, USA)	Mejia LIU, C. Chen, H. Li, Y. Chen Advancing thermoelectric performance in Al ₂ CoSb-based ZnTe phase via the synergistic effect of Sb deficiency and dynamic doping	Sanyin QIU, D. Xu, C. Ming, P. Qiu, X. Shi, I. Chan High-performance n-type Bi ₂ Te ₃ /PbTe/graphyne organic-inorganic flexible thermoelectric composites
10:30-10:45	Marek BOROCH, Michal MUSIAL The performance study of the gas-liquid thermoelectric generator for waste heat harvesting (TECOG, Poland)	Shunya SAKINE, A. Ayulasa, N. Kikuchi, Y. Yamashita, H. Ueno Thermoelectric performance of epitaxially grown Mg ₂ Sb ₂ Te film on sapphire substrate	Bajjal MUHAMMAD, M. Faruqi, S. Gallone, C. Barilo, A. Reale Printable thermoelectric devices based on organic semiconductor composites for low-temperature grade energy harvesting
10:45-11:00		Hong-ling SHANG, H.-W. Gu, F.-J. Ding Realizing ultrahigh zT values in Mg ₂ Sb ₂ Te ₂ for superior thermoelectric power-generation	Shun-ichiro ITO, K. Katsurashi, H. Tanaka, S. Chae, H. Ohta, T. Terasaki Temperature Dependence of Thermoelectric Properties in Electrochemically-Doped Conducting Polymer P6TTT

Figure 19 - Programme of the ECT/ICT conference in Krakow, with A. Ray's presentation highlighted.

Furthermore, the project had its booth in the exhibition (Figure 20) that was appreciated and led to some useful contacts, mainly with academicians in the sector.

START will likely take part in the next editions, although in next years the event will be just European (ECT).

Figure 20 - Members of the START consortium at the booth in the ECT/ICT conference in Krakow

EPMA Powder Metallurgy Summer School, Alessandria (Italy), 15th - 19th July 2024

The 22nd EPMA powder Metallurgy Summer School was hosted in Alessandria (Italy) from 15th to 19th July. In this event, that has been running since 1998, more than 60 trainees coming from all over Europe (and even from outside Europe) are being taught by experienced lecturers from academy and industry the basics of powder metallurgy. In this edition, they were shown a small demonstration about thermoelectric devices. The demo was brought to the School by TEGnology, one of the partners in the project, and Hao Yin explained how these devices can be used for waste heat harvesting and other applications. This happened in two separate groups, one on Wednesday 17th and the other on Thursday 18th.

Figure 21 - H.Yin (TEGnology) addressing a group of students at the 22nd EPMA PM Summer School.

In addition to this, B. Vicenzi of EPMA gave some basic info about the project in the initial speech of the school, and START leaflets were available for the participants

Figure 22 - B; Vicenzi (EPMA) explaining the basics of START in the plenary session of the 22nd EPMA PM Summer School on Monday 15th July 2024.

START at the MacaroNight on 27th September 2024

In 2024 there was again a START presence at the MacaroNight event that LPRC organised in the Canary Islands as part of the European Researchers' Night. LPRC printed 100 copies of the START comic, which were given to the visitors at the EU Corner. In total, there were 762 students and 171 general public attending the event.

Figure 22 - START leaflets available at the 2024 Macaronight.

Euro PM2024 Congress & Exhibition, Malmö (Sweden), 29th September - 2nd October 2024

START took part with its own booth in the Euro PM2024 European Powder Metallurgy Congress & Exhibition, organised as usual by EPMA and taking place this year in Malmö (Sweden) from 29th September to 2nd October. The booth featured all materials about the project, posters, roller banner, leaflets, looping video with the Starty stories published to date, samples in the showcase, all available for the visitors of the large PM community. The thermoelectric device demo from TEGnology already taken to the EPMA Summer School was shown at the booth as well.

This year there was no presentation of START in the technical sessions, but there was again a visit of the so-called Young Engineers, a group of students that have a special care during the congress, and in particular visit the exhibition booths; D; Karpowicz (GeniCore), A. Colella and E. Forlin (MBN) addressed them on the afternoon of Tuesday 1st October.

Figure 69: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-018.

Figure 23 - The START booth at the Euro PM2024 Congress & Exhibition in Sweden.

Figure 24 - Detail of the START booth's showcase at the Euro PM2024 Congress & Exhibition in Sweden, with various materials, including the TE demo (visible on the wooden tabletop).

Future events

START is organizing its participation in several more events in the next months.

- XXX General Assembly of ASGMI: This will be held during the last week of March in Peru.
- First MERCOSUR Geology and Mining Meeting: ASGMI has been invited to participate at the main table, providing an opportunity to present ASGMI's activities, including a mention of the START project.

More events might see START participating in addition to these, and we will inform you in due time.

If you are from a similar initiative or project and would like to organise something together, please contact us!

REGISTER FOR THE CLUSTERING EVENT IN BRUSSELS!

As a result of its clustering initiatives, START is preparing a Clustering Event in Brussels, on 10th December 2024 from 14:00 to 17:30, at the Hotel Marivaux: it will be a Side Event of the well-known and established EU Raw Materials Week⁶, that will run from 9th to 13th December at the nearby La Plaza Hotel, also in Brussels, organized by the European Commission, and where START will also be visible.. The title of the workshop is "Supporting the Critical Raw Materials Act: Research Projects in the European Union"⁷. This event will bring together 8 European projects for presentations (and likely a contribution from EU officials) and a round table discussion.; The aim of the event is to create a space for exchange where project progress can be shared, common challenges identified, and collaboration and the creation of new partnerships fostered, and will include a networking session to explore synergies among them.

This is the list of projects invited to speak:

- - START
- - GSEU⁸
- - FutuRaM⁹
- - CRM Geothermal¹⁰
- - CIRAN¹¹
- - SUPREEMO¹²
- - REESOURCE¹³
- - REPTIS¹⁴

The workshop will be moderated by Thomas Unterweissacher, of GEO Unterweissacher, one of the partners of START (see its description in this issue of the Newsletter), and will include a panel discussion and a networking time at the end of the event.

Participation is free of charge, but registration beforehand is necessary, with a deadline on 25th November 2024. If you are interested, do not forget to register on our website by reaching the relevant page.

TECHNICAL PILLS

Some useful information that covers topics that are linked to our project! In this issue, we deal with the basics of Life Cycle Analysis and its use within START.

Basic LCA Concepts and LCA in the START project

Introduction

Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) is a methodology which aims at assessing potential environmental impacts of a product across its life cycle, from extraction of natural resources or raw material acquisition to final disposal (end-of-life). It is mainly used to compare impacts of different products with the same function or a product in relation to a standard and identifying the most impactful stages and processes of the products life cycle. Thus, LCA can also be an instrument for industry implying cost-savings and competitive advantages.

LCA evaluates impacts related to a functional unit (FU) of the product or service, defined according to the goal and scope of the assessment, and all inputs and outputs throughout the life cycle are related to the FU. LCA can be carried out from two perspectives, i.e. Cradle-to-grave, which includes complete life cycle stages, raw material extraction/generation, production, transportation/distribution, use and the end-of-life; and Cradle-to-gate, which concerns only initial stages of life cycle, raw material extraction/generation and production.

LCA involves several steps ([Figure 25](#) and [Figure 26](#)), which include:

- 1) Definition of the goal and scope – the reasons for the study, intended audience, system boundaries, assumptions, limitations and functional unit are defined.
- 2) Life cycle inventory (LCI) – data describing the system is collected (e.g. materials, travel distances, consumables) and converted to provide the description of the systems. Data can be retrieved from scientific research papers, life cycle databases and manufacturer information, among other sources.
- 3) Impact Assessment (LCIA) – in which material, energy and waste flows are modelled based on the LCI, and physical quantities are translated into environmental indicators.
- 4) Interpretation and improvement – the results are evaluated and interpreted regarding the significance and uncertainty of the environmental indicators. Based on these results, the system or product can be modified and improved.

Figure 71: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-020.

Figure 25 - LCA framework and simplified operational phases

Figure 26 - Detailed overview on LCA approach.

Figure 72: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-021.

It is worth noting that LCA is not a substitute for location dependent assessments (e.g. Environmental Impact Assessments) nor risk analysis or strategic assessments, and it can be rather considered as a complementary tool. Furthermore, LCA can be paired with a Life Cycle Cost (LCC) analysis, which evaluates all the costs throughout the life cycle phases. The associated effective and/or potential costs (including e.g. capital investment, production costs, maintenance costs, capital replacement costs, operating costs, resale, salvage, or disposal cost) are considered within the LCC analysis.

A wider overview on the LCA basic principles and application on the project can be found both in the START website and the workshop on LCA (available from YouTube¹⁵) presented by 3drivers in June 2023.

LCA in Start

In START, LCA will be used to compare environmental impacts of the mineral-derived sulphide-based semiconductor TE generators (TEGs) developed in the project based on tetrahedrites, obtained from mining waste (with a general formula of $(\text{Cu,Fe})_2(\text{Sb,As})_4\text{S}_{13}$, comparing the different obtained TEGs and the most commonly used, commercially available TE generators (e.g. based on BiTe - bismuth tellurite and PbTe - lead tellurite, for low and medium/high temperature applications, respectively). LCA analysis will be referred to a specific TEG module (n-type and p-type legs, interconnect and with ceramic plate); TE generators will be analysed in a full life cycle perspective (cradle-to-grave), from raw material extraction/processing, until the end-of-life. The functional unit was defined as 1 kWh of electricity produced by the TE generator. Furthermore, Life Cycle Cost (LCC) analysis will also be performed to determine potential and/or effective costs of these machines. The LCC model will include capital, facility & management (operation and productivity) and disposal costs, although maintenance costs for TEG use stage should not be considered, since this type of device has no interchangeable parts.

The environmental impact and costs analysis will be performed concerning scenarios with and without waste heat recovery and semiconductor material recovered from tailings (naturally formed tetrahedrite), and in comparison with semiconductor material based on synthetic tetrahedrite. A list of items for collection of data regarding the TEG life cycle inputs and outputs, as a result of recent implementation of the methodology specific for the LCA inventory development, is presented in [Figure 27](#).

<p>Inputs (materials):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sulphides tetrahedrite for p-type formulation (kg) ▪ Cleaning products, other reagents and consumables (kg) ▪ n-type component base material (kg) ▪ TEG components (alumina plates, cooper interconnectors, others) (kg) ▪ Cleaning fluids, adhesives, solder, other consumables (kg) ▪ Water consumption (kg or m3) ▪ Diesel consumption (kg or m3) <p>Inputs (energy consumption):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mining activities (extraction, concentration, purification) (kWh, MJ) ▪ p-type production (powder technology, rapid solidification, layer deposition, others) (kWh, MJ) ▪ n-type production (kWh, MJ) ▪ TEG assembly production (kWh, MJ) ▪ End-of-Life technology (kWh, MJ) <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Electricity produced by the TEG (kWh) ▪ Wastes, leachates (kg or m3) ▪ Air emissions (kg)

Figure 27 - List of input and output used in the LCA analysis.

MEET THE EXPERTS

In this issue we present you two interviews.

The first is with Dr. Doris Hlam-Galvez, of Hatch Consulting, who is a world-renowned expert, member of the Board of Directors of the prestigious PDAC (Prospectors and Developers Association of Canada). She tackles global challenges like the present warming and proposes a holistic solution to our current situation that is the DSP (Designing Sustainable Prosperity) method. Read more below!

The second interview is with our START member Hao Yin of TEGnology ApS and is a reprint of the interview given to the Associazione Italiana di Termoelettricità (Italian Thermoelectricity Association). Read Hao's ideas on thermoelectric applications from his own words!

Interview with Dr. Doris HIAM-GALVEZ

Question: The recently released report by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) on greenhouse gas emissions ("UNEP Emissions Gap Report 2024") highlights that achieving a level of emissions reductions in line with the Paris Agreement target of 1.5°C is at serious risk of being compromised unless there is an immediate global mobilization and a six-fold increase in investment in mitigation actions. Dr. Doris, what are your thoughts on this and what strategies do you believe are most effective and realistic to be implemented in the short term so that the 1.5°C target can still be achieved?

Doris Galvez: Achieving the 1.5°C target calls for more than immediate innovation and investment; it requires societal transformation.

This means moving beyond isolated actions to designing integrated systems. Here, DSP plays a crucial role by creating ecosystems that balance development and sustainability, benefiting both people and the planet. Practically, each of us has a role- small shifts in consumption can collectively drive significant change, as seen during COVID. Meanwhile, we must urgently cut emissions by addressing major sources like fugitive emissions - leakage throughout the oil and gas sector - and accelerating the shift from high emissions energy sources to green energy such as wind and solar. This requires pressing both industry and governments to move beyond setting broad targets and commit to specific, actionable plans.

Q: You recently introduced the "Designing Sustainable Prosperity (DSP)" method, which focuses on long-term sustainable development. Can you describe this methodology and what contribution it can make to the active implementation of climate change solutions?

DHG: DSP is a holistic approach that unlocks untapped potential through system wide solutions to addresses climate change and regional resilience. By fostering economic diversification and scaling innovative solutions, DSP positions the regions as leaders in the knowledge economy, adapting educational systems to equip communities with future-focused skills that support long-term sustainable prosperity.

A key feature of DSP is how it frames the mining industry as catalyst for change, enabling regional prosperity by driving green innovation, circular economies, and lower impact mining methods. This approach aligns economic,

Figure 28 - Dr. Doris Hlam-Galvez is a senior Advisor at Hatch Consulting, Board Director, and an outspoken champion of sustainable development. She has a PhD in Metallurgy with broad senior level experience in leading organizations and driving significant expansion globally focused on value creation. For the past 16 years, her activities at Hatch involved leading regional operations and creating new and innovative businesses in Australia, South America, Europe & North America. Inspired by her work with global investors facing sustainability challenges, she developed "Designing Sustainable Prosperity (DSP)". A method to create resilient and sustainable regions. Her contribution to DSP has earned her the prestigious "CIM Distinguished Lecturer Award". Her book on the DSP method was recently published by Wiley. Designing Sustainable Prosperity (DSP) goes beyond just accessing and extracting the natural resources. It is an approach that unlocks the potential of resource-rich regions by integrating economic diversification, social well-being, and environmental sustainability. A systems design that leverages a multidisciplinary approach to co-create resilient regions and craft financially viable, environmentally responsible, and socially beneficial enterprises. This approach empowers local communities, fostering societal transformation and promoting a knowledge-based economy to meet market needs, all while aligning seamlessly with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UNSDGs).

Figure 74: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-023.

environmental, and social transformation, resulting in self-sustaining, climate resilient ecosystems. By integrating economic, environmental and social transformation, DSP helps build ecosystems where climate goals, community wellbeing and economic expansion reinforce each other, driving meaningful, long-lasting change.

Q: How do you envision the future of sustainable mining and what role does the DSP method play in this vision?

DHG: In the future of sustainable mining, I envisage a sector that not only minimizes its environmental footprint but actively contributes to regional resilience. DSP transforms mining into an enabler of regional prosperity that continues long after the mine has ceased to operate.

It positions sustainable mining as a key contributor to climate action and regional transformation, by balancing economic, social and environmental objectives, delivering enduring benefits for communities and ecosystems.

Q: Can you share some key milestones in your career that led you to focus on sustainable development and the creation of the DSP method? And what were the main challenges you faced while developing the DSP method?

DHG: Leading company operations around the world, I have witnessed the contrast between wealth and poverty in resource rich regions. Evidence that whatever we are doing is not working. For years, I have pondered if there was a better way to approach this complex situation. It has taken me 15 years to develop, implement and publish a book on a new way of achieving both development and sustainability.

One major challenge in creating DSP was helping people understand that real, lasting change requires a systems approach. We often work in silos, which limits our ability to tackle complex issues effectively.

DSP integrates scientific rigor with an emphasis on social transformation because regardless of innovative technologies or ideas, meaningful change occurs only when individuals are open and willing to collaborate. DSP employs a facilitated process in which key players co-create the future of their region through a structured seven-step process. The first two steps focus on preparing each individual and the team to broaden their perspectives about themselves and their region. This preparation enables them to progress to a stage where they can bring forth truly innovative ideas for system wide solutions, ensuring they are ready to create meaningful and specific action plans rather than general goals.

Q: What strategies do you recommend for fostering stronger partnerships between European stakeholders and other global regions to enhance sustainable development?

DHG: To enable Europeans to play a transformative role in fostering regional prosperity in resource rich areas, a strategic partnership is essential. Europeans' stakeholders can collaborate to build innovation hubs that address urgent climate challenges and position these regions as knowledge economy centres of excellence. By sharing expertise, Europeans can help create educational programs that equip local talent with skills to sustain these economies long after natural resources are exhausted. This cooperation should be done with developed nations especially with North America and China to drive global sustainability and strengthen long term resilience for these regions.

Q: The DSP method prioritizes waste reduction and the use of recycling and renewable resources. You have seen what the START project is trying to do in the field of thermoelectric device development, through a methodology that is based on "transforming mining waste into waste heat recovery materials". It is therefore a methodology that incorporates some of the ideas that were at the genesis of the DSP method. So, what is the aspect of the START project that you find more appealing, and why?

DHG: The START project redefines waste as a valuable resource by converting it into thermoelectric materials that capture waste heat and turn it into renewable energy. This approach mitigates environmental issues such as acid drainage, directly reducing the impact of mining on ecosystems, while supporting sustainable energy production. By creating new uses for mining byproducts, START has the potential to become an integral part of regional ecosystems, fostering circular economies that prioritize resource efficiency and environmental resilience.

Thanks for your views!

Figure 75: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-024.

Interview with Hao YIN, published on the bulletin of Associazione Italiana di Termoelettricità (Italian Association for Thermoelectricity, AIT)

Figure 29 - Dr. Hao Yin, CEO of TEGnology ApS, one of the partner companies in START, focused on TE devices production

With the kind permission of the Associazione Italiana di Termoelettricità (Italian Thermoelectricity Association), we share here the interview made by the AIT President Carlo Fanciulli to our partner Hao Yin, manager of TEGnology, published in June 2024 on the bulletin of AIT¹⁶. It contains interesting views about the thermoelectric industry and was also useful to attract participants to our Industrial Workshop in September.

Carlo Fanciulli: As a former researcher in thermoelectrics, Hao Yin started a company for designing and manufacturing thermoelectric generators for more than 10 years ago. Based on his observations and lessons, Hao agrees to share some personal thoughts, with the intention to accelerate the commercialization of thermoelectric generators. I want to thank Dr. Yin for accepting our invitation to share his vision on the market of thermoelectricity. What is your approach to the market development and what does drive you on the path of commercialization?

"Digging a tunnel" I have had a similar dream many times, when I'm stuck in darkness, trying to seek a tiny spot of vague light, which indicates the exit. If dreams only reflect reality, the reality is no less desperate. I usually compare the commercialization process to digging a tunnel from both ends. On one end, it's called technical "push" and on the other, the market "pull". When the tunnel finally got through, we call it a product-market fit. The situation when the market pull exceeds the technical push, often witnesses a new era of technology revolution, just as what is happening now in AI, the green transition and the climate change mitigation. However, it is not unusual during the technology commercialization, that the push exceeds the pull, which is also known as over-engineering. When a new technology doesn't have a market, it's often tempting to believe it is because the technology is not ready, yet. Well, this might often also be true. But the line between a perfect product (doesn't exist) and a good-

enough solution (much desired) worths investigating. And the criteria should be defined more by what the market wants, other than what can be done in a lab.

CF: This is something many of us see every time a new project must be designed. For thermoelectrics, in most of the cases, technology suffers specifically because of the low performances in terms of efficiency. What is your approach to this critical issue?

"Efficiency. Efficiency! Efficiency?" It has been my first lesson when learning thermoelectrics, that the efficiency of TEG is (relatively) low. And most of the R&D in thermoelectrics has been focused on fundamental research and materials engineering in boosting the efficiency. In terms of energy conversion, it's of course crucial to have the efficiency as high as possible, period. However, the question is, does it mean that the efficiency of TEG is too low to be useful at all? Take the photosynthesis process for example. If we calculate the yield of biomass (dry weight over the solar energy), the plants are converting no more than a few percent of the energy into their leaf and fruits (3.5% for sugarcane, among the highest). But that a few percent are supporting the whole population on the planet, generation after generation. Also, I couldn't stop thinking of another example, combustion engines. Burning, one of the least efficient manners of utilizing the energy that is stored in the chemical bonds in fossil fuels, has been the driving force for human society for over two centuries, bringing us from iron age to steam and electric age, still continuing. The calculation behind is, the fossil fuel is (was) cheap, compared to the benefits it brings us (from A to B in shorter time). So, it is worth to accept the low efficiency of combustion engines (25-30%). (Oh, by the way, yes, we need to pay back for the benefits we've enjoyed, by reducing the Carbon from the atmosphere.) So, the absolute efficiency might not bring the whole picture. It would be more inspiring to think what can we do with the current efficiency of TEGs. If we couldn't get more electricity output from the heat input, maybe we should spend some time in finding the applications where the heat is available anyway and the electricity is so valuable, that people don't care about the efficiency?

CF: The key to thermoelectric technology is the materials. A lot of efforts have been and still are spent in developing new materials with improved characteristics. However, the effective impact of such improvements on the products accessing the market is negligible. Could you give us your comment on this?

"From materials (labs) to products (markets)" I used to be so excited over a new set of data, that shows the zT of a sample is X percent higher than the previous, until frustrating amounts of failures in bringing the state-of-the-art samples into a working module, that barely delivers some meaningful power. I will still applaud sincerely for any breakthroughs in thermoelectrics. But the lessons should be learnt. We can easily start from the best material but end up in nowhere. The evils are in the details. We need

Figure 76: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-025.

innovative ideas and out-of-box solutions in the lab. That's the place where imagination should be set free. Science and technology are boundless. However, it doesn't hurt to come with a solution, you will still be the person who answers all the following questions. Nobody is there to do them for you. And the problems won't disappear by themselves. It is usually not the case, that you happen to use some spare time, between the intense brain sprints, to connect the new ideas to the industrial status quo. If you think the solution is still too early to answer the questions like "how to build a business on it", then try something easier, like "how to repeat the exercise 100 times by a less technical-savvy person", or "can the production be done without human intervention". Then start collecting some information that is required in the solution. It could be "the price/ availability/toxicity of the chemicals involved in the solution", or "the procedures of producing, say 100 kg of materials, or 10,000 modules", or "who should you talk to, after you've solved the problem", or simply, "what kind of people will eventually use the solution". These questions are most likely still there, when you assumingly can solve the current challenge. If you really are the first person answer the "last question" of a complex problem. If you can find some evidence that disqualify the argument, that "the solutions have been tried before and for some reason didn't work", it will make your solution more robust (and more likely, your funding application easier to get granted).

CF: All this is interesting. In your answer you are suggesting an approach often underestimated in lab. The shift of the focus from the improvement of the element of the chain to the design of a process capable to open the door to the product industrialization for such an element is a suggestion a lot of us are working on supporting the idea that an easier way could be better than a higher performance. But this opens the discussion about the availability of components and thermoelectric systems production worldwide. What do you think of this issue being on the "high readiness" side of the wall?

"Production & Supply-chain" It's not trivial to discuss where and how to get the TEGs produced. Without scalable production and reliable supply chain, we are still more or less creating visions only. Traditional commercially available Bi₂Te₃-based modules used to be produced in China, Russia and Ukraine, now mostly China. (BTW, the top three countries that produce Te are China, US and Canada). Several US, Japanese and European companies do design and post-manufacturing business of the modules. But it's not completely off to say, that the TEG market is dominated by a few non-EU producers. You don't feel the pressure? That's partly because TEG is still in a niche market compared to PV, batteries and PtX. But for us, including you my dear readers, who want to promote TEG as a unique and irreplaceable solution in the green transition, the task is tremendous. We need to:

Strategically choose the non-Te-based raw materials, which is abundant in EU.

Setup production procedures that are compatible to the European environmental and labour market legislations.

Design and setup production lines that are productive, flexible, and automated to compete with Asian producers.

To foster ecosystems in order to increase the awareness from politician, market and consumers.
The list continues.

CF: A lot of issues also common to other technologies! EU is supporting some steps out to escape these strategical limits but, as you state, the way is still long and hard to face. What is your vision for the future?

"A closing window" Thermoelectric has been a hotspot in academia for decades. And we don't have decades to catch up in commercialization. On one hand, we have competitors, solar panels (PV) being the most prominent one. You don't think so? Well, think about just 30 years ago, when the most useful application (if not the only one) for PV is the small window on a pocket calculator. Now, everyone wants PV panels on their roofs. Considering the sun is also providing heat (actually more than light, energy wise), that we potentially can use for thermal energy harvesting, PV has already taken the places. And there is no way we can take them back. On the other hand, we have nuclear power catching up, either SMRs (Small Modular Reactors) or fusion energy (I would rather believe it will take less than 50 years this time, maybe less than 30!). And even batteries(!) or some other science fiction-like solutions. Who knows which one will reduce the needs of thermoelectrics even more. When it will most likely go good for the society, it leaves us "TEGers" a closing window for commercialization.

CF: The scenario you are describing doesn't seem so promising. As the leader of a company working on thermoelectrics, do you still see a successful path for thermoelectric system? What are you planning in practice to further support and promote the growth of a market?

"Call for action" By bringing these concerns on the table, it is not to suffocate thermoelectric development by creating more constrains. On the contrary, it is the hope to set a better meaningful frame for innovation. We cannot build a car with a closed garage. By involving more people, especially stakeholders from the industry, we want to identify new applications, create new ideas, accelerate go-to-market. For that purpose, TEGnology is hosting an industrial workshop on thermoelectrics in Copenhagen on the 26th of September¹⁷. You will not only hear the latest development from several EU funded projects, but more importantly, requirements and wishes from the industry, if they are to integrate TEGs, as well as supply chains in EU. If you are interested, please preregister on the page.

Figure 77: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-026.

CONSORTIUM TOUR

We continue our tour of consortium members: in this issue, meet GEO (Austria) and MBN (Italy).

GEO UNTERWEISSACHER (GEO)¹⁸

GEO Unterweissacher GmbH is a geological consulting company based in Hochfilzen, Austria. The company's expertise extends beyond the assessment of natural hazards, hydrogeology as well as the research and analysis of geological raw materials. The company was founded over 20 years ago and has since developed into a leading expert in the field of raw materials geology.

The company GEO Unterweissacher GmbH focuses on four main pillars in its business activities: geological exploration, evaluation of raw material deposits, environmental impact assessment and consulting for companies in

the field of raw material geology. Thanks to the many years of experience and expertise of its employees, the company is able to carry out comprehensive geological investigations and make well-founded recommendations for the utilization of raw material deposits. The company has state-of-the-art laboratories and analytical equipment that enable it to examine geological samples precisely and obtain important information about the nature of raw material deposits. By using innovative technologies, the company can solve even complex geological problems and make well-founded decisions. Thomas Unterweissacher, the founder, has had a passion for historical mining ever since he was a child. His extensive knowledge of nearly every historical mine in Austria makes his company the perfect partner for the START project. With numerous mines and spoil tips scattered throughout the country, GEO Unterweissacher's ability to interpret natural signs has been invaluable in the project's success. The geology experts found several historical mine dumps, which contain the necessary mineral for creating a new and unique technological solution for thermoelectric elements.

Figure 78: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-027.

MBN Nanomaterialia (MBN)¹⁹

For over 30 years, MBN has been at the forefront of high-tech metal powder production, leveraging its proprietary Mechanomade® synthesis process to create materials with superior mechanical properties. Headquartered in Treviso, Italy, MBN operates across eight production plants, offering advanced alloy powders, nanostructured materials, ceramic-metal composites, and oxygen-sensitive materials for a range of industries. As a leader in the diamond tool industry, MBN specializes in cobalt-free, pre-alloyed metal powders. These innovative formulations enable the production of metal bonds that can be consolidated at lower temperatures and in shorter times, resulting in significant energy savings across various sintering methods, including graphite sintering, hot pressing, and HIP (Hot Isostatic Pressing).

MBN's expertise extends beyond sintering to support other cutting-edge manufacturing methods such as thermal spray deposition and additive manufacturing. MBN's approach to material development considers the final properties as a result of all the manufacturing processes that the material experiences and not only as intrinsic material characteristics. MBN's materials are designed with this concept in mind, and tested accordingly thanks to a well-equipped lab and extensive prototyping capabilities—including gravity sintering, press-sintering, and laser cladding—MBN offers customized solutions tailored to clients' specific needs, optimizing powder morphology and microstructure for superior performance.

In the START project, MBN is applying its Mechanomade® capabilities to transform mineral ore into high-performance thermoelectric materials. By mechanically alloying the tetrahedrite mineral with elements like Cu, S, Sb, Fe, Zn, and Ni, MBN can fine-tune the composition to maximize thermoelectric efficiency. The high-energy mechanical alloying process triggers the formation of tetrahedrite and incorporates dopants, creating a nanostructure that enhances thermoelectric properties by reducing thermal conductivity. The resulting tetrahedrite powder is then ready for sintering into p-type thermoelectric legs. In addition, MBN plants provide the material for the n-type legs, utilizing direct mechanical alloying of elements to create Mg₂SbBi powders. MBN's teamwork advances material performance and supports a future where efficient thermoelectric technologies can be scaled up for practical applications.

Figure 79: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-028.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- 1) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xyyf9siMpZl>
 - 2) <https://www.start-heproject.com/industrial-workshop/>
 - 3) <https://asgmi.org/en/curso-virtual-pasivos-ambientales-mineros-y-materias-primas-secundarias/>
 - 4) <https://xtract-project.eu/>
- Social Media Links:
- YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC9eNoqHV2BLXc37O_CTWfuQ
 - X (Twitter): https://twitter.com/xtract_project
 - LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/xtract-project/about/>
- CORDIS: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101138432>
- 5) <https://asgmi.org/en/asambleas-generales/>
 - 6) https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/raw-materials/week_en
 - 7) <https://www.start-heproject.com/clustering-rm-workshop/>
 - 8) <https://www.geologicalservice.eu/>
 - 9) <https://futuram.eu/>
 - 10) <https://crm-geothermal.eu/>
 - 11) <https://ciranproject.eu/>
 - 12) <https://www.supremo-project.eu/>
 - 13) <https://www.reesource.eu/>
 - 14) <http://www.reptis.eu/>
 - 15) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dhjkdH8Fybg>
 - 16) Il Bollettino, Anno 11, numero 2, Marzo-Aprile 2024. Available for members at <https://ait.icmate.cnr.it/>.
 - 17) See the relevant chapter; this interview was published before the event.
 - 18) <https://www.geo-unterweissacher.at/en/>
 - 19) <https://www.mbn.it/en/>

CONTACTS

START regularly updates its website and social media with news about its activities, but also with more general documents and info on the topics of relevance for the project. Thermoelectricity, waste heat recovery, mine waste reming, sustainability, raw materials and critical raw materials, energy efficiency, and many others.

If you are interested in receiving this newsletter and other special news from the project directly in your mailbox, consider subscribing our mailing list on the website ("Contacts" page, "subscribe" section). Clicking on the "Subscribe" button, you will fill a form generated by Brevo, our mailing system, and will subsequently receive an E-Mail to confirm your address. Your data will be treated and stored in accordance with the EU GDPR Regulation. And do not forget to follow all our social media accounts! Here is the list of the important links to click to reach our news:

Website: <https://www.start-heproject.com/>

X: https://twitter.com/START_HEproject

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/86266991/>

Twitch: https://www.twitch.tv/start_he_project

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCHVJEhpVz9uaEgzlCj2InPA>

SlideShare: <https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject/>

If you have special queries, you can contact us at the following addresses:

contact@start-heproject.com

Filipe Neves, LNEG (coordinator) filipe.neves@lneg.pt

Bruno Vicenzi, EPMA (dissemination manager) bv@epma.com

Figure 80: START-Newsletter_Issue_5-page-029.

11 ANNEX II – START ARTICLE ON “THE INNOVATION PLATFORM”

INNOVATION IN MINING | PROFILE

The START project: Transforming mining waste into waste heat recovery materials

The START project aims to produce thermoelectric devices for waste heat recovery applications from secondary mineral resources (mining waste)

THE START PROJECT is co-funded by the European Union (EU), Grant Agreement No 101058632, via its Horizon Europe programme, under the topic 'Building innovative value chains from raw materials to sustainable products' (HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-07).

It is a breakthrough project that aims to use secondary resources from mining waste and tailings to develop sustainable tellurium-free thermoelectric (TE) devices.

START approach and concept: Recovering heat from mining waste

The ultimate goal is to build an innovation ecosystem in the EU related to the production of TE devices with the highest economic efficiency suitable for use in waste heat recovery systems.

This represents an opportunity to efficiently use the EU's discarded secondary resources, reduce its waste and dependency on third countries, and offer a competitive solution for the sustainable development of renewable energy ecosystems using TE systems, in line with the

strategies outlined in the European Green Deal and the EU Action Plans on Critical Raw Materials and Circular Economy.

A TE device is a solid-state energy converter made from several TE junctions electrically connected in series that consist of n- and p-type TE semiconductor materials (Fig. 1). It converts thermal energy into electrical energy. It possesses unique attributes: No moving parts, no maintenance, quiet operation, and absence of production of environmentally deleterious mining waste.

Currently, most commercial TE devices use bismuth telluride (BiTe) or lead telluride (PbTe) as TE materials, which depend on the availability and price of tellurium. Considering, simultaneously, that China is responsible for around 60% of the world's tellurium production and the restrictive export policies it has recently adopted about certain raw materials, this dependence on tellurium-based materials becomes a huge disadvantage that hinders the large-scale implementation of TE technology in Europe.

Fig. 1: Schematic illustration of a thermoelectric device

36 | The Innovation Platform ISSUE 18 | www.innovationnewsnetwork.com

Figure 81: START article on Issue 18 of “The Innovation Platform”, June 2024, part 1.

To overcome this issue, START is proposing a solution based on the production of p-type materials that incorporate abundant sulphide minerals not currently in use, the tetrahedrite-tennantite mineral series, a copper antimony sulfosalt mineral, with generic formula $(\text{Cu, Fe})_{12}(\text{Sb, As})_4\text{S}_{13}$, which does not contain tellurium in its composition. These minerals are being collected in the respective European countries of the Geological Survey institutions included in the consortium.

The general concept of the START project is based on a 'waste material-waste heat to power' methodology (Fig. 2), which is the genesis of a completely new value chain linking secure European mineral resources and energy production. At the same time, it also contributes to the advancement of scientific knowledge and technological innovation in the field of thermoelectrics, as well as promoting a decarbonised society.

within the EU. This will substantially contribute to the main expected impact of Cluster 4 ('Industrial leadership and increased autonomy in key strategic value chains') of the Horizon Europe Programme. It is then expected to impact several areas significantly, as explained below.

For the environment, START plans to reprocess sulphide-containing mining residues, thereby reducing the environmental impact of mining activities by remediating potential acid mine drainage while preventing the loss of valuable resources currently ending up in mine tailings.

START will address the sustainable supply of raw materials, securing a reliable supply of raw materials for green technologies and, more specifically, for TE applications, as it aims to replace the current TE materials (BiTe and PbTe) and produce tellurium-free TE devices based on tetrahedrite. This mineral in START is being sourced from European mining sites.

Regarding materials and technology innovation, START is using scalable and cost-effective methods for producing high-quality p-type tetrahedrite powder materials that will be assembled into the TE devices. The production of tetrahedrite powders by High-Energy Ball Milling has already been scaled up to pre-pilot capacity. Innovations in assembling TE modules for demonstration are also being adopted.

Fig. 2: START project concept based on 'waste material-waste heat to power' methodology

START outcomes

START will have many outcomes. By creating an innovative, flexible, scalable, adaptable mineral-derived value chain for TE devices based on raw materials that are readily available in Europe, START will create a new rapid-growth commercial ecosystem that will attract new stakeholders exploiting market opportunities for replication and market development.

In fact, this will be a new market opportunity for European mineral resources, converting discarded waste secondary sulphide materials available in Europe into useful and valuable mineral resources, boosting EU competitiveness on raw materials through the recycling of such mining waste, fostering the transition to a greener society and economy through eco-innovation, and promoting energy security.

START impact

START strengthens and expands the European raw materials supply sector by replacing a key component of thermoelectric (TE) devices with new materials sourced

The goal of promoting the development of a sustainable society is pursued by several dissemination and communication activities about the project aims and topics to inform about the benefits and potential of the TE technology and the importance of ensuring secure, sustainable and competitive supply chains for green technologies in Europe. The project has also started a benchmark analysis of life cycle assessment (LCA) and life cycle costing (LCC) studies to evaluate the environmental and economic impacts of its TE devices compared to conventional ones.

Thus, the START project also contributes to the UN Sustainable Development Goals 7 (affordable and clean energy), 9 (industry, innovation and infrastructure) and 11 (sustainable cities and communities) and to the implementation of the actions of the EU Action Plan on Critical Raw Materials outlined in Fig. 3.

START main achievements during the first 15 months

In accordance with the specific objectives planned, START already obtained some important results.

Figure 82: START article on Issue 18 of "The Innovation Platform", June 2024, part 2.

INNOVATION IN MINING | PROFILE

Fig. 3: Actions of the EU Action Plan on Critical Raw Materials to which START contributes

of three free webinars on project activities, whose videos are accessible on START's YouTube channel (more are being organised in 2024), and the multilingual comic storyboard 'Starty explains START', where Starty, a robot character, addresses and explains the project topics in an easily understandable way.

Concerning the objective of developing a resilient and sustainable raw materials supply chain for the TE technology, first of all, donor sites containing mineralogically suitable sulphide minerals for producing the p-type semiconductor thermoelement were identified in various historical European mines, based on: The volume of sulphides; the presence and content of tetrahedrite; and accessibility and logistical issues. Sampling protocol methodologies have been established that follow a scientifically sound approach to sample collection and subsequent treatment.

Based on this, several hundred kilogrammes of discarded mining waste sulphides were collected. Tetrahedrite-rich concentrates from these minerals were successfully processed via High Energy Ball Milling (HEBM) in a pre-pilot scale (300g batches) to produce kilogramme-scale batches of mineral-derived tetrahedrite p-type powder materials incorporating different amounts of synthetic material to adjust the composition. Spark Plasma Sintering subsequently achieves the production of mineral-derived tetrahedrite p-type thermoelements. Work is progressing to optimise the composition, performance, and maximum amount of mineral concentrate that can be added to the initial mixture simultaneously. At the same time, a compatible n-type TE material was identified.

Based on simulated performances, two applications for the TE devices have been defined: Combined heat and power (CHP) and low-grade waste heat from heavy industry. Work is underway to assemble the first TE device of the START project.

To define the commercial ecosystem and business environment, a comprehensive analysis towards benchmarking the life cycle assessment (LCA) and life cycle costing (LCC) studies to measure the environmental and economic performance of the TE devices has started. The first component of the prospective exercise, i.e., focus groups, was initiated to assess the market perspective and social acceptance. A first-round Delphi Survey was prepared.

Dissemination/communication activities were carried out, including the publication of a biannual project newsletter entitled 'RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE for a Sustainable Future' (available on START's website), the organisation

START Consortium

The START project is co-ordinated by LNEG, a Portuguese public research and development institution. It brings together a total of 15 partners (Fig. 4) from ten EU countries and one associated country, including: Six research organisations with strong knowledge of geology, materials science and renewable energies; seven SMEs that cover the entire supply chain from production to exploitation and ecological footprint assessment; and two non-profit international associations with a wide network of partners and stakeholders.

Fig. 4: The START consortium

Disclaimer
Co-Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Filipe Neves
START Project Coordinator
LNEG - Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia, I.P.

Bruno Vicenzi
START Dissemination Manager
European Powder Metallurgy Association

Figure 83: START article on Issue 18 of "The Innovation Platform", June 2024, part 3.